

The Institutional complexity of a Religious Microfinance
institution: A case study of an Islamic Microfinance
Institution (Akhuwat)

Submitted by

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Abstract

The research aim of the study was to examine the institutional complexity of a religious microfinance institution, which includes a case study of an Islamic microfinance institution (Akhuwat). The world remains as religious as it was. However, despite the spread of secularisation efforts and ideology, religion has continued to play a vital role in both societal life and the personal lives of individuals, and it is also one of the six core logics of institutional logics. The importance of religion in everyday life and management literature is significant, and it is surprising to see the dearth of research on religion in management literature. The research conducted on this topic is inadequate, and no in-depth analysis is available, given the topic's importance.

The focus of this study is on a case study of a religious microfinance institution (Akhuwat). Islamic microfinance organisation Akhuwat is unique for this research, as its operations are based on institutional complexity in a long-term environment. Initially, Akhuwat was a non-profit organisation; religion and social welfare were the only institutional logics that influenced it, but due to its collaboration with Meezan Bank, it is now also influenced by the logic of commerce. This study employed a thematic literature review to highlight religion as an institutional logic, with a brief history of organisations experiencing institutional complexity and a discussion of different models of conventional and Islamic microfinance. The study examined the use of multiple logics by a religious organisation and its response to experiencing institutional complexity, using 14 closed-ended semi-structured interviews. It also investigated its role in alleviating poverty, employing 385 questionnaires from microentrepreneurs. To fulfil the objectives, a honeycomb was used as a research method, and a case study was employed as the research design.

Research findings indicate that Islamic microfinance organisations have been historically drawn to specific institutional logics. The dominance of those logics has significantly changed over time, resulting in the standardisation of the organisation, in this case through the Shariah board, to remain Shariah compliant and remain religious. Findings show that more than three institutional logics influence Akhuwat and may increase to more than five due to the offering of new Islamic microfinance products to microentrepreneurs. Descriptive analysis indicates that Akhuwat is making a significant impact on poverty alleviation through its Islamic microfinance products. Akhuwat's organisational response to facing institutional complexity has surprisingly surpassed and contradicted previous research. The more institutional logics it is influenced by, the better the performance due to robust practices, which Shariah defines.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

GDP- Gross Domestic Product

IAS International Accounting Standards

IFI Islamic Financial Institution

IFRS International Financial Reporting Standards

IFSB Islamic Financial Services Board

ILP Institutional Logics Perspective

IMF International Monetary Fund

IMFI Islamic Microfinance Institution

IRP Islamic Relief Pakistan

ISRA International Shariah Research Academy for Islamic Finance

KCB Karakoram Cooperative Bank

MASB Malaysian Accounting Standards Board

MENA Middle East and North Africa

MFI Microfinance Institutions

MIA Malaysian Institute of Accountants

SAC Shariah Advisory Council

SSB Shariah Supervisory Board

WB World Bank

WTO World Trade Organisation

Chapter 1 Introduction

Background of the research

There is a scarcity of empirical and theoretical research emphasising many elements of microfinance institutions (MFIs) around the world, including their social and financial performance. Researchers employed various methods and statistical tools to assess the effectiveness of these organisations, particularly over the last 30 years. The literature on MFIs accessible worldwide can be broadly classified into two main groups. In the first set of studies, the social and financial success of these organisations is measured by several indicators, including sustainability, portfolio quality, efficiency, and asset and liability management. The second set is focused on the social performance of these organisations, which is also explained and analysed. This research focuses on the second type of literature. This section of the report contains a review of several related research papers (Farooq & Khan, 2014).

As a result, there is a growing interest in examining the behavioural, social, and cultural dimensions of IMFI, or, in other terms, understanding IMFI as an integral component of a broader system that influences and is influenced by various elements and components within that system.

Religion has been considered a significant component influencing the development of an Islamic microfinance organisation. This phenomenon occurs because religions are associated with specific values and ethical standards that their adherents are expected to uphold throughout various aspects of life, including commerce.

Islam, being one of the world's major religions, encompasses a wide range of socioeconomic concepts. These principles are likely to impact the accounting system in Muslim-majority cultures, as accounting serves as a mechanism for reflecting on and reporting the economic activities of individuals and organisations within those societies.

The rise and acceptance of the Islamic finance industry have significantly driven this study trend. The industry has generated an immediate demand for a financial reporting framework that allows Islamic financial institutions (IFIs) to convey the Shariah compliance of their operations to various stakeholders and addresses accounting issues unique to these entities that are not addressed by conventional accounting standards. Islamic accounting scholars and practitioners have advocated for the establishment of a specialised framework to tackle these challenges and standardise the accounting processes of Islamic Financial Institutions (IFIs)

(see, for instance, Abdel-Magid 1981, Karim 1990, Gambling and Karim 1991, Ibrahim 2000a). Some scholars have expanded these calls, advocating for the development of a comprehensive framework that addresses the informational requirements of Muslim societies and all business entities, both financial and non-financial, operating in alignment with Islamic principles.

Researchers have conducted several studies to explore the various aspects of these projects and their impact on the financial reporting standards of International Financial Institutions (IFIs). Although the significance of these projects has been recognised by certain studies (Karim 1990, Karim 1999, Vinni Combe 2010, Mohammed et al. 2016), they have faced considerable criticism from others for their failure to transcend conventional accounting practices and ideologies (Maurer 2002, Yaya 2004, Kamla 2009, Ibrahim and Siswanto 2013, Levy and Rezgui 2015, Kamla and Haque 2017). Nevertheless, minimal research has been conducted to comprehend the contextual environments and institutional requirements influencing these projects and their decisions regarding the most suitable approach to standardising Islamic financial reporting (Abdelkader & Salem, 2013).

The historical fulfilment of specific institutional demands for these projects in establishing their objectives remains ambiguous. Furthermore, there is a lack of research elucidating the rationale behind the diverse techniques employed by these programs, despite their purported alignment in pursuing a common purpose under similar institutional pressures. Organisational studies focus on comprehending the role of players immersed in specific institutional logics (Thornton et al. 2012), who serve as representatives of these logics in influencing their organisations' policies (Pache & Santos, 2010).

Nevertheless, the influence of participants and their integration within specific institutional contexts on Islamic financial microfinance initiatives remains largely unexplored. This gap in the literature highlights the need for further investigation into how these participants negotiate their roles and the implications of their interactions for the development of standardised frameworks. Understanding these dynamics can provide valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities that arise in the context of Islamic.

1.1 Islamic Micro Finance

Microfinance, which aims to meet the financial needs of the impoverished, has recently evolved to help alleviate poverty worldwide. This industry attracts the interest of various stakeholders, including scholars, practitioners, government officials, and lenders. Islamic microfinance must

take bold steps to fulfil consumers' growing demand in the Muslim world and help the needy meet their financial needs. Islamic microfinance organisations function by implementing the values of Islamic teachings. These ideals include monotheism, the application of Shariah maqashid, the prohibition of usury, maintaining justice, eradicating injustice, and disregarding the gambling component in financial transactions. Purchase and sale agreements (bai' al-murabahah), lease-based deals (al-ijarah), business cooperation arrangements (al-musharakah, al-mudharabah), and interest-free loans (qardh-hasan) are now in use at Islamic microfinance institutions. Islamic microfinance institutions have experienced significant growth over the past few decades, albeit at a slower pace than conventional microfinance institutions. Research on Shariah microfinance organisations has grown in tandem with the development of Islamic microfinance institutions. Research into Islamic microfinance institutions is deemed necessary to investigate their limitations and advantages, to find explanations and policies for addressing the difficulties faced by IMFI. Therefore, all of this bodes well for the present and future expansion of Islamic microfinance organisations.

1.2 Scope of the Study of Islamic Microfinance

People experiencing poverty are those with very modest incomes and have very few resources, and others have none. Furthermore, individuals are not given access to loans made available by financial institutions. This arises because poor individuals lack collateral, which is required for financial organisations to provide loans. They also have a low level of financial literacy. The poor need assistance to rise above the poverty level. The growth of financial services is crucial to the social and economic well-being of households, particularly those from low-income backgrounds. Loans from the impoverished may generate revenue, boost local transactions, and generate supply and demand for services and goods in their own economy at any rate (Abdelkader & Salem, 2013). Consequently, many financial organisations may refuse to allow low-income individuals to engage in and access their services because they are perceived as being incapable of servicing their loans. There is little profit that can be made from destitute people (Rokhman, 2014). As a result, a poor household will eventually experience financial difficulties and get trapped in the poverty cycle.

Microfinance is one of the most effective instruments for low-income individuals to improve their livelihoods by providing small loans to businesses. It is praised as a powerful tool for helping poor people get out of poverty and help their economies grow. Numerous studies have been conducted to examine the economic and social consequences of microfinance, particularly

on its borrowers or clients, with mixed results. Furthermore, microfinance is regarded as an alternative for women's empowerment, with numerous studies investigating the influence or interaction of microfinance with women's empowerment. According to (Moll, 2011), three components of microfinance affect the poor, namely an improvement in their ability to consume, produce, and invest.

Microfinance institutions are depicted as a solution to the issue of poverty. Microfinance organisations can provide microloans to micro and small businesses. Credit services are available to the impoverished and the poor at the bottom of the pyramid just as they are to all other individuals. It is anticipated that by utilising this credit facility, people will be able to launch new businesses as a source of additional income. Additionally, the poor use credit services to pay for daily necessities like food, drink, education, and wedding expenses. Nevertheless, traditional microfinance organisations have not been able to tackle the issue of poverty, especially among Muslims. Traditional microfinance firms continue to use interest as a component of usury, which is one of the reasons why they persist in using interest. In addition, there are still banned components of microfinance institution transactions, including maysir and gharar. So, Islamic microfinance institutions are meant to help the poor people who are still a big part of the Muslim population (Begum, et al., 2019).

In terms of both economic development and social welfare, microfinance has a substantial positive impact on most borrowers. Although microfinance is a technique that can help alleviate poverty, numerous studies have highlighted concerns about the severely poor population, who have historically been overlooked. As a result, Islamic finance plays a significant part in overcoming this difficulty. If the main goal is to improve social welfare, microfinance and Islamic finance cannot be separated. Some research has emphasised the importance of ethics in microfinance. Also, Islamic microfinance has shown that it can deal with a wide range of activities and levels of poverty, especially extreme poverty, through its many forms and structures. As a result, this will gradually create a platform for microfinance institution viability. Nonetheless, the emergence of Islamic microfinance, which has a vast potential market, could not be compared to a conventional loan. Most Islamic microfinance organisations are in a few countries. As a result, Islamic microfinance be utilised as an alternative to enhance the living conditions of poor people in all developing nations, regardless of their religious affiliation. Moreover, since the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015 were established by United Nations, with the aim of fulfilling them by 2030, poverty

elimination has been a clarion call. Many poor Muslim countries require significant initiatives and reforms.

Many studies have shown that to accomplish the SDGs, Islamic finance might make a significant contribution. Several SDGs can be met with Islamic microfinance, focusing on combating poverty, improving health services and education, increasing access to clean water and sanitation, and reducing gender inequality in many poor Muslim nations. As a result, through various creative products and tools, Islamic microfinance would become an important measure in accomplishing the SDGs. Even though it's unlikely that poor Muslim countries would be able to implement Islamic microfinance in a limited period of time experience, money, and other assets, If there is strong political will and rapid, ambitious effort, it is still possible. (Mohamed & Fauziyyah, 2020)

1.3 Islamic Microfinance Institutions in Pakistan

Pakistan ranks 40th on the International Monetary Fund's 2019 list of poorest countries. Its per-capita GDP is \$1,541. This list includes the GDP per capita of 187 nations. Microfinance organisations, especially Islamic ones, help alleviate poverty in Pakistan. The Micro Watch Report showed an increase in microcredit outreach in Pakistan. However, Akhuwat (the leading Islamic microfinance provider) maintained the highest microfinance distribution in 2017, with 820,000 active borrowers.

Several studies have been conducted to assess the success of the Akhuwat Foundation in terms of its long-term viability, customer service, borrower conditions, its role in combating poverty, and its business strategy.

Islamic microfinance is considered an appropriate model for raising finance from the poor in many Muslim countries, such as Pakistan, Indonesia, and Malaysia, because it offers both social capital and social intermediation, along with Islamic ideals. Techniques of social intermediation incorporate capacity building and financial intermediation. The finest example of how to fund small businesses or farmers is by educating them. Islamic microfinance aims to provide financial opportunities to the poorest of the poor in society, including the informal sector, and is primarily supported by the third sector of the economy, such as compulsory Islamic taxes (Zakah) and charitable contributions (Sadaqah and Infaq).

In conformity with Islamic teachings, Islamic microfinance offers money to qualified individuals without charging interest. Along with financial services, Islamic microfinance encourages social services in the shape of Sadaqah, Zakah, and Infaq to help people cleanse their wealth and gain Allah's favour by serving the needs of the poor. Microfinance began in Pakistan in 1970, when the government gave loans to people who needed them at a lower interest rate. In 1982, two non-governmental organisations, AKRSP and OPP, began operations in Pakistan. Microfinance services were launched by NRSP in 1992 and network leasing in 1994. On the advice of the provincial government, the Bank of Khyber began providing microfinance services in 1995. Pakistan's first microfinance bank was established in 2002. Several institutions in Pakistan have offered Islamic microfinance programmes in recent years. There are two organisations: the Wasil Foundation, which offers Shariah-compliant goods such as Ijarah, Mudarbah, Diminishing Musharakah, and Istisna, and Akhuwat, which follows Qard Hassan principles.

The condition of Islamic microfinance in Pakistan today demonstrates that existing Islamic microfinance services still have a way to go to tap into this specialised market. There is a demand for nationwide geographic distribution as well as a range of items that may satisfy the requirements of the target market. Islamic microfinance has a significant supply and demand mismatch that cannot be fully explained by contributions and government funding alone (Brandsma & Hart, 2002). With these funds, only the start-up costs of new Islamic microfinance institutions, like Human Development, can be subsidised and paid for. The only way to fix the supply-demand gap in Islamic microfinance is for these institutes to be able to take care of themselves. (Arif & Wahab, 2016)

1.4 Microfinance in the Islamic Tradition: Pakistan's Urgent Need

Muslims only make up 24 per cent of the world's population, but they are responsible for half of the world's destitute. Microfinance accounts for less than 1% of the Islamic financial sector. Both forced and self-imposed isolation from the banking system limit microfinance's reach. Supply-side MFIs cause involuntary exclusion because of high transaction costs and the absence of collateral, while voluntary exclusion is caused by religious concerns. In Pakistan, 58.7 million people live in multidimensional poverty, with 18% of urban households and 46% of the rural population living below the poverty line. Even though there are an estimated 50 million poor people in Pakistan, only about 3 million of them are receiving microfinance services (Arif & Wahab, 2016).

1.5 Microfinance as a technique for alleviating poverty

Through microfinance institutions, the core goal of reducing poverty can be realised. The ultimate purpose of these institutions is to give less expensive loans to the impoverished than informal and legal financial institutions. A microfinance institution is an essential tool for achieving the Millennium Development Goals. According to Shirazi and Khan's research, microfinance is the most efficient method for increasing social welfare and eliminating poverty. Additionally, microfinance seeks to increase long-term income. Most studies undertaken on this subject revealed that microenterprise does not provide viable solutions for alleviation of poverty; rather, it is most valuable for individuals living close to the poverty line. The goal of alleviating poverty through microfinance can only be accomplished if the impoverished have access to financial services. The component of trust and commitment is vital for establishing a good rapport between customers and microfinance companies (MFI). By establishing a community-based framework for MFIs, the eradication of poverty through microfinance can be done at a realistic level. The issue of nonperforming loans in MFIs can be resolved by assessing the creditworthiness of borrowers. In addition, MFIs must raise the awareness of the impoverished in order to reach them.

Most academic research reveals a good correlation between microfinance and poverty reduction. According to one study conducted by Imai et al., the accessibility of microfinance has a favourable effect on multidimensional welfare indices, ultimately leading to the eradication of poverty. The outcomes vary across rural and urban regions. Government and non-government organisations have distinct impacts on poverty in Bangladesh. Government organisations (GOs) are more effective than non-governmental organisations (NGOs) in providing access to wealth for multiple hands. Specifically, NGOs are concerned with repayment schedules, interest rates, and loan distribution to the poor, whereas GOs are concerned with the outcome of a program.

According to other studies conducted in Pakistan and Bangladesh indicate that MFIs can reduce poverty when donor organisations, MFIs, and the government collaborate. Similarly, according to Imai et al., nations with higher microfinance loan portfolios per capita have lower poverty metrics. In practice, microfinance reduces the severity and intensity of poverty as measured by its indices. Thus, Imai et al.'s conclusions provide solid suggestions for governments, mostly in industrialised nations where subsidised credit is dispersed via MFIs. In addition, these funds contribute to the enhancement of children's education and family income. In addition to improving family income, access to microfinance also improves family health and diet. The

practice of MFIs in Indonesia demonstrates the effectiveness of microfinance in combating poverty (Ahmed, 2007).

In Indonesia, the establishment of MFIs such as Bank Rakyat and several NGOs satisfied the enormous unmet need for financial services in underprivileged areas. Numerous studies demonstrate a beneficial relationship between poverty alleviation and microfinance; however, a study presented in Sri Lanka showed significantly divergent results. Microfinance programme development must contribute to physical infrastructure and social investment. To get favourable outcomes from microfinance initiatives, international donors and the government must invest in capital expenditures to address the affordability and accessibility of rural financial services. Microfinance does not positively affect the degree of poverty due to financial constraints caused by poverty traps, higher indebtedness, and poorer debt capacity (Gehlich-Shillabeer, 2008). MFIs' deprived infrastructure and inexperienced personnel lead to their indebtedness. These conditions are obstacles for MFIs seeking to reduce the incidence of low-credit recovery.

Microfinance is widely recognised as a financial development tool for individuals deprived of access to financial services, particularly women. However, the literature provides conflicting evidence, showing that women's empowerment may not, or may only be partially achieved, through microcredit, especially in Muslim societies. This study aims to examine the impact of Amanah Ikhtiar Malaysia (AIM), a microcredit institution, on Malay Muslim women in an urban setting. A quasi-experimental method was used to conduct a cross-sectional survey of 500 old and new clients. Informal semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 current clients who had received microcredit two years earlier. The findings show that AIM microcredit empowered the women and enhanced gender equality. It enabled women to access financial capital, form their micro- and small-businesses and obtain an income which helped them to contribute to household expenditure. Even though the effect of microcredit was partial, it provided them with bargaining power for decision-making and controlling of resources and enhanced their self-esteem in their households and communities (Al-Shami, et al., 2016).

Islamic microfinance organisations offer a variety of poverty alleviation programmes. Khaleeq-uz-review zaman's offered alternative poverty alleviation mechanisms for Islamic MFIs. The golden ideals of Islam establish a mechanism of confidence amid consumers and MFIs. In Bangladesh, other studies have examined the microcredit programmes of Islamic banks and concluded that such programmes are conducive to the improvement of the living

circumstances of the poor, as well as socioeconomic growth. There is an urgent need to merge Islamic microfinance institutions with commercial banks to increase the poor's access to credit. However, it is challenging to connect these two institutions in the contemporary day. To bypass this obstacle, Dusuki's research advocates the use of specialised vehicles to transfer funds from Islamic banks to the impoverished. The participation of SPVs will make up for the inability of MFIs to defend Islamic banks (Ahmad, et al., 2020).

Moreover, the participatory schemes of musharakah and mudharabah can address the need for risk sharing among the poor. The primary purpose of Islamic microfinance institutions is to eradicate poverty by Islamic ethical values such as responsibility, free will, balance, and oneness. The clearest example can be found in India, where a Muslim NGO has launched programmes to alleviate poverty by integrating Islamic MFIs into profit-generating industries (Hossain, 2019). In addition to Waqaf and Zakah, an essential instrument for reducing poverty is coverage for the risk of default by impoverished borrowers and poverty-alleviating expenses. Moreover, improving capability and care has contributed to the reduction of poverty. Thus, microfinance institutions (MFIs) not only assist the poor by extending credit to them but also provide additional services that contribute to poverty alleviation (Abdelkader & Salem, 2013).

1.6 Importance and Contribution of the Research

The Islamic financial sector has undergone significant expansion since its establishment in the early 1960s. The World Bank indicates that this sector achieves an annual growth rate of 10-12%, with current projections of Sharia-compliant financial assets amounting to US\$2 trillion. In many Muslim-majority countries, this sector has been growing more swiftly than conventional finance, asserting itself as the primary economic system. Interest in Islamic finance has recently proliferated in non-Muslim countries, such as the UK, Luxembourg, South Africa, and Hong Kong (Disli & Jalaly, 2024).

Islamic Financial Institutions (IFIs) derive their legitimacy in the market by functioning as Shariah-compliant financial entities. Annual reports function as an essential tool for international financial institutions communicate the Shariah compliance of their operations to stakeholders, particularly shareholders and clients. The lack of financial reporting regulations or guidelines for Islamic Financial Institutions to demonstrate their adherence to Shariah in their operations is acknowledged as detrimental to the credibility of these institutions. Initiatives for standardised Islamic financial reporting have made considerable efforts in recent decades to meet the needs of the Islamic financial sector in terms of relevant standards and

guidelines. Consequently, we must acknowledge the influence of these projects on the Islamic financial industry and its growth and in this case, Islamic microfinance organisations. This study is essential for its effort to attain a profound understanding of these initiatives, the institutional logics that have influenced the shaping of their policies and established their standards and regulations, and the historical challenges they have faced. Consequently, undertaking this research would significantly augment the current corpus of knowledge (Alawode, 2015).

This research will enhance the financial reporting practices of international financial institutions by offering pertinent policy implications and recommendations. Moreover, global financial institutions (IFIs) currently exemplify the primary entities operating in compliance with Shariah law.

This research contributes to various fields of literature, with a primary focus on the influence of institutional logics on Islamic microfinance and its response towards facing multiple logics. It contributes to the field of organisational studies by examining how organisations behave in a situation of institutional complexity to achieve the same goals. Conducting a study in the unique domain of Islamic financial microfinance, facing multiple logics while trying to alleviate poverty, presents an intriguing opportunity.

This study advances the expanding literature by employing the institutional logics approach as a theoretical framework. Friedland and Alford (1991), along with Thornton et al. (2012), identified religion as one of the institutional orders that comprise the 'interinstitutional system'. However, their identification was limited to a specific context, namely the influence of Christianity in the Western world. Thornton et al. (2012) acknowledge that this narrow perspective reflects a significant bias. They argue that the impact of religion may be even more pronounced in other societies. Thus, this study is crucial as it underscores the role of Islam in shaping specific practices, such as Islamic microfinance organisations, in a region of the world that is not Western (Thornton, et al., 2012).

1.7 Research Aim

This study seeks to examine the intricate institutional dynamics faced by the religious microfinance organisation, Akhuwat. This study will examine the impact of religious beliefs on the organization's identity, analyse the management of multiple institutional logics, and

evaluate its efficacy in alleviating poverty and improving client well-being. This objective involves a comprehensive examination of how religious beliefs influence the identity and operational practices of Islamic microfinance institutions within a multifaceted institutional structure.

1.8 Research Objectives

The objective of the study is to find The Institutional complexity of a Religious Microfinance institution through a case study (Akhuwat). The aims of the study are as follows:

1. To explore religion as an institutional logic and its role in shaping the organisational identity of an Islamic microfinance organisation.
2. To explore the response of an Islamic microfinance organisation towards multiple institutional logics while experiencing institutional complexity.
3. To investigate the performance of Islamic microfinance organisations, their effects on poverty alleviation and the welfare of their clients.

1.9 Research Questions

The following are the study's research questions:

1. What is the role of religion as an institutional logic in determining the organisational identity of an Islamic microfinance organisation?
2. How does an Islamic microfinance organisation alleviate poverty and also respond to multiple institutional logics while experiencing institutional complexity?

Research Question 1 is related to Research Objective 1, and Research Question 2 is related to Research Objectives 2 and 3.

1.10 Thesis Structure Outlined

This thesis is organised into seven chapters as represented in Figure 1 below which depicts the link between the chapters.

Chapter 1: This chapter is an introduction. It provides a summary of the research, highlighting its aim, scope, significance, and contribution, and demonstrating the thesis's structure.

Chapter 2: This chapter provides an extensive examination of the literature on institutional logic, institutional complexity, and organisational responses. It begins by discussing the contentious issue of the applicability of a single set of accounting standards across various countries, settings, and sectors. This chapter reviews the literature that advocates for the creation of a framework to meet the financial reporting requirements of Islamic law. It also examines the debate over whether alternative methods are suitable for building such a framework. The chapter thereafter presents a critical analysis of the literature related to specific initiatives aimed at developing Islamic accounting standards. Finally, this chapter identifies gaps in the study and concludes by listing the research goals and questions that this thesis seeks to address and contribute to the existing body of work.

Chapter 3: This chapter introduces the Institutional Logics Perspective (ILP) as a theoretical and analytical framework for this thesis. This section provides an overview of the concepts, principles, and assumptions underlying ILP, clarifying the framework's relationship to the thesis objectives and its practical application.

Chapter 4: This chapter outlines the philosophical and methodological stance adopted in the thesis. Furthermore, it outlines the research strategy, along with the methodology for data collection and analysis. This chapter, in conjunction with the theoretical framework chapter, establishes the groundwork for the empirical research detailed in the subsequent chapters.

Chapter 5: This chapter examines the themes derived from the semi structured interviews using NVivo.

Chapter 6: This chapter aims to provide a descriptive analysis of the questionnaire to investigate the influence of Islamic microfinance on

Chapter 7: This chapter acts as the conclusion. It reiterates the research context and summarises the key findings, offering conclusions that address the research questions. The study outlines both its empirical and theoretical contributions, highlighting the policy consequences and significance.

This chapter discusses the study's limitations and concludes by offering potential future research areas.

1.11 Summary

This chapter summarises the first phase of the research on Islamic Microfinance Institutions (IMFI). It provides a comprehensive overview of the study's background, scope, significance, and structure.

The chapter opens by discussing the lack of empirical and theoretical research on the social and financial performance of microfinance institutions (MFIs), particularly in the context of Islamic finance. The research is divided into two categories: studies investigating financial performance (including sustainability and efficiency) and studies evaluating social performance. This study is on how Islamic principles affect the operations of Islamic Microfinance Institutions (IMFIs) within a broader social and cultural context.

Scope of the Study:

This chapter explores how Islamic financing can benefit disadvantaged individuals, particularly those without collateral or prior experience with traditional financial services. It emphasises the importance of microfinance in improving the economic situations of the poor, with a focus on women's empowerment.

This study is significant because it investigates the operational dynamics of IMFIs, namely the interaction between religious beliefs and organisational identity. The chapter emphasises the growing need for comprehensive rules that define Shariah compliance and meet the unique reporting requirements of IMFIs. This study aims to contribute to existing knowledge in multiple domains, including organisational studies and Islamic finance, by examining the distinct institutional logics that influence Islamic microfinance institutions (IMFIs) and their responses to complex settings.

Research Purpose & Goals:

The chapter clearly articulates the study's primary purpose, which is to investigate the institutional challenges faced by Akhuwat, a well-established Islamic microfinance institution. The study emphasises on defining the role of religion on organisational identity, investigating reactions to diverse institutional logics, and assessing the effectiveness of IMFIs in reducing poverty.

Two main research questions emerge: the impact of religious beliefs on the identification of IMFIs and their function in poverty alleviation within the context of institutional complexity. The chapter concludes by outlining the thesis structure and organising the following chapters,

which include a literature review, theoretical framework, methodology, empirical analysis, and conclusions.

This chapter establishes a solid foundation for the thesis, paving the way for a thorough examination of the institutional logics affecting Islamic microfinance practices and their consequences for socioeconomic development.

Chapter 2: Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Introduction

This chapter presents a systematic literature review and hypothesis development. The discussion begins by developing a hypothesis, using the research objectives and research questions as a guide, and provides a rationale for the hypotheses that are created.

The chapter is then divided into two parts. The first part of the chapter presents an overview of previous studies related to institutional logic, the role of religion in shaping institutional logic, institutional complexity, and an organisation's response to institutional complexity. The second part focuses on reviewing the literature that emphasises the necessity of meeting Islamic microfinance requirements and the financial reporting needs of Islamic Financial Institutions (IFIs). The study examines conventional microfinance, different models of Islamic microfinance and Islamic guidance that form the basis of these models. This chapter concludes by outlining the research objectives and questions that this study aims to address. A critical discussion of both sections of the literature review helps to test the hypothesis. The mentioned terminologies are described along with their background in this chapter.

Hypothesis Development

When formulating hypotheses for a study on the beneficial correlation between Islamic microfinance (IMF) and poverty alleviation, as well as client welfare, it is essential to base them on current literature and the distinctive tenets of Islamic finance. Tamanni and Besar (2019) demonstrated that Islamic microfinance institutions have remained committed to their poverty alleviation objectives, albeit with enhanced financial strategies. Moreover, literature indicates that Islamic microfinance may serve as a lasting option for poverty alleviation and offer economic advantages for livelihoods (Begum, et al., 2019). It can address a substantial demographic of those who are unable to utilise traditional microfinance due to their religious convictions concerning interest.

Consequently, the Islamic economic system may serve as a practical framework for economic progress by eschewing interest. This literature has led to the following hypothesis:

H1: The organisational identity of Akhuwat, as an Islamic microfinance institution, is significantly influenced by the institutional logic of religion and acts as a guiding force for its mission, practices, and stakeholder interactions.

Rationale: This hypothesis suggests that religion influences both the ethical framework and operational principles of the organisation, while also shaping its identity among stakeholders, including clients and the wider community.

Additionally, Islamic microfinance streamlines the repayment process and advises creditors to offer charity when surplus money is available. Mahmood et al. (2017) identified a positive correlation between Islamic microfinance and poverty alleviation. This report recommends that the Government of Pakistan formulate a policy for Islamic microfinance in collaboration with the State Bank of Pakistan. Sofi and Sumaira (2016) have elucidated the shortcomings of the two predominant systems, capitalism and communism, and proposed Islamic economic systems as an alternative, highlighting the contentious issue of Ribā prohibition. Capitalism has overlooked economic and social justice, while communism has arisen as a formidable force. The IMF provides funding to micro-enterprises (e.g., via Murabaha and Musharakah), enabling clients to initiate or develop their firms, thereby enhancing their revenue and, ultimately, household income (Malik, 2024).

Hypothesis for Research Question 2 (Related to Research Objectives 2 and 3):

H2: Akhuwat exhibits a dynamic adaptation to various institutional logics, effectively balancing religious imperatives with market-oriented practices and social welfare objectives, thereby enhancing its performance in poverty alleviation and the overall welfare of its clients.

Rationale: This hypothesis suggests that the organisation does not simply succumb to institutional complexity but actively navigates it. The balancing act between various logics (such as religious, social, and economic) leads to innovative practices that enhance both organisational performance and client welfare.

These hypotheses provide a foundational framework for the research, guiding data collection and analysis as the study explores the institutional complexity of the religious microfinance institution.

2.1 Discussion of Institutional logic and Institutional complexity

Institutional logic

Institutional logic, also known as societal logic, was introduced by Friedland and Alfred in 1991 and got a lot of attention from scholars. These institutional logics are revised by Thornton, Lounsbury and Ocasio (2012) to amend the collection of societal logic, which includes logics such as family, community, religion, state, market, profession, and business. They are principles that infer an organisation's reality, what can be appropriate behaviour, and how success could be achieved. Institutional logic was initially presented to conceive the influence

on individual and organisational behaviour through some of the major institutions of Western society, such as the family, religion, market, democracy, and state. (Lounsbury, 2007)

Logics are characterised as socially built, historically significant sequences of material activities, assumptions, values, beliefs, and rules by which people make and reproduce their material sustenance, organise time and space, and give meaning to their social reality. Institutional logics exemplify the references that ease the sense-making of actors, their use of language to drive action, and their foundation of legitimacy in terms of a sense of self and identity. Meanwhile, their belief system provides recommendations for action. They are also a cultural belief system that implies specific guidelines and gives directions in different social situations (Bridwell-Mitchell & Sherer, 2017). Therefore, institutional logic delivers a structure of demand for actors, helping them to define the problems that need to be addressed and how to know what is essential and how to evaluate situations while ultimately learning how to behave. Institutional logic depicts ‘the implicit relationship between means and ends. (Hustedt & Danken, 2017)

The goals of an organisation and practices are reflections of institutional logic, and they are accessible to representatives of organisations in the form of reflections and understandings. As social agents, representatives are based in cultural, organisational, and political institutions that determine identities and organisational objectives. (Thornton, et al., 2012). It has been observed that the most important institutional orders of contemporary western society each have a central logic, such as the logic of capitalism, the state, democracy, family, and religion (Friedland & Alford 1991). The Organizational fields have been believed to have their logic immersed within a societal-level institutional order (Goodrick & Reay, 2011), whereas logic is conceptualised hierarchically (Thornton & Ocasio, 2008). These higher-order logics provide an explanation of the exercising impact on institutional logic that emerges in various societal conditions (Bossy, 2016).

Institutional logics suggest historically dependent structuring principles and languages of practise that can influence the values, beliefs, and behaviour of individuals and organisations. Institutional logics shape logical and conscientious behaviour, and individual and organisational actors shape and alter these logics. Societies and organisational areas have distinct institutional logics, and these distinct institutional logics are frequently in conflict with one another; these contradictions are the drivers of change. A focus on the diversity of logic (different types of institutional rationality) may aid in the variety and dynamics of investigative practise change (Lounsbury 2008).

In Academic science departments in universities, the logic of science and commerce are both active and yet they influence dissimilar behaviour, for example, compared to proprietary retention and commercial exploitation of research discoveries, open publication and the quest for knowledge are preferred. In another instance, accounting firms are simultaneously confronted with the logic of professional service and the logic of commerce, which, within certain conditions, may suggest divergent responses. In hospitals, various professions, such as physicians, physiotherapists, psychiatrists, social workers, nurses, etc., who are socialised within different cognitive and normative norms, are brought together (Zaid-ul-Hassan, 2016). In this research, the organisation we are working on is an Islamic microfinance organisation which is dealing with three institutional logic that are commerce, religion, and community.

2.1.1 Religion as Institutional logic

Societal logic religion is a core institutional logic from the beginning but did not get any attention from scholars. Recently, a book on religion and organisational theory made a serious call for including religion in organisational studies. This research is aimed to establish a theoretical framework depicting the response of a religious microfinance organisation facing multiple institution logic and institutional complexity (Peifer, 2014).

Religion, as an institutional logic, gives direction to organisational behaviour in a way that it affects the habits and opinions of customers regarding how to value something and to know what is wrong and right. (Ebaugh, 2006) The religion-based standards, values, beliefs, and norms pressurise both fields and organisations while controlling them at the organisational level and individual level. The effects of the logic of religion become more apparent when they are according to the social structure surrounding them (Luckmann, 1979). The logic of religion affects what, how, when, and where of the organisation when considered in an integrated framework (Mittelstaedt, 2002). Different authors suggest that religion as an institutional logic can direct an organisation in shaping its organisational structure, identity, processes, decisions, and outputs (Ashworth et al., 2007).

Religion enlightens a person as to what "type" of person they are, the gravity of the roles they play, the significance of the rituals they attend, and the significance of becoming who they are (Petersen & Roy, 1985). As a result, it is possible to assert that religion, through its integrating societal impacts, provides many suggestions on how individuals should think, feel, and conduct themselves on a common subject (Snibbe & Markus, 2003). According to this opinion, religion has a strong influence on an individual's attitude, perception, and behaviour (Emmons & Paloutzian, 2003). It should be noted that in institutions that are socially organised in a

structural sense (Zucker, 1983), an employee's emotions, attitudes, views, and behaviour can be influenced by their religious beliefs (Hicks, 2003) As a result, it should be emphasised that employees may have a proclivity to transmit the values, beliefs, and norms of the religion with which they are affiliated into an organisation, to practise and maintain them within the organisation, or to share them with others. Employees will, similarly, choose their attitudes toward stakeholders, work, and organisation based on their religious values, habits, attitudes, and lifestyles. According to Hicks (2003), employees' religious commitments find a space for themselves within the workplace. This situation fits with the idea that religion has a big impact on how people think and what their roles are in society (KOÇ, 2012) (Peifer, 2014).

It is surprising since one of the six meta institutions at the base of the new institutional theory is religion, even though extensive research data exists on some other institutional logics such as the state, market, and so on (Thornton, 2004). Furthermore, religious organisations engaged in commercial activities provide a hopeful backdrop as hybrid organisations experiencing institutional complexity throughout time in instances when an organisation receives various types of pressure from diverse institutional logic. For Greenwood and colleagues (2011) In their review of the literature on institutional complexity, Greenwood et al. (2011) found two critical flaws in current studies on institutional complexity. The first concern is that the focus on institutional logics is limited because religion isn't included. The second worry is that institutional logics are thought to be inherently incompatible.

Religion is an important and fundamental part of every culture and economic organisation, yet management theorists sometimes disregard it. It is neglected in research of religion in secular groups as well as studies of religious organisations itself. In fact, Tracey (2012) discovered in a recent study of management literature from 1950 to 2011 that only 86 papers across 21 notable management journals addressed the concept of religion. It is confusing and unfortunate that management researchers have avoided one of the most powerful influences on an organisation. Though the implicit assumption in organisation and management research is that religion has only peripheral significance for contemporary organisations, such an assumption might well have impact in only one part of the world, namely Western Europe, some of whose constituent countries have been defined as "post-Christian" communities.

However, it is difficult to argue that religion has no significance in this setting. It is worth noting that extensive research on religion and organisation has been conducted. Mark Chavez and Melissa Wilde are two sociologists who have investigated religion through the lenses of

institutional theory and social movement theory, elaborating on a set of assumptions about culture and the social environment that are reliable with conventional thinking in organisation theory (Wilde, et al., 2010). There have also been a few notable innovations to organisational theory (Tracey, et al., 2017).

2.1.2 Multiple logics

Multiple logic is the employment of multiple institutional logics. Long since, academics have emphasised that businesses must continuously respond to various institutional pressures. Selznick, in early research (Selznick, 1948) (Selznick, 1957), examined organisational solutions to multiple expectations that arise from the external world, whereas Cyert and March (1963) examined the various responses to divergent expectations from inside subgroups (Cyert & March, 1963). Meyer and Rowan (1977) noted how institutional diversity presents itself in frequently contradictory internal organisational configurations (Meyer & Rowan, 1977). Meyer and Rowan (1977) offered a ground-breaking study that conceptualised how a pluralistic institutional environment could impact conflicting arrangements, particularly within an organisation. DiMaggio and Powell (1983) noted that institutional pressures could be coercive (created by regulatory agencies), normative (created by professional identities), or imitative (created by other organisations) (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). In spite of this, organisations have various distinguishing qualities, including their external environment, structure, ownership, governance, and identity (Greenwood, et al., 2011). Thornton, Ocasio, and Lounsbury (2012) subsequently characterised institutional logic as reference frames that condition actors' choices of sense-making and the lexicon they use to launch any action, including actors' conceptions of self and identity.

In recent years, academics have begun to investigate the pervasiveness, testing, and potential benefits of incorporating numerous institutional demands within organisations, frequently referring to the concept of institutional logic (Thornton et al., 2012). When fields undergo transformation, organisations frequently incorporate both new and old logic (Haveman & Rao, 1997; Lounsbury, 2002). (Thornton, 2002). In periods of relative field stability, hybridity is also mutual. When organisations exist at the intersections of disparate areas, they embody numerous institutional logics (Morrill, 2006; Purdy & Gray, 2009). (Smets et al., 2012). Diverse fields are ingrained in fields that emphasise creativity (Jones, et al., 2011); Rao, et al., 2005) or depend on diverse professional or occupational groups (D'Aunno, et al., 1991); Dunn & Jones, 2010); Heimer, 1999; Reay & Hinings, 2009); Thornton, et al., 2005)). Hybridity enables organisations to acquire legitimacy despite their various and frequently

contradictory institutional logics (Kraatz & Block, 2008). In addition, entrepreneurs may design hybrid organisations with the purpose of constructing new organisational systems that bridge several logics (DiMaggio, 1988; Thornton & Ocasio, 2008). It can be advantageous, as the differentiation of competing demands affords leaders greater latitude to design innovative alternatives to existing institutional arrangements (Seo & Creed, 2001) (Besharov & Smith, 2012) This line of research believes that organisations are not only influenced by the institutional arrangements in their sector but also shape these orders through their decisions. (Peifer, 2014).

According to Pache and Santos (2010), there are two primary lines of inquiry into organisational responses to competing institutional demands (Pache & Santos, 2010). The first includes decoupling studies, which involve separating the formal structure from the operational structure (Boxenbaum & Jonsson, 2008; Meyer & Rowan, 1977; Scott, 2003; the second step involves predictive studies on organisational behaviour toward competing logics in the case of permanent competition, such as workforce downsizing (Greenwood et al., 2010) and contractual techniques (Lounsbury, 2007). As evidenced by the literature cited thus far, there has been a substantial amount of research on institutional logic. Nevertheless, none of these studies has addressed religion as a dominant institution. (Aysan, 2017). This study will investigate the nature of hybrid organisations that incorporate diverse societal-level logic, such as an Islamic microfinance organisation.

2.1.3 Institutional complexity

It is defined as an organisational structure with multiple institutional logics. (Greenwood et al., 2010; Greenwood et al., 2011), or, in simpler terms, when an organisation employs numerous logics. Few other academics have highlighted the concept of persistent institutional complexity in the literature on institutional complexity (Pache & Santos, 2010). This includes a progressive descriptor indicating that institutional complexity may be an ongoing reality for organizations. A summary of empirical studies on institutional complexity is provided in Table 1. These works focused primarily on institutional complexity, regardless of whether they expressly employed logic or not. The table displays the variety of empirical conditions mainly associated with the United States, the timescales, and the analysis level that offered tested and created ideas and insights. The table displays a good balance between qualitative and quantitative methodological approaches, with multimethod and longitudinal study designs predominating in only a few studies. The table balances qualitative and quantitative methodological

approaches, with multimethod and longitudinal study designs predominating only a few studies. The table shows two restrictive assumptions that are used to deal with complexity: that logic has a limited range and that logic can't work together.

Kraatz and Block (2008) concluded that there is no reason to conclude that an organisation cannot fulfil numerous purposes, accept various values or logics, and effectively legitimise several institutionally formed identities. Many academics argue that organisations with multiple values or logics and that are effective at more than one logic have multiple values or logics. This shows that certain organisations thrive as they must deal with institutional complexity.

Numerous studies that acknowledge institutional complexity tend to concentrate on field-level logics that are entrenched in large societal logics (Greenwood et al., 2010). For example, Reay and Hinings's (2009) research shows that two groups of actors (doctors and government officials) work together, even though their actions are driven by different ideas (medical professionalisation and health care as a business).

Lounsbury (2007) explains how the divergent mutual fund logics of Boston and New York City (trustee versus performance logic, respectively) helped to illustrate the disparity in relationships with money management firms. Meyer and Hammer Schmid (2006) analysed the Austrian public sector, the arena for field-level competition. Ocasio (2010) shows the process whereby the new field-level logic of "managed care" dominated the organisational field of hospitals while the previous administrative orientation resisted giving way to the new management orientation (Nigam & Ocasio, 2010).

When confronted with contradictory procedures from several institutional logics, organisations must tackle institutional complexity. Companies must typically contend with multiple logics that may or may not be incompatible. Insofar as the prescriptions and prohibitions of different logics are irreconcilable, or claim to be, they will inevitably create difficulties and conflicts within organisations that are exposed to them. There have been attempts to classify organisations' responses to institutional complexity. Pache and Santos (2010) propose five organisational responses to institutional complexity, ranging from passive (acquiescence to institutional demands) to more hostile (manipulation or altering the content of institutional demands). In response to institutional complexity, Kraatz and Block (2008) identify four techniques for organisational variety. The organisation can (1) suppress or disprove the legitimacy of external claims originating from a competing logic, (2) categorise the various institutional constituencies to interact with each separately, (3) balance dissimilar requirements to find more profoundly cooperative answers, and (4) develop identities that incorporate

institutional complexity. This study examines how a religious microfinance organisation negotiates institutional complexities (Peifer, 2014).

2.2 Critical Discussion of Microfinance Institutions and Islamic Microfinance Models

Microfinance

Microfinance institutions (MFIs) generally strive to generate positive social impacts while simultaneously delivering sound financial performance to achieve a “double bottom line.” By the end of 2017, 981 MFIs had submitted performance reports to the Microfinance Information Exchange (MIX Market), which revealed an estimated US\$114 billion in loan volume and 139 million customers (Valette & Fassin, 2018). That is, this sector clearly has expanded to comprise a vast variety of organizations, which appear heterogeneous in their approaches to achieving this dual mandate. In response, a debate has cropped up, regarding which types of MFIs may be most successful in realizing both objectives (e.g., Armendáriz & Morduch, 2010; Banerjee, Karlan, & Zinman, 2015; Morduch, 2016). Some studies propose an influence of religion, such as when Mersland, D’Espallier, and Supphellen (2013) argue that Christian-based MFIs earn lower profits but also incur lower funding costs than conventional MFIs. The specific financing practices adopted by Islamic MFIs, such as interest-free forms of financial access, also might allow for greater outreach but require more resources to manage, relative to conventional microfinance (Visser, 2013). To the best of our knowledge, rigorous comparisons of conventional and Islamic MFIs, in terms of outreach and financial performance measures, and thus their ability to achieve the double bottom line, are lacking. The question of whether conventional and Islamic MFIs perform differently is particularly relevant, considering the increasing interest in MFIs that offer products and services compliant with Islamic financial principles (Abedifar, Molyneux, & Tarazi, 2013). (1) A large proportion of the world’s poor (700 million in 2013; World Bank, 2013) live in Muslim-majority nations, sparking interest in Islamic microfinance as a financial outreach tool. Even MFIs that previously offered only conventional microfinance products have started offering Islamic versions, marketing them as effective tools to facilitate and encourage small businesses (Ahmed, 2002). Yet Islamic MFIs differ markedly from conventional MFIs on several key dimensions, such as their sources of financing, investment and product portfolios, and management (Valette & Fassin, 2018). (2) For example, high interest rates in the conventional MFI sector, in addition to being criticized as unethical (Hudon & Sandberg, 2013), conflict with Islamic prohibitions on microfinance products that involve paying or receiving Riba (Abedifar, et al., 2013). (3) Conventional, for-

profit MFIs charge significantly higher interest rates when markets are less competitive (Baquero, Hamadi, & Heinen, 2018), and several conventional MFIs have been accused of acting like loan sharks, not only charging extremely high interest rates but also using aggressive collection methods (Boatright, 2013).

Parker defined microfinance as the supply of tiny sums of credit to the needy, who typically do not have access to the regular banking system (Mushtak¹², 1998). Additionally, it is described as "the provision of savings, loans, insurance, and other fundamental financial services to low-income populations" (Imboden, 2005). Numerous financial services, such as loans, deposit accounts, transfers of money, payment systems, and insurance, are made available to low-income and poor households and their microentrepreneurs., according to another definition offered by the Asian Development Bank (Conroy, 2002). On the other hand, Ledgerwood (1999) defined it as "the provision of financial services to poor and low-income clients, including low-income entrepreneurs and self-employed, in both urban and rural settings."

Institutions that provide financial services to low-income individuals and micro-entrepreneurs are known as microfinance institutions. They are typically unable to enter the mainstream banking system. Most of the time, microfinance and microcredit are used interchangeably. Microfinance refers to a range of financial activities that primarily assist the poor, including loans, savings, micro-Takaful, and funding for small businesses to expand.

Operating microfinance institutions. It may be a non-governmental organisation (NGO), a cooperative, a non-bank financial intermediary, or an Islamic banking product. Microfinance institutions are viewed as a paradigm shift in the perspective and practises of poverty alleviation as well as builders of inclusive economic growth. Due to the magnitude of economic forces and the absence of institutional frameworks that enable rules and regulations, as well as a shortage of donors, microfinance remains an unfinished business in many countries. In eliminating poverty, microfinance organisations have encountered various hurdles, such as the stretched boundaries of formal finance and the participation of the most disadvantaged women in formal commercial systems. Thus, seed money can be used to diversify the revenue bases, physical assets, and social assets of households. Operating expenses and capital limitations have prohibited microfinance firms from meeting the enormous demand. The demand for credit is variable, and as a result, microfinance organisations may be unable to serve the lowest-income consumers if interest rates rise. In recent years, internal and external demands on microfinance institutions to reduce their reliance on subsidised or grant funding have increased. Microfinance organisation as a business model, should seek outside capital.

Consequently, the topic of business models merits discussion. Several theoretical models have been presented in this effort to explain business models across countries. These models have been empirically evaluated in the real business world; however, alternative models have been largely disregarded because the majority of past research has focused on typical business models. Microfinance institutions, on the other hand, can achieve their social goals through good financial performance. External funding may impact the organization's financial performance because it increases expenses. To eliminate poverty, it's essential to understand how external financing impacts a country's financial stability.

2.3 Models of microfinance

This section aims to illustrate the numerous models currently utilised by microfinance institutions worldwide. The models are taken from a book (Obaidullah, 2008), where all the models that will be discussed in this chapter are taken from different case studies.

Village banking models include organisations, insurance contracts, community banking, cooperative societies, credit unions, Grameen, individuals, intermediaries, non-governmental organisations, peer pressure, ROSCAs, and local businesses. There is a close connection between these models, and it is common for microfinance institutions that are efficient and sustainable microfinance institutions to use parts of two or more models. Extensive studies were conducted in nations such as Pakistan, Indonesia, Malaysia, Brunei, and Sudan to produce these models.

2.3.1 Association Model

Several microfinance operations are launched in this model through an "association" created by the target community. The activities may involve savings, and the associations made may also include youth, women, and concerns such as politics, religion, and culture. These organisations may address other work-related issues as well as provide microentrepreneurs with support structures. In certain states, an "association" can be a permitted entity that provides various benefits, such as Takaful (an alternative to insurance), tax rebates, other protection measures, and fee collection. There is a variation among these models and others since it is a community-based model that is closely tied to the group model (Obaidullah & Khan, 2008).

2.3.2 Bank Guarantees Model

To attain financing from an Islamic bank a bank guarantee is used. A guarantee can be arranged externally or internally. If externally arranged it can be sourced from a donor's donation or a government agency and when internally arranged, members savings are used. Individuals may get the financing obtained, directly or a self-formed may be given the financing. The Bank Guarantee is a type of capital guarantee programme. Guaranteed money may be utilised for a variety of purposes, such as financing restoration and Takaful obligations. Several international groups have been putting together international guarantee funds that Islamic banks and non-governmental groups can use to start microfinance programmes or contribute to.

2.3.3 Model of Community Banking

The Community Banking Model satisfies the needs of the entire community and maintains formal or semi-formal institutions through which microfinance is distributed with the assistance of numerous NGOs and other organisations. Typically, the purpose of these organisations is to educate community members on the numerous financial transactions of the community bank.

The frameworks of the institutions may also include savings mechanisms and other revenue-generating efforts. In several instances, community banks are also components of larger community development programmes that employ monetary rewards to encourage action. The model closely resembles the village banking model.

2.3.4 Cooperative Model

A cooperative is a voluntary group of individuals formed to address their shared cultural, economic, and social needs and ambitions through a democratically operated and owned business. The mission of certain cooperatives includes member funding and savings.

2.3.5 Credit Union Model

A credit union is a financial institution limited to members that provide mutual aid. It is organised by a specific group or organisation whose parties agreed to pool their funds and lend to one another at reasonable interest rates. Members are those who share a connection, such as working for the same company, attending the same mosque, social fraternity, labour union,

etc., or living and working in the same community. A credit union restricts membership to members of a particular group, such as a community or religion. A credit union is a democratic, non-profit financial cooperative. Participants manage and own the organisation they are a part of. They elect the board of directors and committee members.

2.3.6 Grameen Model

Mohammed Yunus founded in Bangladesh a poverty-focused institution from which the Grameen Model emerged. In general, the following procedure was adopted: a bank unit with a field manager and several bank personnel covering 15 to 22 towns was formed. Managers and personnel visit the villages to familiarise themselves with the local context in which they will discover and operate prospective clients, as well as to explain the bank's functions, purpose, and mode of operation to the local community. There are five groups of prospective borrowers, but only two of the qualifying groups obtain a loan in the first round. A one-month survey is conducted to assess whether the organization's members comply with the bank's regulations. Other group members are eligible to receive a loan only if the two lead borrowers pay the principal and interest within 50 weeks. Due to these limitations, keeping individual histories places a substantial societal cost on society. In this manner, the group's shared responsibility serves as collateral for the loan (Obaidullah, 2008).

2.3.7 Group Organization

The Group Model's key assumption is that deficiencies and weaknesses can be resolved through the joint responsibility and security managed by the individual-level development of a group of such individuals.

Individual members utilise their collective approach for a variety of purposes, like education and awareness building, peer pressure, collective negotiating power, etc. Numerous different financial models have been influenced by the group model and are closely related to it. These include village banking, Grameen, community banking, self-help, peer pressure, and solidarity.

2.3.8 Individual Model

The individual model is a simple credit loaning method in which microloans are given to the borrower directly. It does not necessitate the formation of organisations or the creation of peer pressure to guarantee a return. Individual models are frequently used as part of a wider 'credit

plus programme that typically includes education, developing skills, and further outreach activities. The Intermediary Model of Credit Lending Positions is a company that works as a "middleman" between borrowers and lenders. The intermediary is critical in increasing borrowers' credit sensitivity and education (including, in some cases, starting savings programs). These steps are designed to raise the borrowers' "creditworthiness" to a level that lenders will find appealing. The linkages of the intermediaries could include money, education and training programs, partnerships, and research. Such actions can take place at several levels, ranging from global and national to regional, local, and individual. Intermediaries include non-governmental organisations (NGOs), individual lenders, microenterprise and microcredit programmes, and commercial banks (for government-funded initiatives). Commercial banks, government organisations, foreign donors, and so forth are examples of lenders. Most of the techniques presented in this article involve an organisational or operational intermediary interacting directly with microcredit or non-financial companies. This method is also known as the "partnership" model (Obaidullah, 2008).

2.3.9 The NGO Model

NGOs have emerged as key players in the microcredit field. They have filled the role of intermediary in a variety of dimensions. Non-governmental organisations have assisted in the establishment and implementation of microcredit programmes. This practise improves community and national and international donor institutions' understanding of the importance of microcredit. Instruments and resources are created to assist communities and microcredit institutions identify and track good practises. This approach also provides opportunities to learn about the practise and ideas of microcredit through workshops, seminars, publications, and training programmes.

2.3.10 Peer Pressure Model

Peer pressure participants use moral and other connections between borrowers and projects to ensure microcredit sharing and repayment. Peers in a borrower's group may be other members (who cannot obtain loans until the initial borrowers in the group pay) or co-borrowers (where the other members do not obtain loans unless the initial borrowers in a group pay). The initial members are therefore under pressure to repay bank community leaders (who are frequently recruited, developed, and trained by external NGOs); NGOs and field employees; etc. Within its borrower groups, "pressure" can take the form of frequent visits to defaulters, community

meetings where they are recognised and pushed to comply, etc. Grameen's repayment model heavily depends on peer pressure (Obaidullah & Khan, 2008).

2.3.11 Models of Islamic Microfinance

Weill (2020) proposes a summary of four main principles of Islamic (micro-)finance: (1) Interest is forbidden. (2) Lenders are rewarded through profit sharing, though the most popular Islamic microfinance products do not reflect conventional profit-and-loss sharing principles, as we discuss subsequently. (3) The MFIs cannot finance activities considered sinful by Islam, such as maysir (gambling) (Chong & Liu, 2009), alcohol, or borrowing and lending to conventional MFIs that charge interest. (4) Contract terms should be entirely clear and eliminate any contractual uncertainty, due to the prohibition of gharar (uncertainty).

As a result of the research, Islamic microfinance is described within an Islamic context. To help low-income consumers or business owners launch or manage their enterprises, Islamic microfinance is classified as the investment of funds (in cash or any other form) based on Islamic forms of finance. Due to their unique qualities, microfinance institutions are viewed as independent components of the financial system. Over the years, conventional microfinance has created numerous approaches for the provision of microfinance services. Similarly, Islamic microfinance implements a similar method, but based on Shari'ah teaching, these techniques have been modified to reflect the distinctive nature of Islamic financing. Below are brief descriptions of a few of these models:

This section signifies the Islamic microfinance models. The tools for this concept are divided into the two groups listed below:

- a) Microfinance tools based on charity
- b) Profit-seeking microfinance instruments

a) Microfinance tools based on charity

In this category, the target audience is truly impoverished, economically inactive, and in need of consumer funds for health, food, shelter, etc. For their long-term social and economic success, it is important to help them become economically effective through training or technical support. In the following two broad categories the instruments for this group may be classified:

I) Zakah, sadaqah & waqf

The extremely needy and poor to meet their requirements of life are helped through the Islamic economic system. And the three major tools of sadaqah, zakah, and waqf are the expanding social safety networks. Zakah is one of the five pillars of Islam and entails the mandatory payment of a specific proportion of one's wealth annually. Sadaqah, on the other hand, is voluntary and varies in quantity and form. This money is contingent on one's intentions, which are uncertain. However, the money collected through these two instruments can be used as charity or subsidy funds for the poorest individuals who are not assisted by conventional microfinance. Individuals are encouraged to assist the destitute and disadvantaged and to prioritise economic empowerment. In this system, excessive reliance on gifts and subsidies is discouraged. Idealistically, Islamic microfinance cannot rely just on charitable donations; it also entails working towards the economic empowerment of the needy and underprivileged. Thus, according to Mufti Taqi Usmani, a Waqf is a religious and legal institution in which a person donates some of his property for charity or religious purposes. It can complement zakah and sadaqah. Waqif, like sadaqah, is not necessary, but it becomes stable and sustainable once it is practised. It has the potential to provide technical training or skills to economically inactive and disadvantaged groups. However, stability has become increasingly difficult to achieve, and combining philanthropic instruments requires institutions that are driven by profit (Obaidullah, 2008).

II) Qard e Hasan

According to Islamic finance, interest-free loans are the purest way to assist the poor. The core of this instrument is that the borrower pays just the principal amount, with the intention of supporting the poorest part of the community. This IMF product can be used for both finance and savings. Since it is a loan with no interest and the borrower is responsible for repaying the principal balance, microfinance can be used to help low-income individuals invest or purchase goods.

However, it is crucial to this topic that the lender or lending institution cover the borrower's operational expenses. Along with being a zero-interest financing facility, this product provides the flexibility of allowing an extension in loan repayment, which helps the borrower avoid falling into a debt trap, which is one of the primary shortcomings of conventional microfinance (involuntary default of a borrower).

Another feature of this instrument is that there is no fixed date of repayment, making it suited for use as a savings product, as investors can deposit funds and withdraw them whenever they need to.

To expand microfinance, Akhuwat in Pakistan employs 'qard hasan' in its community-based strategy (Case Study1). In Afghanistan, Islamic microfinance institutions also use this product. In Indonesia, on the other hand, many Islamic products are used, such as qard hasan and zakah (Obaidullah, 2008).

2.4 Profit Based Microfinance Instruments

2.4.1 Financing modes

The most well-known Islamic financial product is Murabaha, which has enormous microfinance potential. An Islamic MFI purchases the seller's assets for their consumers and then resells them to the clients at a fixed profit margin. On agreed future dates, the client may pay in instalments or a lump sum. Both parties must know how much the transaction will cost and how it will be priced. This makes it less likely that the client will be taken advantage of because of a lack of information. The exploitation of consumers is one of the primary criticisms levelled against conventional microfinance, where high interest rates are imposed on clients who are not necessarily knowledgeable of the marketplace and the situation operations. In this model, the customer is not compulsory to keep in the least records after the transaction has been accomplished, despite the need to purchase documentation during the transaction, which makes it a useful solution for small enterprises. If institutions have to meet strict documentation requirements, they may be less likely to take loans from formal institutions or give their information to manipulative money lenders.

There is an additional concern associated with the goods from the perspective of the MFI: the risk of ownership from the time the MFI obtains the product from the vendor until he offers it to the customer. The Islamic MFI, like other Islamic financial institutions, enters into an agency agreement with a third party to purchase the assets from the source in its favour. The client could be a third party. Even though the seller is acting as an agent, he or she still has ownership risk. This risk may be contractual or physical, but takaful (insurance) can help reduce it. Idealistically, the Islamic MFI should not authorise the agency agreement that encourages economic activity with the client in order to generate additional jobs. The Wasil Foundation (formerly known as the Centre for Women's Cooperative Development) in Pakistan is a good example of an Islamic microfinance model in which Murabaha is offered without any agency arrangement (Obaidullah, 2008).

A Murabaha to purchase orders is also a unilateral duty, suggesting that the customer may cancel the asset acquisition. Nonetheless, early payment helps lessen this danger (*himish jiddiya*). To reduce the risk of default, the lending institution may require collateral. Clients in microfinance may find it difficult to furnish collateral. So, the Group Lending Model is used. In this model, the group acts as collateral, which is similar to how microfinance is usually done. In Malaysia, Islamic MFIs utilise the Murabaha the most.

A case study on Murabaha loans in Afghanistan analysis indicates that borrowers of Islamic loans in Afghanistan default more frequently than borrowers of conventional loans, particularly in Taliban-controlled areas. These observations remain largely consistent when we explore the factors influencing the number of days overdue on loan repayments. Furthermore, our conclusions find further support from both microfinance institutions' Islamic loan products: business Murabaha loans, available to individuals of any gender, and women's Murabaha loans, created as a group lending scheme exclusively for women. The results from this study offer valuable insights into how policy discussions in Afghanistan should be adjusted to facilitate a smooth transition for the microfinance industry (Disli & Jalaly, 2024).

a) Mudaraba and Musharaka

Islamic microfinance is distinguishable from conventional microfinance on the basis of its partnership-based modalities. Mudaraba implies trustee finance when a partnership is established among two parties in the execution of a project in which one (*rub-ul-mal*) provides funds and the other provides managerial expertise (*mudarib*). Under mudaraba, profits are divided based on predetermined ratios, whereas in the event of a loss, the MFI-financier bears the loss of capital, unless the loss is the result of the *mudarib*'s malfeasance or carelessness. This product may enhance the social standing of a client of an Islamic MFI by providing financial stability and allowing them to assume business risk. Institutions provide financing that will serve as an effective incentive for the institution to be vigilant in the monitoring of the business/venture, lowering the risk of losses and enhancing their managerial abilities by pushing the client.

When Islamic microfinance was implemented in Sudan in the 1980s, mudaraba and *qard hasan* were its primary products. In Bangladesh, which is one of the most important Islamic microfinance markets, mudaraba is also a common way to get money.

In musharaka, the capital and managerial responsibilities are shared by both parties (client and financier), who at the time of the agreement divide the profit at a fixed rate. Loss allocation is proportional to invested capital. This product may be appropriate for an Islamic MFI because

the financier not only provides funding but also assists with the management of company operations. This solution can facilitate the achievement of two goals for small businesses that lack access to capital and also lack entrepreneurial abilities. As the MFI will be actively engaged in the operation of the business, monitoring and supervision will be rather successful in lowering both voluntary and involuntary default risks. Still, the MFI is at risk of capital impairment. This risk can be lessened with help from a third party, like the Credit Guarantee Corporation of Malaysia. This seems to be the best way for Islamic microfinance to work, but it doesn't happen very often because of ethical risk, cash flow, adverse selection, long-term participation, and high costs for both the client and the institution to meet extra requirements like accounting procedures and formal documentation. Yemen is an example of operating Islamic microfinance based on musharaka (Obaidullah, 2008).

b) Decreased musharaka

It resembles musharaka in which the financier gradually transfers ownership to the client. Under the terms of this agreement, the Islamic financial institution's stake in its shares steadily decreases. It accepts earnings proportional to its remaining investment in the business during the time. So, the client's share grows over period, and when the contract ends, the whole asset is own by the customer or business undertaking.

c) Salam and Istisna

Salam is usually used in agriculture, while istisna is a type of short-term financing used in trading. To satisfy his funding requirements, the consumer, who might be a small merchant or a farmer, under salam, for spot payment sells his crop/output to the MFI, while the delivery of production is permitted to be completed at a future date. The product is organised such that the spot price is less than the future delivery price. Salam is a good method for microfinance clients, and it has been acknowledged that the targeted group includes a significant proportion of consumers who require only short-term credit. like Salam the framework of Istisna is identical, but the emphasis is on manufacturing things with flexible partial payments by the financier. Due to the client's potential inability to provide the commodity in the future, the MFI is vulnerable to credit risk under these terms. This danger can be mitigated with takaful. The institution is also exposed to the risk of price changes (market risk), because the future price of a good or service may be less than what the MFI paid for it from the client (Obaidullah, 2008).

2.4.2 Rental models (ijara)

The MFI uses Ijara to gain from the usufruct of the revenue-producing resources for a fixed payment, the amount and duration of which are predetermined. The microfinance institution Unlike renting, this option enables clients to develop the asset for their own benefit while the institution retains ownership. An Ijara is a contract for a specified duration in which the institution may gift or sell the asset to the same client. The institution appreciates taking on all obligations and risks because asset ownership remains with the MFI, which is notably different from conventional leasing and makes microfinance leasing a more attractive option for microfinance borrowers.

Under Ijara, the institution is exposed to possession risk: if the item is lost or stolen, the institution is responsible for all damages, not the client, unless the client's carelessness caused the loss. Therefore, through takaful, the institution can mitigate this risk (Obaidullah, 2008).

2.4.3 Saving products

preserving products

In general, three modes of energy conservation are available: i) wadia, (ii) qard, and (iii) mudaraba. These products may be used to encourage microfinance clients to save even smaller sums, as withdrawals are permitted at any time and there is no danger of loss.

As previously discussed, the transaction structure is identical in mudaraba. The main difference is that the MFI acts as the mudarib and the client takes on the role of rab-ul-mal. Under this manner, the client is exposed to investment risks (in the event of a loss, the rab-ul-mal bears full financial loss) and divides the benefit with the institution according to a predetermined ratio.

iv) Takaful: As a rule, clients of MFI institutions are unable to plan for or save for unforeseeable or uncertain future situations, making takaful one of the most essential products available. Ideally, takaful is a non-profit mechanism in which all participants provide joint guarantees. Under takaful, a joint fund is created through the contributions of each participant. At times of adversity, such as death, illness, crop, or business loss, the fund's resources are used to assist or support any member of the contributing fund. (Obaidullah, 2008)

Islamic and conventional MFIs are incredibly similar. Due to MFIs' extensive reliance on BBA style of financing, however, a significant distinction exists, although this difference is currently quite negligible. The primary distinctions between conventional and Islamic MFIs are detailed in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Difference between Conventional and Islamic MFIs

	Conventional MFIs	Islamic MFIs
Liabilities (Sources of Funds)	External Funds, Savings of clients	External Funds, Savings of clients, Islamic Charitable Sources
Assets (Mode of Financing)	Interest-based	Islamic Financial Instruments
Financing the Poorest	Poorest are left out	Poorest can be included by integrating <i>zakat</i> with microfinancing
Funds transfer	Cash given	Good transferred
Deduction at inception of contract	Part of the funds deduced at inception	No deductions at inception
Target group	Women	Family
Objective of targeting Women	Empowerment of women	Ease of availability
Liability of the loan (when given to women)	Recipient	Recipient and spouse
Work incentive of employees	Monetary	Monetary and religious
Dealing with Default	Group/centre pressure and threats	Group/centre/spouse guarantee, and Islamic ethics
Social development Program	Secular (or un-Islamic) behavioural, ethical, and social development.	Religious (includes behaviour, ethics, and social

Source: Ahmed, H. (2002). "Financing Microenterprises," p. 41.

Islamic microfinance offers an alternative to conventional microfinance for meeting the financial needs of the poor and the financially excluded (Karim, Tarazi, & Reille, 2008). The two microfinance forms differ considerably from an operational perspective (Ahmed, 2002). Even if some fundamental similarities apply to the financial instruments or techniques, the products and services provided by Islamic MFIs are free of elements (Obaidullah, 2008), because their business activities must adhere to halal (permissible) principles. For example,

both conventional and Islamic MFIs use equity and debt-based financing, but they operationalise the instruments differently (Ahmad, et al., 2020).

Conventional microfinance institutions (MFIs) can promote financial inclusion, but they also prompt ethical concerns regarding the social consequences of commercialisation and high interest rates. Islamic MFIs, which adhere to Sharia's prohibition of Riba (usually interpreted as a ban on interest), present an alternative. Differences between conventional and Islamic MFIs in terms of outreach and financial sustainability remain underexplored

2.5 Islamic Microfinance

2.5.1 Islamic Microfinance Background

During the Prophetic era, Islam created a financial system with social and economic fairness. In all human transactions, a perfect Muslim society prioritises socioeconomic fairness. Islam forbids inequality, injustice, and unjust property appropriation. Since Riba damages, any society's socioeconomic conditions produce injustice, exploitation, and indebtedness to fulfil demands. Shariah bans Riba (interest). Allah has threatened people who practise Riba or steal others' possessions.

"And for charging Riba (interest) when unlawful, and for devouring people's property by dishonest means. We've prepared a severe retribution for disbelievers. " (161:4)

Poverty-stricken developing countries use many techniques to battle poverty and improve the lives of the poor. Unfortunately, the strategies haven't raised the poor's living standards. Poverty eradication demands a multidisciplinary approach. Microfinance was created to fight poverty.

Microfinance organisations serve low-income groups that cannot approach regular banks owing to a lack of collateral. Microfinance lets the disadvantaged create small businesses or production activities at cheaper costs. Standard microfinance is expensive. It's suggested that microfinance organisations benefit disadvantaged communities with loans.

In Latin America and South Asia (1970s), for the poor without collateral microfinance made simpler credit. They started their enterprises using interest-bearing loans. They started their enterprises using interest-bearing loans. Microfinance has evolved into numerous models. Dr. Muhammad Yunus introduced Bangladesh's Grameen Bank Model. This model empowers poor women. The second form, the "village bank model," was popular in Latin America and Africa. Its implementing agency provided loans to its participants. The local bank established

independent microfinance. Non-profit financial cooperatives, which are popular in Asia, are also known as third microfinance model credit unions (CU's). Member-run, this methodology sought to increase CUs, monitor financial performance, and teach unions in crucial areas. In India, "Self-help Groups" with 10–15 members who pooled their funds for loans became popular.

Leikem (2012) suggested that typical microfinance services concentrated on empowering low-income enterprises, but the poor received little benefit and their incomes remained the same. Traditional microfinance institutions (MFIs) rely on interest-bearing foreign donations for funding and violate shariah. Islamic microfinance was established to benefit the needy by satisfying Shariah standards (no usury, uncertainty, gambling, criminal activities, unearned income). Islamic Microfinance Institutions help Muslims and non-Muslims (IMF). Shariah-based Islamic finance supports justice and equitable income and wealth distribution. It helps balance the social and economic aspects of human society and alleviates poverty by preventing poor exploitation.

According to statistics, Muslim countries are the poorest. After the 2008 global financial crisis, Islamic microfinance gained importance. Islamic microfinance was more productive than conventional due to its unique qualities. Islamic microfinance products, such as charity, Zakah, and Awqaf, reduce poverty more effectively.

From Islamic finance Microfinance could not be separated, if indeed, the ultimate purpose is to improve social welfare by enabling equitable growth and wealth distribution. In addition to laying the groundwork for the long-term viability of institutions, Islamic microfinance structures have inherent safeguards and the adaptability to address varying degrees of poverty. In addition, the presence of Islamic microfinance remains relatively low and concentrated in only a few countries, indicating a substantial market opportunity for Islamic financial institutions and microfinance organisations to gain faith-sensitive microfinance customers.

2.5.2 Islamic Microfinance In Pakistan

Pakistan is the 36th largest country by area (881,912 km²) and sixth most populous, with approximately 227 million people in the first quarter of 2021. 51.36% of the population are men, and 48.64% is women. Economists are split on the impact of a growing population on a country's development and growth. One side believes that an increasing population stimulates economic growth and development. Ibn Khaldun's theory emphasises this. The second group

adopts Robert Malthus' idea. According to Malthus (1798), population expansion causes several challenges for a nation's economy (Malthus, 1986).

Overpopulation and population increase the strain on resources, causing a chain reaction of difficulties as the nation develops. Third, population growth doesn't affect economic growth and is neutral. Other elements drive economic growth. Population expansion spurs technical advancements and improvements. Population expansion stimulates corporate competition and expands a country's potential market. Market growth drives entrepreneurs to start new enterprises (Simón-Moya, et al., 2014). The Islamic perspective argues for tapping man's natural resources to promote growth and development.

At first, to deal with its poverty, Pakistan embraced the Grameen model of Bangladesh. In many countries the Grameen model has been successful in alleviating poverty by increasing poor earnings. Pakistan has 10 licensed MFIs and microfinance banks. Considering all these microfinance organisations, every third Pakistani is poor (Begum, et al., 2019).

With approximately 98% of its 180 million population being Muslim, Pakistan is among the most potential countries for Islamic microfinance. Though, worldwide, Islamic microfinance accounts as it represents barely 0.5% of the microfinance business and is therefore regarded to be in its infancy. Pakistan has taken measures that can elevate Islamic microfinance to another level. Although many MFIs currently provide Shariah-compliant financial products in the industry, the MFIs listed below offer an entirely Islamic financial product range. (Kazim & Haider, 2012)

Traditional microfinance didn't help the poor; it prioritised the wealth. Islamic microfinance continues to be in its infancy and faces resource and coverage issues. A few Islamic NGOs in Pakistan provide Islamic microfinance. Islamic Relief Pakistan (IRP), Akhuwat, Karakoram Cooperative Bank (KCB), National Rural Support Program, Wasil Foundation, Kashf Foundation, Naymet Trust, Kawish Welfare Trust, Esaar Foundation, and Muslim Aid. Akhuwat is the only organisation that uses crowdsourcing. Akhuwat offers Qard al-Hassan interest-free loans (Mahmood, 2019).

2.5.2.1 Akhuwat

Akhuwat was established in 2001 with the intention of providing Shariah-compliant microfinance solutions that would encourage economic development and alleviate poverty. Akhuwat had a net loan portfolio of 355 million rupees in 2011, which was divided to 42,069 borrowers. Akhuwat only worked in cities and concentrated on Punjab. It does, however, have

offices in KPK and Baluchistan, but with limited impact. They've been able to develop a model with the following features during the last ten years:

i) *Primary product:*

Akhuwat's primary Islamic microfinance product is Qarz-e-Hasan, which consists of interest-free loans with flexible repayment terms. Akhuwat does not follow a group methodology in providing loans, instead lending on an individual basis. Nonetheless, there is social collateral, as many of Akhuwat's offices are established in areas where the community vouches for its members. Deficient delinquency levels are indicated by the PAR > 30 days to gross portfolio ratio of 1%3.

ii) *Funding:*

Individuals and organisations that support Akhuwat's mission provide the majority of Akhuwat's funding through donations. Even though the organisation has established its financial base, it continues to rely on donations to meet its expenses.

iii) *Beneficiaries*

The targeted recipients are underprivileged people with business potential. and the desire to establish their own companies. Transfers of money and income aren't given out as a form of charity but rather to help entrepreneurs get money.

iv) *Stakeholder roles:*

Akhuwat distinguishes the roles of all stakeholders participating in the delivery system. The idea is rooted in the concept of community, as the word "Akhuwat" means "brotherhood." In mosques and churches, most branches are located, which locals frequent. Based on this brotherhood, Loans are provided, with the society acting as a guarantor for all its members. This link also focuses on when the community provides financial support to the Akhuwat brothers.

2.5.2.2 History of Akhuwat

Akhuwat was a pioneer Islamic microfinance organisation that used the "Qard al-Hassan model" It redistributes resources effectively. Dr. Amjad Saqib founded Akhuwat after observing that typical MFIs fail to aid the poor and reduce poverty due to exorbitant interest rates and a lack of shariah compliance. This led to interest-free loans in Pakistan being modelled after Qard al-Hassan. Akhuwat's acquaintance donated \$100 to start Akhuwat. Dr.

Saqib used this donation to help a widow live with dignity. Six months after using the loan, she repaid it. It recalls Muakhat-e-Madina when Prophet Muhammad travelled to Madinah with his companions. Natives' financial, moral, and empathetic assistance sets an example. This example could also help the Muslim ummah reduce poverty and deal with economic issues. The Akhuwat concept believes the destitute have objectives and motivations. If they can grow and prosper, they can boost economic growth. Akhuwat provides health services, business training, scholarships, and a clothing bank. Akhuwat also helps transvestites find work. It also helps the poor, and it's compassionate.

Akhuwat's ideals include loans which are interest-free (Qard al-Hassan), effective custom locations of worship, volunteering, and borrowers as givers. (Iqbal & Shafiq, 2015)

The Akhuwat microfinance model is a one-of-a-kind model based on the idea that Muslims are brothers who should aid one another. The strategy is founded on the perception of community solidarity, with facilities provided through places such as churches and mosques, which community members frequently visit. Based on Qard Hasan, Akhuwat offers individual or family loans with no collateral. The premise for extending funding under this paradigm is social collateral, in which the community guarantees the borrower. To cover management costs, Akhuwat raises funds from both civil society and borrowers who contribute to the fund. Borrowers make voluntary contributions to the fund. Borrowers are encouraged to contribute to the community brotherhood idea, which indirectly pushes them to save. The administration costs are covered by the contribution fund and some donations cover the administration costs. The simplicity of the approach and the widespread distribution of Qarz-e-Hasan loans have contributed significantly to Akhuwat's general appreciation. Moreover, since the loans are interest-free, the poor can repay them without paying interest. In addition, the communal nature of the mosques and churches instils trust in both the employees and the borrowers, resulting in the effective return of donations from previous borrowers.

2.5.3 Islamic microfinance and sustainability

Sustainability is the most critical aspect of a good Islamic microfinance model, as without it the programme cannot be executed properly. The microfinance model's sustainability can be assessed from two perspectives: its economic and social impact. A microfinance strategy should contribute to raising income, alleviating poverty, and accumulating assets from a financial perspective. At the same time, its social impact should be evaluated in terms of its outreach, skill development, knowledge enhancement, family empowerment, religious

adherence, etc., (Rabbani, et al., 2007) suggesting that the Grameen Bank Model cannot be considered optimal due to its higher interest rates and inability to reduce poverty. He underlined the use of Sharia-based microfinancing methods, which are appropriate for alleviating poverty in a society. He stated that the structured collection of Zakat can assist in alleviating poverty. Most microfinance institutions (MFIs) charge exorbitant interest rates on their loans, which places an additional burden on the poor. In lieu of taking advantage of the poor by charging them exorbitant interest rates, greater effort is required to develop an Islamic microfinance model created on the principles of righteousness, piety, brotherhood, and mutual collaboration. The strategy prioritises social impact over financial maximisation. According to Hassian and Khalil, Musharrakah, Mudaraba, Murabaha, and Qarz e Hasana are the most important interest-free lending options. (Hussain & Khalil, 2017)

2.5.4 Islamic Microfinance Institutions and Poverty Alleviation

In recent decades, the Muslim population has reached over 1.8 billion, or nearly a quarter of the world's total population. Some data indicate that nearly one-third of Muslims worldwide are living in poverty (Economist, 2008). In addition to the increase in the Muslim population, additional issues such as the global economic collapse and global warming, which cause long-term drought in many Muslim nations, further restrict the lives of Muslims and exacerbate the problem.

To comprehend the contemporary understanding of Islamic finance institutions, one must grasp the philosophical underpinnings of several key notions that constitute the foundation of accountability in Islam. Tawhid signifies the unity and singularity of God. This notion suggests that, given the existence of a singular God, Islam, derived from the term meaning 'submission', demands complete devotion to that God in every facet of life (Ibrahim 2000a, Napier 2009). This introduces the concept of Khilafa (vicegerency), which posits that humans must serve as trustees and agents of God on Earth, managing its resources and caring for God's creatures (Ketola et al., 2009; Ariff and Iqbal, 2011). In essence, God, regarded as the supreme proprietor of all, has designated humanity as divine stewards on earth, entrusting them with the holy responsibility of managing its resources. Consequently, property ownership is regarded as a trust, and individuals are responsible to God for how they utilise this trust for the sake of humanity (Lewis, 2001).

The term 'Hesab' (literally meaning 'account') is the etymological foundation of accounting. This term and its derivation are used in the Quran over eighty times (Askary and Clarke 1997).

Lewis (2001) asserts that the term 'Hesab' pertains to an individual's duty to render an account to God, to whom every Muslim is answerable in all facets of life. He states that every Muslim possesses a record or 'account' with God that documents all virtuous and malevolent activities to be considered on the Day of Judgement (Ketola, et al., 2009).. This introduces additional dimensions to the concept of valuation of objects and actions, in contrast to the human-centric conception of valuation that underpins traditional accountability and accounting (Lewis, 2001).

The term Ummah can be interpreted as 'community.' Nevertheless, this phrase possesses a hallowed connotation (Levy & Rezgui, 2015). This concept signifies that each individual action should ultimately benefit the collective welfare of the community. The Islamic economic system, as articulated by Ariff and Iqbal (2011), aims to enable individuals to earn a livelihood in a just and profitable manner, free from the exploitation of others, so benefiting society as a whole. Ariff and Iqbal (2011) contend that Islam prioritises "the welfare of the community over individual rights and the interests of the entirety of the Muslim society, rather than on the special interest of individual Muslims" (p. 45). Baydoun and Willett (2000) assert that, in this setting, Islam emphasises God and the human society over individual interests, prioritising social accountability over the personal accountability characteristic of Western principles. Therefore, the emphasis of Islamic accounting should not be confined to individual accounting profit; instead, it should encompass the assessment of their substantial contributions to the entire community (Levy & Rezgui, 2015).

Ultimately, the notion of Adl pertains to justice in its socio-economic context. Levy and Rezgui (2015) assert that Adl is the principal moral purpose of Shariah, integrating the social and economic facets of justice. They cite gambling and interest-based transactions as instances of economic activities that have been banned due to their social injustice ramifications, resulting in the impoverishment of one segment of society while enabling wealth accumulation in another. Consequently, accounting ought to serve as an instrument of justice. recognises activities related to economic and social injustice and facilitates the establishment of justice in its socio-economic context (Kantakji, 2003).

In addressing best practices for Islamic microfinance and poverty alleviation, Obaidullah (2008) spot out that although Islam promote charity on one side, it also stresses on need to reduce dependence on charity by poor on the other. For poverty alleviation he used a hadith, reported in Sunan Abu Dawud, to illustrate an approach and strategy. For poverty alleviation important phases in operating microfinance services, following Obaidullah's approach, the

hadith is broken down into numbered statements so as to highlight the main principles and components of the strategy that follows from the hadith. derived from this hadith (the full text of the hadith below) are briefly summarised in Table 3 below. (Obaidullah, 2008)

Table 2.2: Fundamental needs for Successful Microfinance Program in Islam

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Access of the poorest of the poor to the program:</i> The <i>hadith</i> shows that the Prophet (p.b.u.h.), being both the spiritual and political leader of the Muslims, was always accessible to the poor and needy for economic and financial assistance. 2. <i>Careful evaluation of the financial health of the poor; a combination of inquiry and compassion; stress on donation and beneficiary ownership:</i> It is believed that the failure of many microfinance programs is due mainly to inadequate evaluation of the client's financial condition. Thus, careful assessment of the financial status of clients is a must. 3. <i>Conversion of the beneficiary's unproductive assets into revenue assets via rigorous valuation (on the basis of price discovery through auction procedure); participation of the greater community in the process:</i> In some cases, clients' own assets, but are unable to derive benefits from those assets. Thus, there is a need for asset transformation from unproductive asset into income-generating and productive one. However, to ensure that the seller receives the fair price and does not lose the value, this transformation or a sale should be done through auction, which is believed to be the most efficient process of discovery of fair price. 4. <i>Prioritized satisfaction of basic requirements and investment of the surplus in productive assets:</i> This implies the importance of the hierarchy in addressing the needs of the poor. Hence, the basic needs <i>should</i> be met before investing surplus in income-generating activities. 5. <i>Direct engagement of the programme in capacity building prior to income production and provision of technical help to the beneficiary; commitment of the program's top management.:</i> This part of <i>hadith</i> shows the direct and proactive role of the Prophet (p.b.u.h.) in the process of poverty alleviation. The same is expected from the top management of the program.
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6. *Technical assistance in the form of providing the beneficiary with the necessary training to implement the business plan / income-generating project; monitoring through a time-bound timetable and impact evaluation through a feedback system.:* This emphasises the importance of merging between financial and technical assistance as well as the importance of impact assessment.
7. *Transparent accounting of operational results and the freedom to use a portion of earnings to address greater needs:* The transparency and proper documentation of financial transaction are enjoined by the Holy Qur'an. In surah al-Bakarah, verse 282, Allah s.w.t. says: *"O ye who believe! When you deal with each other, in transactions involving future obligations in a fixed period, reduce them to writing... and let a scribe write down faithfully as between the parties."*
8. *Strong disincentive to pursue altruism:* This part of *hadith* shows clearly that begging is discouraged in Islam. It has been allowed only to three categories of people: *"one who is in grinding poverty, one who is seriously in debt, or one who is responsible for compensation and finds it difficult to pay."*

Source: Obaidullah, M. (2008). *Introduction to Islamic Microfinance*. New Delhi, IBF Net, pp. 14-17.

Poverty is defined in Islam as a state in which a person fails to meet any of the five essential criteria, which are physical self, religion, intellect of knowledge, offspring, and riches. As a result, Islam regards poverty reduction as part of social justice and faith in Allah. Contributing zakat to the will of Allah to purify a person's wealth becomes the main source of Islam, among others. Muslims who can pay zakat are obligated to do so as a means of worshipping Allah and sharing their riches with the less fortunate. Likewise, Islam believes and recognises that all of the possessions of Muslims belong to Allah. Given this, Muslims should collaborate to improve the Ummah (community or society) (Ali al-Fijawi, 2023).

Microfinance (microcredit) has grown in importance as financial institutions feel it may help the poor and enhance their living conditions. Similarly, numerous studies have found that Muslims don't fully implement the benefits of microfinance (Karim, 2012). To bolster this argument, the Consultative Group to Assist the Poor (CGAP) discovered that around 20%–40% of respondents from 19 Muslim countries agree that religious reasons are the primary proximal contributors to microfinance underutilization. Furthermore, most Muslims consider typical microfinance policies to be in violation of the Maqasid Al-Shariah (objectives of

Islamic law). As a result, Islamic financial organisations have stepped in to meet the demands of lower-income Muslim clientele (Rahman, et al., 2015).

In this context, Islamic financial concepts and microfinance are two key aspects of dynamic change for Muslim poverty alleviation. Islamic financial principles, according to Islamic doctrine, emphasise both wealth and social equality, and it is regarded as a state of compliance with Islamic law. Microfinance, on the other hand, is still in its early stages, and interest among Muslim clients remains low.

Religion and religiosity, perceived Shariah conformity, and the religious Imam's endorsement can all impact microfinance scheme implementation. Thus, the goal of this study is to determine the elements that influence the level of intention in the use of microfinance in accordance with Islamic financial principles. The study's findings will ultimately supply decision-makers with insights about microfinance enhancement strategies.

Prospective research has demonstrated that the Theory of Planned Behaviour can be used to evaluate microfinance underutilisation. It is a commonly used theory in the prediction of behaviour in a variety of subjects of study. With this idea, it's easier to figure out how likely it is that Muslims will apply for microloans.

The notion of planned behaviour is a more comprehensive form of the theory of reasoned action. To forecast the indicated behaviour, this theory lays a strong focus on a person's intention. As a result, it claims that if the desirable intention inspires a person's behaviour, that person will engage in the desired behaviour (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1977). In the case of Muslims not using microfinance enough, it is very important to find out what makes Muslims not to use microfinance.

In conjunction with the above explanation, the fundamental constructs that contribute to predicting a behavioural intention are a person's attitude toward the behaviour, subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control. Given this, it is essential to understand how Muslims perceive microfinance, as well as the intentions of third parties and their beliefs about control, which influence their desire to apply for microfinance.

The first component, attitude toward the intended behaviour (behavioural beliefs), states that a person would consider the consequences of an intended behaviour before engaging in actual behaviour. Muslims will be more likely to use microfinance when they have a favourable

attitude toward it. Such cognitive evaluation stems from behavioural beliefs in which Muslims feel themselves to be real Muslims.

Subjective norms (normative beliefs), the second basic component, is an influential factor in which other parties influence a person and translate his beliefs into expected behaviour. Under the impact of subjective norms, a Muslim relies heavily on the approval of other Muslim people (friends, family members, Imams) or the Ummah (Muslim society) while asking for microfinance. Evidently, the other Muslims' acknowledgement holds significant weight in contributing to the level of purpose in programme application.

The third construct, perceived behavioural control (control beliefs), relates to a person's experience of their ability to carry out the desired behaviour. As a result, when a Muslim believes that microfinance may be easily adapted with few hurdles, he or she will believe that he or she can carry out the intended action to apply microfinance. Furthermore, a Muslim's control ideas may be influenced by previous experience as well as observation of others using microfinance.

In his work, Mughal (2018) addresses the sources of funding for Islamic microfinance. He proposes that the waqf fund be used for Islamic microfinance. Furthermore, in their edited book (Alpay & Haneef, 2015), Alpay and Haneef (2015) developed an integrated waqf-based Islamic microfinance (IWIM) approach for poverty reduction in Malaysia, Indonesia, and Bangladesh. In their study, Saad and Anuar (2009) investigate the possibilities of cash waqf and Islamic microfinance (Saad & Azizah, 2009).

Furthermore, Mohamed Ali (2014) proposed three poverty alleviation methods, including Zakat, Awqaf, and Islamic microfinance. There is a lot of similar research out there, but none of it connects the waqf-based Islamic microfinance programme to rehabilitation and the slum population. This is the main point of this article, which is to propose a model for the slum population. Furthermore, this article differs from past studies in that it examines the most recent scenario of waqf estates and regulators, the slum population in Muslim nations, and the position of Islamic microfinance in the Muslim world. Furthermore, it suggests a methodology for launching an Islamic microfinance and rehabilitation programme for Muslim countries' slums and floating populations using waqf funds. This model adds to previous research; earlier studies, on the other hand, only focused on waqf and Islamic microfinance separately. They

did not, however, propose using waqf funds for the slum and floating population through the Islamic microfinance scheme (Hossain, 2019).

Islamic microfinance can meet the needs of the poor for financial inclusion while also providing Muslim consumers with an Islamic option that aligns more closely with their religious and cultural requirements. 650 million Muslims around the world live in poverty, earning less than \$2 per day. Also, Islamic microfinance institutions have only tried to help 1.3 million Muslims get out of poverty out of a total population of 650 million. This means that the other 649 million Muslims need financial help through Islamic means (Obaidullah & Khan, 2008).

Microfinance programmes have grown in importance as the primary source of new job opportunities and income generation for the objective of improving the poor's social and economic status and reducing poverty. The incorporation of entrepreneurial concepts, training, and microenterprise within microfinance programmes also contributes to the program's effectiveness. Based on Shariah and Islamic finance concepts, the Islamic microfinance programme (IMP) has a high potential for assisting impoverished people in expanding and diversifying their economic activities, increasing their income, and improving their social well-being. (Nawai, 2018). Muhammad Yunus (1999) proposed a solution to world poverty based on the notion that credit is a basic human right: lend impoverished people money on their terms, teach them a few decent financial principles, and they will help themselves. Yunus is the creator of Bangladesh's Grameen Bank and a pioneer of the microcredit concept, which utilises small loans at low interest rates to transform the lives of disadvantaged individuals, primarily women. In 2006, Yunus and Grameen were jointly awarded the Nobel Peace Prize. Khandker (1995) conducted a study in Bangladesh that focused on Grameen Bank and the Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee (BRAC). He discovered that microcredit reduced poverty by up to 5% every year. Furthermore, Rena, Ravinder, and Ghirmai (2006) discovered that microfinance is the foundation for poverty alleviation. They demonstrated a crucial relationship between microfinance and poverty alleviation (Rabbani, et al., 2007).

According to the National Statistical Agencies (2010), West Java is Indonesia's most populous province. It had 43,053,732 people in 2010, with 10% of them being micro-entrepreneurs. These microentrepreneurs are classified as "economically active poor" by the World Bank (Robinson, 2001). They generate their income by working for themselves or in microenterprises (extremely tiny firms employing up to four individuals). These micro-

entrepreneurs produce a wide range of commodities in small workshops; participate in local trading and retail events; sell fruits and vegetables; or build furniture, pots, and pans (UNDP, 1999). The country comprises three provinces and one region. There are three major Baitul Mal Wa Tamwil (BMT) institutions in Indonesia: Central Java, East Java, and West Java. West Java has the most BMTs, with 637 BMTs; East Java has 600 BMTs; and Central Java has 513 BMTs. The slowdown in poverty reduction growth is related to the advancement of BMTs as Islamic microfinance institutions, which appears to be contradictory. The following research question was posed: Does Islamic microfinance have an impact on poverty alleviation in Indonesia? As a result, this study suggests investigating if Islamic microfinance has any effect on poverty alleviation in Indonesia. It is well known that Islamic microfinance institutions in Indonesia account for 60% of their market share. The microfinance sector is a crucial companion to the country's effort to reduce poverty. Specifically, those micro-entrepreneurs in traditional markets are the link to society's livelihood. The impact of access to BMT finance on microentrepreneur poverty must be estimated. This research attempts to address a vacuum in the study of poverty alleviation, as well as Islamic microfinance, in particular, on the poverty alleviation of micro-entrepreneurs, by demonstrating that the recipient financing scheme does not attend to the spiritual side (Hossain, 2019)

2.6 Islamic Microfinance Challenges

The development of Islamic microfinance institutions in the modern world has numerous positive consequences for society and the economy, as it contributes to improving the living standards of the underprivileged. Furthermore, both traditional and Islamic microfinance institutions play an important role in this society's struggle against poverty. However, when it comes to providing microfinance programmes and services to their clients, these Islamic microfinance organisations face several difficulties and challenges. Due to the layout of their branches, Islamic microfinance organisations are hampered in their outreach to unbanked individuals, particularly rural residents. Poor promotion and advertising of Islamic microfinance instruments among the populace is a contributing issue. Also, there are no good ways to teach the public, especially the poor, about the importance and benefits of the Islamic microfinance industry (Alshebami & Khandare, 2015).

Similar difficulties are encountered by Islamic microfinance organisations in Pakistan, which struggle with limited market penetration. Even though the conventional and Islamic microfinance markets in Pakistan are huge and expanding, this industry continues to face

difficulties regarding sustainability and market penetration (Karim, 2012). The second challenge that the Islamic microfinance industry faces is regulation and control. For an Islamic financial cooperative to be successful and easy for its members and customers to use, it needs to provide as many services as possible. The problem stems from the absence of regulation, monitoring, and dependable reporting. Most microfinance institutions outside of these three countries were registered as non-governmental organisations (NGOs), which meant they were unable to provide deposits in addition to loans. Thus, it creates a challenge of sustainability, especially given the importance of savings to preserving the net safety for the poor and managing their financial flow. Because of this, most of investors and commercial banks don't want to back microfinance organisations that are run by NGOs. This means that in those areas the microfinance division must rely on donors and government-funded lending programs. Inadequate infrastructure was also a problem in the microfinance sector, where the legal and regulatory framework was often not well developed and was only partially used (Karim, 2012).

Alshebami and Khandare (2015) say that infrastructure of some Islamic countries, like Yemen, is very poor. This includes things like electricity, safety, transportation, and the stability of the foreign currency. This makes it hard for Islamic microfinance institutions in these countries to stay on the market and help people with low incomes in rural areas. In addition, Islamic microfinance organisations have the issue of high operational expenses, which place a load on the deprived as the cost of loans rises. Therefore, it leads to the over-debt of clients. High operating costs also cause poor people to give up their contracts with Islamic microfinance companies and rely only on family and friends, which in their living standard does not improve (Alshebami & Khandare, 2015).

An additional problem for some countries, like Yemen, is that microfinance institutions don't have enough money or resources to reach more people in the market. According to the Islamic Finance Global Report, about 5 million potential microentrepreneurs cannot access microfinance services (Karim, 2012).

Regarding Islamic microfinance organisations in Pakistan, most potential borrowers choose not to participate in microfinance for numerous reasons, such as a absence of information, not knowing enough about money or religious beliefs. A group of researchers also did a thorough Akhuwat's financial analysis, which presented that the organisation helps both poor people living below the poverty line and impoverished people. For eliminating poverty Akhuwat's interest-free loans could be a powerful weapon. But this study showed that Akhuwat's loan

portfolio growth has slowed for five years in a row, and its equity growth has slowed dramatically. (Islamic micro-finance and poverty alleviation: A case of Pakistan. Proceedings of the 2nd CBRC, 2009) The financial stability of Akhuwat may be impacted in the future by the tendency above. However, there are several Islamic microfinance organisations in Indonesia, their size remains tiny, according to (Kazim & Haider, 2012).

Consequently, this is one of the obstacles they must overcome to appeal more customers to the industry and fight scarcity. The second issue. In Indonesia, with Islamic microfinance organisations, there is a requirement for organisational adjustments. No authority or agency monitors and supervises microfinance institutions. However, microfinance institutions provide counsel and oversight to their clients. In some nations, the slow expansion and development of the Islamic microfinance industry is an additional difficulty. The primary cause is policymakers' lack of commitment to building a more professional microfinance industry. In addition, a lack of innovation and originality prevents the introduction of new Islamic products and services to the market.

A recent study on Islamic microfinance targeting Rohingya Muslims depicts that due to the refugee crisis, many Rohingya Muslims have left Myanmar with the hope of a better life in a new place. However, they are unable to embark on economic empowerment activities due to a lack of access to banking services. Islamic microfinance has the potential to solve the financial marginalisation issue among the Rohingya refugees based on fairness, social justice, and ethics. The study aimed to assess the potential of Islamic microfinance in addressing this issue and to identify the challenges in implementing such programs. The study examined the role of Islamic microfinance in fostering entrepreneurship and socioeconomic integration and offers recommendations for its effective implementation. The study provided relevant insights for refugee policymakers, practitioners, and humanitarian organisations in tailoring interventions to the needs and aspirations of Rohingya refugees. In methodology, the study adopts qualitative semi-structured interviews with NGO experts in Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh, which is currently the centre for Rohingya refugees. The findings of the survey helped identify opportunities and challenges to assist policymakers and practitioners in successfully implementing Islamic microfinance projects, thereby boosting the chances of Rohingya refugees for a sustainable future (Nazim Uddin, et al., 2023).

Finally, the Islamic microfinance industry faces a shortage of experienced and competent staff who fulfil the requirements of Islamic microfinance organisations. To be more specific, no

Shariah counsel can consult with their Islamic microfinance organisations on a regular basis. A Shariah counsellor is needed to make sure that the goods and services offered are in line with Islamic law.

Chapter 3: Theoretical Framework: Institutional Logics Perspective

This research employed the Institutional Logics Perspective (ILP) as a theoretical and analytical framework for institutional and organisational analysis to achieve the aims and address the research questions. The selection of ILP as a theoretical framework is influenced by the literature gaps noted in the preceding chapter, which acknowledge the importance of comprehending institutional complexity as well as the role of agency in Islamic microfinance standardisation. The goal of this section is to go over the key concepts, principles, and assumptions that make up ILP and how they are used in this thesis.

This chapter tries to examine the ILP's guiding ideas and core concepts. To understand the Institutional complexity of a Religious Microfinance institution, the primary objective is to propose a theoretical framework for multi-level analysis. This chapter is divided into three sections. The first section presents an overview of ILP as well as its definition. The second section discusses ILP principles regarding the variety of institutional logic and the organisational reaction to this variety (Gümüşay, et al., 2020).

3.1 Institutional Logics Perspective

By laying the foundation for the institutional logic perspective, Friedland and Alford (1991) began a new approach to organisational and institutional studies by laying the foundation for institutional logic's perspective. Since then, ILP has undergone substantial empirical and theoretical growth. This paradigm has been a valuable instrument for responding to criticisms of the neo-institutional theory's overemphasis on institutional isomorphism and organisational homogeneity. (Friedland & Alford, 1991)

In contrast, the institutional logic perspective contends that the institutional environment is diverse, and that society is comprised of a collection of dependent, even though sometimes contradictory, inter-institutional logics accompanied by various belief systems and sources of reason. This makes ILP a unique metatheory that explains how similar organisations are and how different they can be. (Thornton, et al., 2012)

3.1.1 Definition an overview of institutional logic

In management and organisational studies, institutional theory has become "one of the most vigorous theories of the previous decades" (Meyer & Höllerer, 2010), with institutional logic being "one of the important concepts in the institutional vocabulary" (Greenwood, Oliver, Lawrence, & Meyer). The "socially constructed, historical pattern of material activities,

assumptions, values, beliefs, and rules by which people make and reproduce their material sustenance, organise time and space, and offer to mean to their social reality" is referred to as logic (Thornton & Ocasio, 2008). While the concept of institutional logic is becoming well acknowledged as a comprehensive technique in institutional analysis, there is a growing dispute about its more extensive and unthinking application (Willmott, 2015). According to Alvesson et al. (2019) the logic method is a dominant theoretical perspective that drowns out other theories and doesn't help us understand modern problems. (Alvesson, et al., 2019)

The institutional logic perspective is defined by Thornton et al. (2012) as "a metatheoretical framework for assessing the interrelationships between institutions, persons, and organisations in social systems." Greenwood et al. (2010) proposed that institutional logic shape and legitimises organisational architecture and managerial behaviours. To comprehend how and why organisations exhibit similarities and differences in these structures and behaviours, it is vital to comprehend the interaction among organisations and the logic underlying their institutional framework. (Greenwood, et al., 2010)

This theoretical model enables us to answer the question of how the social location of individual and organisational actors in an organisation influences them. It also assists in comprehending how organisations and individuals are positioned in numerous institutional logics and elucidating the varied implications of this circumstance on organisational behaviour and cognition ((Thornton, 2002)

3.2 Institutional Logics and Organisational Responses

3.2.1 Institutional logics

The fundamental theoretical progress being made by Friedland and Alford (1991) is based on their innovative conception of society as an interinstitutional system. They contend that society is structured by institutions or "institutional orders" that exist and potentially conflict with one another. According to Thornton et al. (2012), ILP employs a subsystem framework that identifies society as a set of discrete, conceptualised institutions.

Every institution is characterised by a number of rules, reinforced by cultural symbols and material activities that govern and provide significance to a particular area of life. In this subsystem, it is feasible to establish which social norms are more significant than others in a certain area. People and organisations are more likely to be centred within one or more institutional orders than others (Thornton et al. 2012, Besharov and Smith 2014). Friedland and Alford (1991) identified five institutional orders in western society: the

bureaucratic state, the democratic market, the nuclear family, and the Christian faith. Thornton (2002) utilised this work to construct industry logics in the form of ideal types. In Thornton's later publications, these ideal kinds have been refined and enlarged to encompass a variety of institutional orders (Thornton 2004, Thornton and Ocasio 2008, Thornton et al. 2012). Thornton et al. (2012) proposed in their most recent framework an inter-institutional system with seven institutional orders: family, community, religion, state, market, profession, and corporation. In their proposed typology, these orders are called the X-axis (Thornton et al. 2012).

Moreover, each of these institutional systems is composed of elemental categories that symbolise the cultural symbols and material behaviours that support that order. In other words, each order is characterised by a unique set of expectations (logic) that define its rationality. As they are a component of the social system of a particular society, the behaviour, interests, and legitimated of individuals and organisations are formed, influenced, and legitimised by the rationality driven by these institutional systems' underlying logic (Friedland and Alford 1991). Thornton et al. (2012) refers to the Y-axis as these elemental groupings. According to Thornton et al. (2012), the principles, symbols, and practises of each institutional order impact "how reasoning occurs and how rationality is perceived and experienced" in distinct ways. This implies that rationality varies in accordance with the distinct logics of various institutional regimes. More intriguingly, numerous institutional rationalities may exist in a given circumstance, causing individuals and organisational actors to respond differently, affected by distinct reference systems (Lounsbury, 2008) (Greenwood, et al., 2010).

ILP departs from the concepts of neo-institutional theory, which implies mindless cognition and an institutional (irrational) interpretation of rationality, according to this conception of institutional orders. Also, it does not entail institutional isomorphism but instead permits cultural and institutional variation, since varied institutional environments and orders create culture (Thornton et al. 2012). This variability permits personal and organisational autonomy in which organisations define reason in accordance with the values, practices, and root metaphors of their home (or dominant) institutional regimes (Friedland and Alford 1991, Thornton et al. 2012).

3.2.2 The Multiplicity of Institutional Logics

According to Meyer and Rowan (1977), institutional contexts are pluralistic. They claim that, because of this diversity and in their pursuit of external assistance and stability, organisations embrace and adhere to a wide range of institutional needs. This view is supported by Friedland

and Alford (1991), who discuss the multitude of institutional logics that organisations might or might not embrace and which might or might not be contradictory. Similarly, Thornton et al. (2012) assert that organisations have numerous institutional logics, which are reflected in their structures and behaviours. Greenwood et al. (2010) coined the term "institutional complexity" to describe circumstances in which organisations are subjected to a variety of pressures resulting from several institutional logics. They require a grasp of how organisations respond to certain institutional complexity. (Meyer & Rowan, 1977) (Meyer & Höllerer, 2010)

The topic of institutional logic multiplicity has received substantial attention in the academic literature. Scholars have explored this issue and its ramifications from many disciplinary and methodological viewpoints. Besharov and Smith (2014) present a quick summary of the literature on this subject. In terms of the repercussions of the plurality of institutional logics within organisations, they note that the literature suggests varying results. They explain that while some scholars equate logic's plurality with conflict and instability, others explain the potential of logic's coexisting in harmony, or "logic blending." They allude to instances in the literature where the presence of numerous logics is viewed as a threat that may result in the demise of an organisation, but in other instances, the presence of multiple logics makes organisations more stable, sustainable, and innovative. But they say that there isn't much information in the current literature about what causes these different outcomes. According to Besharov and Smith (2014), the primary disagreement in the literature concerns the interaction between logics and whether they complement or contradict one another. Meyer and Hollerer (2010) outline many interactions that might develop between distinct institutional logics by stating, "logics can cohabit quietly, compete, supplant one another, meld or hybridise, or strike a temporary truce." In this way, Besharov and Smith (2014) talk about research in which organisations represent multiple institutional orders in a way that is mostly compatible. Similarly, Kodeih and Greenwood (2014) argue, using empirical examples from the literature, that institutional logics can interact and coexist in a variety of ways in which neither unique order can be deemed dominant. On the other hand, Friedland and Alford (1991), in their early theory, feel that different institutional logics are inconsistent. This is because each collection of logic corresponds to a distinct belief system and source of rationality. Similarly, Thornton et al. (2012) stress that each institutional order presents a unique vision of rationality, which leads to inconsistencies inside organisations because organisations are positioned within and impacted by various sectors of different institutional regimes.

Some scholars ascribe the position of conflict and competition across institutional logics to the predicament that satisfying one institution's demand may infringe on the rights of others

(Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978, cited in Pache and Santos 2010). In this context, Heimer (1999) argues that "the adoption of a policy or practice that conveys a favourable message to one audience may simultaneously send an objectionable response to another" (p. 18). Therefore, some academics do not believe that two logics can equally dominate the same topic. This is due to new logic coming to dominate a particular field; organisational actors modify their norms and practises to align with those associated with the new dominant logic (Ezzamel et al. 2012).

3.2.3 Organisational Responses to Institutional Logics

Friedland and Alford (1991) dispute DiMaggio and Powell's (1983) argument regarding passive organisational conformity to institutional demands and the concept of isomorphic organisational fields. However, they emphasise the possibility for variations, tensions, and autonomy in organisational forms and activities as they are linked to distinct societal-level institutional regimes. According to Pache and Santos (2010), not all organisations respond to competing institutional requirements in the same way because institutional logic is executed differently by various organisations. They establish that organisations can exhibit strategic choice in reacting to many logics that determine their institutional framework. Similarly, Greenwood et al. (2011) suggest in their work "Institutional Complexity and Organizational Responses" that because organisations experience institutional complexity to varying degrees, this indicates that they may respond differently to this complexity.

Organizational structures and practices, as previously indicated, are embodiments of distinct institutional logic. To comprehend organisational behaviour and the application of such structures and practises, it is vital to comprehend the interaction between organisations and the logic that comprises their institutional environment. It is stated here that organisations respond by incorporating "all sorts of contradictory structural components" in their quest for external support and endorsement from the relevant audiences (Meyer and Rowan 1977, p. 356). The character of an organization's response to institutional demands is essential in this context. This is because how an organisation reacts to such demands has significant ramifications for its social legitimacy and access to essential resources (Greenwood et al. 2011). Failure to pursue organisational practices justified by prevalent logic can have negative effects. The very survival of the organisation may be jeopardised (Greenwood et al. 2010; Greenwood et al. 2011).

According to Thornton et al. (2012), using ILP to analyse organisational reactions to institutional logic is an attractive new research topic. Despite acknowledging the significance

of understanding how organisations respond to various institutional logics underpinning their institutional context, Kodeih and Greenwood (2014) report that most empirical studies have been devoted to the institutional field with the goal of understanding how institutional commands promote, diffuse, and maintain their logics at a certain level. They go on to say that relatively little research has looked into how organisations deal with and respond to the requirements of those logic. Pache and Santos (2010) agree on this point, stating that while institutional scholars recognise the importance of multiple, conflicting institutional demands that influence organisational behaviour, there is still a lack of a clear framework that allows for systematic understanding and prediction of how organisations will conduct and respond to the influence of such conflicting institutional prescriptions.

There have subsequently been some efforts to comprehend and theorise the patterns by which organisations deal with and respond to institutional complexity. For example, Greenwood et al. (2010), follow the problem of organisational downsizing in Spain. They investigate the effects of various institutional arrangements on organisational downsizing and propose that organisations respond to their institutional environments in a variety of but patterned ways. They discovered specific patterns that govern how organisations behave and make downsizing decisions. Greenwood et al. extended this work with another theoretical study (2011). They investigate how organisational field structure (fragmentation, formal structuring/rationalization, and centralisation/unification) and organisational features or 'filters' (field position, structure, ownership and governance, and identity) influence organisational responses in this article. Another example is Pache and Santos'(2010) study on the theorisation of organisational responses to institutional logics is another example (2010). Pache and Santos (2010) aim in their study to develop a more systematic model of organisational responses that take Intra organizational political ties into account. Organizational responses to multiple institutional logics are hypothesised based on the centrality of these logics to the organization's mission and goals, the extent to which these logics are represented within the organisation, and the power balance between the representatives of different logics, expanding on the model developed by Oliver (1991).

3.2.4 History of Institutional Logic

One of the major meta-theoretical assumptions of ILP is the historical contingency of institutional logic. Thornton et al. (2012) believe that the prevalence of specific institutional logics in an organisation, as well as the interconnections between these logics, evolve over time and between settings. Modern societies, for example, are more influenced by the logic of the

state, professions, corporations, and markets than by the logic of family and religion, which were more important in the past.

Although the dominance of institutional commands fluctuates over time, Thornton et al. (2012) contends that the emergence and rise of one institutional order corresponding to another do not always follow a linear progression in the context that the dominance of one institutional order somehow doesn't necessarily entirely replace another. According to Thornton and Ocasio (2008), recognising historical contingency as a meta-theoretical premise in ILP intends to investigate whether the impacts of institutional demands alter over time. They go on to say that the goal of this assumption is not to theorise organisation performance based on this circumstance, but rather to find out if theories of organisational behaviour that are thought to be universal across time and space are, in fact, specific to a certain time and institutional context.

3.2.5 Institutional Logics Perspective in Islamic Microfinance

In organisational studies, ILP has been frequently used to describe organisational practices and behaviour. ILP and the theory of institutional logic have also been used extensively in management accounting and management system control studies (for example (Jayasinghe & Wickramasinghe, 2011), Ezzamel et al. 2012). Some of these works used the word "logic" while not applying Friedland and Alford's (1991) approach or its developments. On the other hand, the ILP paradigm is rarely used in financial accounting research. In this context, some organisational studies have looked into the institutional logics that exist in accounting businesses and how they have evolved through time (Thornton et al. 2005, Greenwood and Suddaby 2006, (Lander, et al., 2013). However, studies on the role of institutional logic in influencing the selection of accounting practises, systems, and standards at the organisational and national stages; the role of institutional logics in the process of establishing accounting standards; and the institutional logics that shape the decisions and policies of accounting standard-setting bodies are lacking. For example, Guerreiro et al. (2012) integrated Oliver's (1991) approach with the concept of institutional logic to explore the incentives for voluntary adoption of IFRS by unlisted enterprises in Portugal. Susela (1999) undertook an intriguing study in this regard, looking into the conflict of interests in Malaysia's standard-setting process, with a particular focus on generosity standards. Although the fact is that she did not rely on the work of Friedland and Alford (1991) or the term "logic," she did employ the concepts of ILP as a theoretical framework. Susela (1999) bases this essay on the work of Streeck and Schmitter (1985) and Puxty et al. (1987), who consider four "organising

principles" of accounting regulations: state, profession, market, and community. She emphasises that inside each principle there are individuals that represent and defend that principle's interests. Susela (1999) concludes from an analysis of those actors' speeches that the process of defining goodwill norms was determined by the interplay and competition between actors' interests as well as the balance of power among these actors. She believes that the standard-setting procedure was not dominated by similar interests (logics); rather, the balance of power had evolved over time from profession to market representatives, and the standard-setting process was dominated by the market as a result.

Moving on to Islamic micro-finance studies, a survey of the literature reveals that, to the utmost of the researcher's knowledge, ILP has rarely been used in studies related to Islamic finance for a matter of fact for Islamic Microfinance Institutions. Piefer (2014) used ILP while working on Islamic mutual funds and societal logic. Kamla and Haque (2017) employed the "collaborative theory of imperialism" as a theoretical framework. Religiously based expectations that distinguish Islamic micro-finance from conventional accounting methods have substantially dominated the field of Islamic micro-finance research. However, according to Maali (2005), while religion has an impact, it is not the ultimate institutional driver of Islamic corporate entities' systems. So, it's important to understand the wide range of elements and institutional expectations that make up financial reporting for these kinds of businesses. In the same way, to understand Islamic micro-finance standardisation programs, you need to understand the institutional logics that guides them and how they balance (or prioritize) different needs while coming up with standardisation strategies.

3.2.6 Islamic Micro-financial: Institutional Logics and Organisational Responses

This study analyses case study of Akhuwat (IMI) to establish their organisational responses. Grasping these programmes necessitates a thorough understanding of their contextual and institutional contexts. ILP is useful for this because there are many different institutional concerns, expectations, and other factors that affect the decision to use Islamic micro-finance standards. To gain a deeper understanding of how microfinance is financed, the institutional logic viewpoint is used and expanded upon to examine the lending practises of commercial and public funders, which together supply most of the capital for global microfinance. Different forms of MFOs attract different sorts of funders because they adhere to distinct financial and development logic. However, in conditions of ambiguity, a convergence of practices inspired by these logics will occur in ways that are damaging to a country's microfinance sector.

Research reveals that the effectiveness of microfinance as a strategy for alleviating poverty is highly dependent on the specific context in which it is implemented (Cobb, et al., 2016).

3.2.7 Islamic Micro-finance in Pakistan

In the first instance, this research investigates the influence and impact of two institutional logics on the above-mentioned research. Religion as logic and social welfare are examples of institutional logic. Both institutional logics have a significant influence, to varying degrees, on Akhuwat. This research examines religion as a significant institutional order represented by religious beliefs, principles, and values that influence all aspects of life, including business and accounting practices. This institutional system is regarded to be the ultimate cause of legitimacy for programmes primarily intended to promote Islamic micro-finance and provide interest-free loans. The social welfare logic on the other hand, is portrayed in this study by the amount of welfare work done by Akhuwat and their efforts to poverty alleviation.

Greenwood et al. (2011) say that institutional logic research shouldn't just focus on two logics that are at odds with each other. Because of the high level of complexity in the institutional context of organisations, any findings based on this narrow scope may be invalid. This complexity may be overestimated and misconstrued under this limited perspective. As a result, Greenwood et al. (2011) advocate a thorough awareness of the many institutional logics accessible in a particular setting, stating that "logics may support each other" (p. 332). Similarly, in Islamic micro-finance studies. Maali (2005) advocates the investigation of a broad range of institutional "secular" variables that support Islamic financial institutions. Taking this accusation into account, this research looks at the role of religion, social welfare and commerce in shaping the organisational identity of Akhuwat.

Furthermore, this study attempts to investigate how diverse institutional logics have influenced Islamic micro-finance standardisation projects, as well as how these accounting standard-setting bodies have historically responded to those different logics. The subject of organisational reactions to institutional logics, as indicated above in Section, is under-researched in the institutional logics' literature (Pache and Santos 2010, Kodeih and Greenwood 2014). As a result, it is critical to address this issue in a unique subject such as Islamic microfinance institution, which is governed by several nationalities, each with its own source of legitimacy.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the organisational responses of Akhuwat in experiencing more than one institutional logic. Institutional theorists typically contrast formal

institutions, such as the government and the military, with informal institutions, which relate to patterns of connections based on culture and values. Both formal and informal institutions might be weak or robust, therefore it would be foolish to believe that there is a clear distinction between them (Bratton, 2007). Formally, Pakistan possesses an elected constitutional government, a well-trained army, an education system, and the rule of law. The formal institutions generally work well in established urban areas, in contrast to the countryside. Some of these are still underdeveloped, and tribal agencies or networks are dominant in governance, including their own traditions and ideals. (Muhammad, et al., 2016)

The ILP literature makes it easier to understand these kinds of differences within a given field. This is because there can be more than one institutional rationale in each field, which can cause individual and organisational actors to respond in different ways (Lounsbury 2008, Greenwood et al. 2010). This makes it both interesting and important to look into the differences in context between the two projects under consideration so that we can get a clear picture of the institutional logic behind the goal of creating Islamic reporting systems on both the national and international levels.

The first 2 research objectives are consistent with ILP, which is characterised by its balanced perspective on the agential role of actors and absolute institutional requirements. According to ILP, the following parts provide insight into the functions of the agency and actors.

3.3 The Role of Actors and Institutional Complexity

3.3.1 Social Structure and Agency in the Institutional Logics Perspective

Thornton et al. (2012) examined the historical dispute in the social sciences between researchers who emphasise the restrictions of social structure on behaviour and those who emphasise how individuals and organisations create, develop, and preserve institutions through their actions. The latter party tends to separate an organisation from its social setting and analyse the rationality of players' roles and decisions. In contrast, institutional theorists examine the influence of social surroundings on the behaviour, preferences, and choices of actors. They show that organisational activity patterns are not just driven by practical concerns (Meyer and Rowan 1977; DiMaggio and Powell 1983). Instead, they are driven by institutional frameworks. In this sense, neo-institutionalism posits that the behaviour of actors is determined by their need to be viewed as legitimate inside their institutional setting. As a result, this idea was utilised to propose and explain organisational uniformity within organisational sectors. In

fact, neo-institutional theory adds to the study of organisations by pointing out how important the social environments in which they operate are and by explaining why similar things are seen in different organisations that face the same institutional constraints. However, it has been criticised for having an overly socialised view of the action, focusing on the passive behaviour of individual and organisational actors and failing to explain how they act as agents (Oliver 1991, Hirsch and Lounsbury 1997).

In their theory, Friedland and Alford (1991) reject rational choice theory's methodological requirements. In addition, they reject the structural determinism of neo-institutional theory. In contrast, Friedland and Alford (1991) describe the behaviour of individuals as "nested" within the common institutional frameworks, which provide specific opportunities and restrictions for their performance. According to Thornton et al. (2012), p. 6, the fundamental premise of the institutional logic approach is that "individuals' and organisations' interests, identities, beliefs, and assumptions are entrenched within prevalent institutional logics." Given the availability of several institutional logics, each with its own sense of rationality, individuals are free to choose which of these logics they will rely on in their actions (Friedland and Alford 1991). Individual and organisational actors are somewhat independent because they can conceptualise actions and act in accordance with alternative interpretations of rationality. Rather than being institutionally defined, the behaviour of these players is institutionally facilitated and limited, according to this theory.

Thornton et al. (2012) summarised their viewpoint in a few words: "human behaviour is placed, embedded, and intentionally constrained." They say that this idea, which they call "embedded agency," is what sets ILP apart from the rational choice model, which says that people have their own wants, and from macro-structural determinism, which says that structure is more important than action.

In contrast, ILP offers a balanced perspective on social systems and agency. This interaction between institutional structures and human initiative influences organisational decisions, behaviours, and outcomes (Thornton and Ocasio 2008).

3.3.2 Role of actors and institutional Complexity

The actors who bring their own perception of reason to the decision-making process impact the organization's decision. Consequently, actors are regarded as bearers of institutional logic (Friedland and Alford 1991; Thornton et al. 2012). Pache and Santos (2010) emphasise the significance of individuals who serve as "internal representations" of particular institutional

logics in advocating organisational policies that are congruent with the logics they represent. In a similar vein, Besharov and Smith (2014) contend that while institutional logics influence the cognition and behaviour of actors, the players themselves influence and define how logics are implemented within organisations. ILP helps in this situation to understand "how actors' choices are affected by specific frames of reference that inform their sensemaking, motivational vocabulary, and identities they bring to situations" (Ezzamel, et al., 2012), pp. 283-284). ILP gives actors a list of social reasons why their actions are okay (Friedland and Alford, 1991). Nevertheless, the behaviour of actors can both strengthen and contradict the logic deemed proper in a given setting. Thornton and Ocasio (2008), on page 100, talk about how logic and actors work together. They say that "institutional logics create rational, self-aware behaviour, and individual and organisational actors have a hand in creating and changing institutional logics." This leads to a kind of institutional entrepreneurship, which will be talked about in more detail in the next section.

3.4 Framework and Objectives

Table 4.0 presents the conceptual framework employed in this research. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, utilising both qualitative and quantitative methods. First, the qualitative method is used and then the quantitative method is used using independent and dependent variables as depicted by the table. The Independent variable is Islamic microfinance, and the institutional logic perspective serves as the theoretical framework. The dependent variables are poverty alleviation and organisational response.

In addition, the purpose of this research is to analyse the potential role of actors whose institutional logics are in contradiction with the objectives of Islamic microfinance in obstructing and exerting resistance to these objectives. From a different perspective, it can be claimed that actors involved in the creation of Akhuwat (IMI) are profoundly influenced by the institutional logics of the socioeconomic sectors to which they belong. These actors, for instance, serve as guides for religion and the welfare of the community. They must also have a solid understanding of Shariah and Islamic microfinance principles. In addition, they are influenced by the commerce and sustainability are incorporated into the values and conventions of their own societies. As stated by Thornton et al. (2012), this exposure to a variety of institutional logic equips students with the ability to recognise and utilise various parts of these institutional logics (2012). Thornton et al. (2012) explain the repeated embedding of players in several institutional systems heightens their knowledge of the existence of alternative options and stimulates institutional entrepreneurship. Given this rationale, the purpose of this study is to determine whether these players have acted as institutional entrepreneurs by leveraging their awareness and activity in various institutional settings. This study also employs Thornton et al.'s (2012) thesis regarding how institutional entrepreneurs exploit and rearrange institutional logic's fundamental characteristics. This is to evaluate the efforts of participants in Islamic microfinance standardisation projects to produce an appropriate combination of parts from various institutional logic to develop a framework for Islamic micro-financial reporting.

3.5 Summary

As a theoretical and analytic foundation for this argument, this chapter introduced the institutional logic perspective (ILP). It provided an outline of the ILP's concepts and principles, discussing why this framework is important to the study's aims and how it has been implemented. The following chapter describes the research design employed to operationalize this theoretical framework in the organisational and institutional analysis presented in the findings and discussion chapters.

Chapter 4 Research Methodology

Business research cannot be undertaken in a vacuum, but intellectual traditions are an essential component of the social science research process. These intellectual traditions manifest themselves in numerous ways, such as philosophical ideas, which influence how social science and business research are performed (Bell, et al., 2011). Extensively recognised research output is supported by reliable research methodology/methods that explain and analyse the data used in the study, as well as provide a more profound knowledge of the research conclusions.

This section's purpose is to introduce the research strategy used in this study and to describe the research techniques that were put into play to attain the study's targets. The introduction explains the thesis's philosophical and methodological stance and justifies the use of that stance over others. Next, the chapter dives into the specifics of the study's methodology, including how the data was collected and analysed. Before wrapping up the chapter, some final thoughts are offered on validity and reliability. As the preceding chapters have shown, the author has relied on several established models and a well-developed conceptual framework to guide their investigation. This chapter, therefore, provides details on the study technique, which includes the research paradigm, research approach, research plan, data collection, and data interpretation. This chapter's goal is to explain why certain research methods were used and what conclusions were made about this study based on those methods.

4.1 Research Methodology using Honeycomb

This study was revised with the goal of providing a guide to assist the researcher to approve one or more research methodologies or procedures, and this assessment serves as the logical foundation for how this chapter is built. This study used a mixed-method approach, including qualitative research and a survey, which were determined using factor analysis and cluster analysis. Inferential statistics were used to test hypotheses.

The following sources were used to address the issue of study methodology: Bryman and Bell (2004; 2007 & 2011); Fisher (2004); Kumar (2014); Saunders and Thornhill (2009); Saunders et al. (2012); Wilson (2014); and Velde (2004). Saunders' research onion (layers) is the most popular structure in the previous list. Various research methodologies show the research process as a linear diagram (Bell et al., 2011) or a sequence of layers and building blocks (Saunders, et al., 2009). Some of them, referenced in earlier literature, lack logical steps or flowcharts. These approaches are great for exhibiting aspects of research methodologies, but

they often fail to address essential issues and demonstrate the methodology and its components logically. Wilson (2014) designed a research process graphic called the honeycomb (or mesh). It sermonises the fundamental problems and puts up a logical pathway. The honeycomb shows six important parts: the research philosophy, approach, strategy, design, data collection, and analysis.

Wilson's research was not interdisciplinary. Each element of the research, including the approach, is explicitly stated in the honeycomb. The honeycomb-style steps make it impossible to miss one or two out of six

Mesh or network shapes might represent stage connections. Instead of a linear progression or layers of procedures, the phases are intertwined and interdependent. Other research doesn't exploit the honeycomb's natural node interconnections (Wilson, 2010). Many published research papers don't follow the logical and sequential order of honeycomb mesh procedures. It is difficult to write a research technique that uses all the study procedures. This study uses honeycomb methodology founded by Wilson's (2014) as it guides through the process in a fluent way comparing to other methodologies.

Figure 4.1: The Honeycomb of Research Methodology (Wilson, 2014)

4.1.1 Research philosophy

Research philosophy affects research outcomes. It's the researcher's perspective on the world and the significance they assign to various aspects of reality and truth. Ontology and epistemology are key research philosophy problems. These criteria help improve research quality and inventiveness. Understanding these three criteria not only aids in raising the bar for research quality but also boosts research originality. There is a lot of ambiguity surrounding these criteria, so they must be explained very clearly before they can be used.

The underlying research philosophy employed throughout the research effort is about the researcher's viewpoint and is based on some essential traditions (Saunders, et al., 2009). These outline the researcher's traditions of the following research to generate an accepted conclusion as part of the research. The significance of having a concise research philosophy cannot be overstated; among the reasons for this are that it aids in the illumination of study design, dealing with the types of data required (secondary/primary), and selecting the collection strategy and techniques of interpretation and analysis. Second, a researcher with a sound philosophical background may understand which study designs work best and which do not, which indicates that these fundamental traditions act in such a manner that they influence the research strategy and methodology (Saunders, et al., 2009); (Wilson, 2014). Furthermore, the research philosophy is of immense support to the research in its capacity to adapt and acknowledge the research design while considering the varied knowledge structures and any restricting variables. So, it can help a researcher use the data they already have to make a proposal that considers the limits of the research, (Saunders and Thornhill, 2009; Wilson, 2014).

Research Assumptions

Research Hypotheses

This analysis of the institutional complexity of the religious microfinance entity Akhuwat is based on three essential assumptions that direct the research methodology. These assumptions are essential to ensure the validity and trustworthiness of the results.

The presence of institutional logics suggests that diverse frameworks function within Islamic microfinance, shaping the organisational identity and operational practices of organisations such as Akhuwat. These logics encompass religious moral imperatives, economic considerations, and social welfare goals.

The research asserts that religion, as an institutional framework, significantly impacts the organisational identity of Islamic microfinance institutions. This assumption suggests that Akhuwat's policies and initiatives will reflect Islamic ideas, beliefs, and practices.

Individuals perceive that institutional complexity constitutes a structural reality for Islamic microfinance institutions. This complexity stems from the interaction of many institutional logics, which may sometimes contradict, requiring the development of adaptive techniques to address these issues.

Poverty Alleviation as a Measurable Outcome: The research asserts that Islamic microfinance institutions, such as Akhuwat, provide initiatives and interventions that have a quantifiable effect on poverty reduction and client welfare. This assumption highlights the necessity for empirical research on the performance outcomes of such organisations.

The corporate identity, influenced by religious institutional logic, is said to impact the perspectives of diverse stakeholders, such as clients, employees, and regulatory authorities. This hypothesis posits that stakeholder perception has a profound impact on the interpretation and management of institutional complexity.

Methodological Rigour: The study assumes that the utilised methodology, including as case studies, interviews, and performance analytics, will produce reliable and valid insights on the dynamics of institutional complexity and their implications for religious microfinance institutions.

The unified interpretation and application of religious principles by the management and staff of an Islamic microfinance institution is believed to influence the overall organisational culture and decision-making processes.

The study seeks to create a cohesive framework for analysing the intricate relationships between religion, organisational identity, and institutional complexity in Islamic microfinance by outlining these assumptions. These assumptions will be crucial as they are evaluated and adjusted during the research process to clarify how religious institutions manage various logics while achieving their primary objective of poverty reduction.

Research Objectives

1. To explore religion as an institutional logic and its role in shaping the organisational identity of an Islamic Microfinance organisation.
2. To explore the response of an Islamic Microfinance organisation towards multiple institutional logics while experiencing institutional complexity.
3. To investigate the performance of Islamic Microfinance organisations, their effects on poverty alleviation and the welfare of their clients.

Research Question 1 is related to research Objective 1 and Research Question 2 is related to research Objectives 2 and 3.

4.1.2 Research Paradigms

In addition to other characteristics, this study will make use of the selected research philosophy and methodological framework (or paradigms) in order to really discover the appropriate tools for this investigation in the realm of business and the social sciences (Bell, et al., 2011) Similar to the honeycomb approach, Grix (2002) demonstrated the usage of research building blocks by relating five distinct steps: ontology, epistemology, methodology, methodologies, and sources. It has been acknowledged, as part of enclosing the philosophical assumptions in research, that researchers face the difficulty determining how to interconnect ideas, their It has been acknowledged, as part of enclosing the philosophical assumptions in research, that researchers face the difficulty of determining how to interconnect ideas, their Grix's (2002) building blocks were also utilised about research techniques and their philosophical assumptions with the express goal of providing additional insight. In agreement with the philosophical approaches of this study, Saunders et al. (2012) stated that the research onion and its layers are exposed to the effect of the research philosophy/approach in the framework of their characters in the research procedure. To answer/support the above four questions, this chapter and its constituent sections will explain further the various theorems as well as integrate them and especially display this study as a component of social science, and the workings required to create this are detailed below.

4.1.2.1 Epistemology

Epistemology is the study of how and why people come to know certain things, and the role that theories play in this process or in the perspective of social realities and social entities, epistemology is defined as the "theory of knowing" or the successful completion of knowledge (Barnett, 2021) (Steup, et al., 2020). It helps in a way that allows the researcher to ponder the universe at large. This is concerned with the supreme method of enquiring into the essential component of knowledge and what is generally accepted as the genuine nature of that knowledge (Bell, et al., 2022). Constructionism, objectivism, and subjectivism are the three most widely used epistemological perspectives in research. (Al-Ababneh, 2020)

The research methodology is established on beliefs that guide the path to numerous concepts and provide the researchers with a worldview (Lincoln & Guba, 1990). The research philosophy is an essential component since it helps determine the study design. (Saunders et al., 2009) Based on the opinions of researchers, there are three sorts of research methodologies, which are as follows:

i) Positivism

Positivism provides assurance of exact and precise world knowledge. This methodology convinces the researcher that "science" is the foundation of accurate knowledge because it accepts or rejects facts that contribute to the generation of knowledge. Positive science is not based on speculation but on real experience. Thus, positivists or positive science refer to the scientific observation of what is hypothesised or derived from direct experience. In positivism, the philosophical study is conducted objectively, without influencing the issue being examined. Therefore, positivism demands extremely well-designed techniques, measurable observations, and statistical analysis (Remenyi, et al., 2005). Consequently, positivism requires that researchers conduct an objective examination and interpretation of collected data throughout the whole study process (Saunders, et al., 2009). The importance of this impartiality from samples is to establish a general rule that can be applied to the full population, such as predicting behaviour or explaining relationships. To support the outcome of a study, positivists rely on facts rather than opinions. Experiments are used in social research in the same way that they are used in scientific research. If a researcher's method is like that of a natural science, the researcher may have a positivist view of how we know what we know. (Bryman and Bell, 2011; and Wilson, 2014). (Easterby-Smith, et al., 2004)

ii) Interpretivism

Interpretivism generates knowledge by developing a comprehension of the world in which the researcher desires to live and interpreting it from their experiences in certain situations. Interpretivism generates knowledge in various systems by emphasising subjective and descriptive approaches to deal with complex situations, as opposed to an objective and statistical approach to comprehend the existing social realities and environment in which the research is conducted. (Blaikie, 2010.); (Scotland, 2012). Therefore, according to this school of thought, researchers must have experience with the social world they are researching, and the researcher is impacted by the universal perspective of the participants, their ideas, agreements, and the insight of others, making the research subjective. (Fisher, 2004)

iii) Pragmatism

Pragmatism asserts that assurance exists in the world and that science is objective. Individuality might affect how people perceive the world, according to this theory, and hence research is subjective. This philosophy's perception includes numerous descriptions and interpretations of science. This philosophy employs both objective and subjective criteria. Saunder (2003) and

colleagues This method will be used by researchers who are required to use mixed methodologies, i.e., quantitative, and qualitative research. This method combines positivism with interpretivism (Jonhson, et al., 2008). In epistemology, pragmatism claims that it is likely to operate with variations, and the debate is between interpretivism and positivism.

This study uses Pragmatism as quantitative and qualitative data were collected sequentially, and then analysed and interpreted, and includes data integration using either quantitative or qualitative approaches, or both, to produce the final output (Creswell & Clark, 2011). Furthermore, both are used in this study at different stages of the research.

4.1.2.2 Ontology

Ontology, the study of reality and reality's nature, requires the awareness of a narrow field and can serve as a barometer of reality. It refers to the philosophical investigation of the nature of presence, becoming, existence, or reality, as well as the fundamental groupings of existence and their relationships (Glattfelder, 2019). Ontology has always dealt with essential concerns about social responsibilities, which must be understood as objective or subjective. Simply put, we must determine if the world is an outward-looking social world or whether social phenomena are created by the perceptions and activities of social performers (Wilson, 2010). So, objectivism and subjectivism are seen as two different ways of looking at ontological ideas.

Subjectivism is a school of thought related to social constructivism or interpretivism, but it emphasises that social phenomena are constructed from the perceptions and subsequent acts of socially concerned stakeholders about their existence (Saunders, et al., 2012). Subjectivity and interpretivism are interwoven when the links between motivation and social ties of organisations being monitored are considered (Bryman, 2012).

Objectivism, On the other hand, presents a scenario in which social beings exist in real life outside of the social players who are obsessed with their existence. Objectivism, on the other hand, "is an ontological position that maintains social phenomena and their meanings have a reality free of social groups."

The researchers need to make assumptions about ontology and epistemology in order to design methodologies and study them. The research philosophy which will be applied to this study is epistemology since this research will use concepts that already exist and will aid in understanding how and why what happened occurred.

4.1.2.3 Axiology /Research Values

Axiology, or research values, is focused on the nature of the principles of the study being performed. It is focused on assessing the role of researchers' personal values throughout the study process (Li, 2016). In a nutshell, axiology is concerned with determining what to value in a study. This is crucial because values influence how to do studies and what to value in research conclusions. They also reveal the vital nature of the study's growth. According to the positivist viewpoint, research begins in a value-free manner where the researcher is independent of the research effort and maintains an impartial attitude. Properly organised data gathering approaches, big samples, measurements, and quantitative and qualitative analysis are all popular. Similarly, the interpretivist approach to research is value-bound; what is being investigated is intertwined with the researcher and cannot be detached, hence it will be subjective. In this sector, small samples, in-depth inquiry, and quantitative analysis are prominent data collection approaches. (Wilson et al., 2014; Kumar et al., 2014; Saunders et al., 2009). In this study, positivism was utilised since it provides inventive and original insights to research endeavours, a criterion that was utilised to justify its application. Saunder et al. (2003) And positivism is methodologically and theoretically adequate and rigorous for this research endeavour. Similarly, to interpretivism (by the researcher, a vigorous role in the study is being carried out). This is since other schools of thought will not provide the best solution or ways to achieve the study's goal and objectives. While pragmatism differs between these two paradigms by considering both the physical and social realms This thesis seeks to answer research problems using a variety of methodologies; the method (positivist philosophy) is best addressed using surveys and secondary data.

The research approach that will be employed in this study will be pragmatism, as it will aid in comprehending the respondents' many truths. This variety of realities is frequently held by the intuitive knowledge of the organization's members and is difficult to quantify, making an interpretive approach ideal because it can only untangle and perceive. The research questions will be investigated through direct observations, semi-structured interviews, and a questionnaire (Lincoln & Guba, 1990).

4.1.3 Research Paradigms and Methodological Selections

Any area of inquiry proceeds through explicit or implicit rules about the state of the world and the way it can be searched, much like a paradigm. These conventions have immediate repercussions on the design and execution of research. 2017. To "be detected within a particular

paradigm is to observe the world in a specific way," claim Burrell and Morgan (1979). According to this viewpoint, a research paradigm is a plan that specifies how to perceive, think, and behave, as well as the eventual course of action to be performed in relation to the research subject. According to Burrell and Morgan, a research paradigm consists of three levels: the philosophical level, which represents the fundamental truths about the world in which we live; the social level, which offers advice on how researchers should conduct their research; and the technical level, which when conducting research acknowledges the techniques and procedures that can be confirmed. Considering the philosophical underpinnings of the three methodological paradigms (positivist, interpretative, and critical paradigms) that social researchers often examine, the researchers in this study chose to use the interpretive research paradigm as their frame of reference.

The positivist paradigm assumes that reality is outside of and completely unrelated to human agents. Situations can be observed, facts gathered, and variables objectively validated. Priest and Knight (2009)

Remenyi (1998) asserts that the positivist researcher is neither influenced by nor unaffected by the research topic. As a result, knowledge derived from positivist research is regarded as being objective, despite the fact that this type of research is primarily concerned with the confidence that social actors and their connections are self-governing (Collis & Hussey, 2014). The main objective of this study is to gain a sophisticated understanding of the problem of creating Islamic accounting standards, not to test hypotheses to determine causal links among variables. Saunders et al. (2012) say that therefore the positivist paradigm doesn't work in this case because it tries to make things easier to understand.

In the social sciences, the positivist paradigm, which stems from the natural sciences, is evaluated since it is not regarded as an approach that would result in "motivating and insightful assessments of complicated situations". In this regard, Saunders et al. (2009) argue that rich impressions of a complex world disappear when such complexity is totally reduced to a series of law-like generalisations. This study aims to provide a comprehensive and accurate overview of Islamic accounting standardisation programmes. Therefore, in the positivist research paradigm, a reductionist approach is utilised, focusing on concluding causal associations between variables through statistical analysis, which is insufficient for addressing the complexity of the institutional expectations and contextual circumstances associated with those plans. By disregarding potential stimulating impressions, the highly structured technique

associated with the positivist paradigm could limit and restrict the capacity of research to provide a comprehensive grasp of the topic of concentration (Collis & Hussey, 2014). The researcher thought it was important to be a "subjective insider" instead of an "objective outsider," as the positivist method suggests (Hallebone & Priest, 2009).

Given the deficiencies of the positivist paradigm in conveying the nature of the analysis, it can be argued that only a comprehensive research paradigm, such as the interpretative paradigm and the one under investigation, can provide the required scope of knowledge about the phenomena. Interpretivism asserts that the social world is extremely complex. Therefore, it is not possible to know this universe solely by defining causal relationships between variables and empirically evaluating these relationships. Likewise, the interpretive paradigm presumes that, in its nature, social phenomena are distinctive and are approved by several backgrounds, circumstances, situations, and behaviours of social actors; consequently, the inclusive approach to research should be complete enough to allow "much more complex circumstances to be examined."

The interpretive paradigm assumes that reality is socially produced and finds that social spectacles have specific meanings because of how social actors interact with each other. Regulations, transactions, events, and situations have no inherent meaning; meaning is conferred on them by human agents.

Thus, the reality is assumed to be subjective, and the right understanding of social phenomena is generated only through reading and comprehending the meanings that social actors attach to these occurrences (Mohajan, 2020). This implies that understanding social actors' intentions, thoughts, and inner perceptions are required to comprehend social reality. It is mentioned here that the purpose of interpretive research is to identify and characterise the world from the perspective of social actors who are interested in social phenomena.

The objective of this research is to comprehend the aspects of diverse institutional logic based on the experiences, views, and knowledge of those participants in these initiatives who have been involved either directly or indirectly. These players distinguish the rationale for guaranteeing that particular organisational policies are inconsistent (Thornton, et al., 2012). This shows that certainty is a matter of opinion since different players can imitate different ideas of reason.

In the critical paradigm assumption, this paradigm usually poses the challenge of identifying a particular phenomenon and then developing theories that can address real-world challenges such as structural discrimination, labour exploitation, unevenly distributed power and

economic benefits, industrial class dominance, etc. By doing so, critical scholars hope to influence the cognition and awareness of the social actors involved in the social process of emancipation and the "pursuit of alternative life practices."

4.2 Research Approach

As indicated previously, the approach to be adopted is derived from the research philosophy. When conducting research, methodologies are established under four approaches: inductive, deductive, retrodictive, and abductive (Blaikie, 2010).

4.2.1 Deductive Approach:

The deductive approach begins by acknowledging a determined or existing general theory appropriate to the investigation; this testable hypothesis is then formed and applied to the study through the formulation of a research strategy (Velde, et al., 2004).

The primary purpose of the inductive method is to develop a hypothesis based on observation of specific situations and to simplify the phenomenon under consideration (Wilson, 2014). The process of constructing a theory entails the utilisation of outcomes derived from observation of the research being conducted, data analysis and interpretation, and the formulation of a theory.

4.2.2 Inductive Approach

Inductive phenomena are discovered, whereas deductive theories are tested. An inductive method doesn't just use interviews to get qualitative data; it also uses closed-ended questions to get quantitative data.

4.2.3 Abductive and reproductive

Abductive and reproductive reasoning are the other two techniques. A data advancement strategy is a retrodictive strategy that involves constructing models and establishing structures with an innate mechanism so that the productivity of the data can lead to observable consequences (Blaikie, 2004).

The abductive approach is the source of data improvement in social science research; whereby inductive and deductive approaches are combined. Two of these methods are making an instructive hypothesis analysis and understanding the ideas from how social actors interpret and explain them (Blaikie, 2004 and Ibrahim, 2014).

The research approach (deductive) is adopted with the research paradigm. In opinion of the existing relationships among the selected variables. To describe differences and predict social spectacles based on theories triangulation or specific theory, the deductive approach is

considered the best. (Creswell, 2014 and Ibrahim, 2014). the researcher is likely to practise quantifiable data in a study concerning the testing of a hypothesis under the deductive approach. Deductive perceptive is the proper approach in research study of a social/natural sciences, (Blaikie, 2004; Easterby-Smith et al., 2004; Hair et al., 2007, and Velde, 2004). To achieve methodologically, fit the above approach is essential, as adopted by Edmondson and MacManus (2007).

In this study, based on the theoretical framework the formulation of the research questions, questionnaire, and relationships among the variables designated for analysis are carried out that supported the research.

Since this study will be based on both qualitative and quantitative data, the deductive method will be unnecessary. The methodologies are separated into several categories, however only two will be covered in this section: qualitative and quantitative.

4.2.4 Qualitative method

The study's primary purpose is explanatory since it sheds light on the participants' underlying perceptions of what drives them. Awareness of the issue, as well as the generation of a hypothesis and the exploration of related patterns and perspectives, are all aided by delving into the issue at hand. Interviews, surveys, and case studies are just some examples of the unstructured and semi-structured data collection methods that may be employed in this approach.

4.2.5 Quantitative method

The information collected can be utilised in statistical analysis to summarise the results of a large sample representative of a population and to better comprehend the relationships between the factors making up that population. When compared to the qualitative approach, the structure of this data makes it easier to represent in formulas and so discover trends. In most cases, the information gathered is secondary in nature, meaning that it was not originally gathered for that purpose. There are four different ways to measure data; the interval scale was used here because it best illustrates the connection between dependent and independent variables and facilitates hypothesis testing.

4.2.6 Multi-Methods (Mixed methods)

Developing a theory is one of the strengths of a qualitative study, which is why it will be the most suitable for this research, as it aims to do so in a little-explored field through complete research. Research benefits from this as well, as it aids in piecing together the respondent's actual life (Lincoln & Guba, 1990).

This study uses mixed methods as both qualitative and quantitative methods are used to answer the research questions.

4.3 Research design

The research design process is a technique that provides researchers with assistance in meeting the objectives of their study. It is predicated on a structure or a strategy that guides the researcher through the phases of the research procedure that involve the collection of data and the analysis of that data (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Additionally, it highlights that the aspect of time or the challenges associated with the time horizon are crucial components to consider when establishing an effective research design (Wilson, 2013). Furthermore, there are many kinds of studies, which give the researcher the ability to choose the research design that is most suitable for their particular study.

The next step is the research design, which includes a comprehensive framework or flowchart that outlines the study's structure. Plans that state explicitly how to respond to research questions or accomplish research objectives in a way that produces trustworthy results and strong conclusions from the study's final product, enabling generalisation, constitute a sound research design. The systematic process of systematically speculating details includes the study design and suggested logical and logistical steps needed to start the investigation. Consequently, the measurement events, the sampling strategy to be used, the environment for data collection and analysis, and the deadline for the conclusion.

Every research or study must have a research plan since it serves as the foundation for collecting and analysing data. It contains the strategy the researcher used throughout the research procedure. It provides answers to the most difficult questions, including how to analyse the results and what materials or tests should be used in a study (Brown, 1998). Study design supports efficiently gathering data to achieve the research purpose by offering a logical reason for decision-making regarding what data demands to be collected, collecting method, and analysis technique to be used, study design supports in efficiently gathering data to reach

the research purpose.

According to Wilson (2014), the identification and improvement of logistical (which includes logical) preparations that can be sufficient to conduct the studies are the primary roles played by research design. Another major role is emphasising that quality should be dominant when carrying out research. This is done with the help of strategies and methods that are legal, reliable, targeted, and accurate. Research design incorporates the methodological paradigm, studies method, facts series techniques and analysis. the research will be conducted by the following research design,

4.4 Data Collection

There are two methods for gathering information: primary and secondary. For primary data collection, things like observation, interviews, and questionnaires are used. For secondary data collection, things like research articles and books were used.

4.4.1 Observations: This is mostly used for qualitative data (but may also contain quantitative data). This is a type of data collection technique in which the researcher is active/present and goal-oriented, utilising a systematic approach determined through observation, recording objects/events, or paying close attention to actions occurring or listening closely to verbal utterances in the environment.

4.4.2 Interview: This is a type of data collection in which the researcher meets directly with respondents, either in person, over the phone, via internet media, or even by mail, and asks them to complete a survey with pre-determined questions or allows them to ask follow-up questions in open-ended ways (Kumar, 2014).

Semi-structured Interviews: The semi-structured interviews will aid in understanding how the three institutional logics (religion, welfare, and commerce) are formed, understood, and what the major matters of these logics and their opinions of contention with one another are, such as whether Akhuwat prioritises Muslim borrowers over Christian or Hindu borrowers. If yes, does it not contradict the idea of equality, and if no, does it violate Islamic principles? Interviews with Akhuwat officers will be especially helpful in figuring out if Akhuwat needs to change its organisational identity in the future to deal with the stresses of competing institutional logics.

4.4.3. **Secondary data:** This refers to data that has already been used or acquired for a further purpose; in this situation, when conducting a research investigation, the researcher recognises previously gathered information as data needed for the current research. Secondary (previous data) and primary (survey) data were employed in this investigation. Because the data acquired were numbers used to measure behaviour, the employment of the last two data collection methods (primary questionnaire and secondary numerical history data) classifies this study as a quantitative investigation.

Questionnaire

This is the major questionnaire-based data collection method. This is accomplished through tools such as formal interviews, mail surveys, online questionnaires are filled out on the Internet/Intranet), telephones, and group-administered questionnaires (Oppenheim, 2000).

4.5 Data Analysis Technique:

In this study, numerous analyses were conducted to understand the quality of the data (both primary and secondary) examined. These studies include:

4.5.1 Descriptive Statistics:

This is the systematic arrangement of statistical characteristics or data types used in a study, such as describing the characteristics (e.g. mean, median, mode, minimum, maximum, kurtosis, skewness, etc.) of a spectacle to provide more details of a particular set of data of interest (Hair et al., 2007; Kumar, 2014).

Kumar (2014) believes that descriptive statistics are not about describing variances or investigating relationships between variables, such as dependent and independent variables. In this study, descriptive statistics, including mean, mode, median, and minimum and maximum values, were calculated using both primary and secondary data. analysis. These approaches should only be used for observations and interviews.

4.5.2 Ethical Considerations

The ethical dimension is yet another consideration in research design. Generally, it is understood that a researcher has an ethical obligation to perform research honestly and accurately. In this investigation, ethical issues were examined. This research adheres to the Research Ethics Guidelines established by UWS (2009), which emphasises the need to morally

evaluate all research involving human applicants and is directed by four ethical principles: absence of harm (doing no harm); charity (doing good); autonomy (respect for the right to self-determination); and justice (fair treatment of people). Prior to sending the questionnaires to the study participants, their written and verbal consent (and, where applicable, that of their employer or organisation) was obtained. See the University of the West of Scotland's detailed evaluation process in the Ethics Committee Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship.

4.6 Research tradition:

Depending on the nature of the study and the researcher's objectives, one of five distinct research methodologies can be employed. The five types of studies are as follows:

4.6.1 Biographical Study

A type of research in which the subject is a single individual whose life story is either directly expressed to the researcher or documented in publicly available archives. A biography is a record of a person's life, both the happy and the sad times. A biography tells the account of a person's life without favour or bias, no matter what form that life takes.

4.6.2 Phenomenological Study

A phenomenological study is a type of research that differs from the biographical technique, which examines the life of an individual and focuses on the individual's experiences, because it illustrates the meanings of phenomena or concepts based on the lived experiences of multiple people. The astute phenomenologist uncovered the patterns of awareness in human experiences as a means of presentation to the objects she initiates on the journey to create logic of the abilities. Phenomenological research is relevant to a wide range of research fields, including sociology, philosophy, psychology, and health in the human sciences, amongst others. Phenomenological research presents the researcher with a number of problems, some of which may be difficult to overcome.

4.6.3 Grounded Theory

Even while the goal of a phenomenological investigation is to give meaning to the experiences of several people, the objective of a grounded theory study is to either find or build a theory. The development of a grounded theory follows the progression of individual interaction, reaction, and involvement in a process in response to phenomena. Data is collected in the form of interviews by the researcher who goes into the fields, develops, and gathers corresponding data before writing hypotheses or theoretical propositions in order to study such individuals and their reaction to the phenomenon. In order to do this, the researcher conducts interviews.

According to sociologists Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss, the purpose behind grounded theory as it is articulated is that theories must be grounded from the field in data form generally in the interaction, actions, and social affairs of individual people. This is the purpose behind grounded theory as it is articulated.

4.6.4 Ethnography

Ethnography is a term that refers to the process of providing an interpretation and description of a social or cultural group. The researchers examine the subjects' or group's patterns of behaviour, as well as their traditions and ways of living, during this phase of the research. In ethnography, a subject or group is observed for an extended period of time while the researchers are completely involved in the study as participants. This type of observation is known as participant observation. The researcher will involve the group and take part in the day-to-day activities of its members by observing the participants and conducting interviews with individuals who are included in the group. The ethnographer is able to observe the meanings of language, behaviour, and cultural elements of the group with the assistance of the interviews and other data obtained. The ethnographer is the one who directs their research in the field and is actively involved in fieldwork in order to lend credibility to their study. They are successful in gaining the confidence of the members of the group who are willing to be honest with the researcher and provide sensitive information that the researcher would not have obtained without their confidence.

4.6.5 Case Study

A case study entails a comprehensive and thorough examination of a person, unit, or community. This focuses on developmental problems and interactions with the environment, as well as documenting real-life experiences and other occurrences through data collection, including cortex-rich data in many forms. Case studies include data from observation, interviews, audiovisual material, and documentation.

The study attempts to create a theory by delving deeply into the case of an Islamic microfinance organisation (Akhuwat). A case study will be the most appropriate research strategy to fulfil the objectives because it is the most common means to perform lengthy research on a given instance (Stake, 1995) (Creswell & Poth, 1998).

Case study approach

This study employs the case-study methodology as part of its design. Yin (1984) defines a case study as "an empirical analysis that investigates a current event inside its real-life setting while

the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly visible and several revaluations of evidence are employed." The assumption that accounting represents a traditional collection of measurement procedures that function independently of their environment has been widely contested in recent decades. Accounting is viewed as a "complex web of economic, political, and unintentional co-occurrences that neither reproduce technical logic nor significant progress". This perspective prompted this case study to employ a holistic research approach. According to Berry and Otley (2004), the power of the case-study method in accounting studies lies in the comprehensive and detailed understanding of accounting methods in their structural and social context. Regarding the objective of this case study, which is to comprehend the tasks connected with developing Islamic economic reporting requirements in their structural and institutional context, the case-study methodology is judged suitable for this research. In the sections that follow, you'll find more information about why the case-study method is used and why certain cases are chosen.

Case Study Approach Rationality

In addition to the prior argument, this study employs a case-study strategy for the succeeding rationalities. First, the case-study technique is suited to the nature of the research questions addressed in the study. This is because, according to Yin (Yin, 2014), the case study approach is best suited for conducting complex, contextualised research when a researcher is seeking answers to "how" and "why" research issues. Second, according to Yin (1984), the case-study technique provides the advantage of studying phenomena in their natural context. This improves the researcher's ability to identify and interpret contextual and environmental aspects that influence the events of interest. As a result, the situation's complexity can be addressed. Akhuwat operates in a long-term environment of institutional complexity, which is why it is primarily stimulating for the purposes of this research. As a non-profit organisation, Akhuwat was heavily influenced by religious institutional logic until 2013. In 2013, Akhuwat signed an agreement with Meezan bank. Meezan is Pakistan's largest commercial Islamic bank and would provide financial consultancy services in the form of Musharakah (participation-based model), Shariah consultancy services, which will ensure that Akhuwat's financial products are Shariah (Islamic law) compliant through Meezan Bank's Shariah Board. Based on the information above and a conversation with Akhuwat's CFO, Akhuwat is now inclined towards another institutional logic, commerce, because they now have the potential to generate profit through Musharakah contracts while strengthening their religious logic through the oversight powers of the Shariah boards (Meezan Bank, 2013).

4.7 Summary

This section of the thesis provides further detail on the research methodologies used in the study. It stresses how important intellectual traditions are for driving business research in the social sciences. The chapter begins by claiming that business research should not be conducted in isolation; instead, it must be grounded in established philosophical principles and intellectual frameworks that shape the design and implementation of research. The chapter offers a detailed framework for demonstrating the interwoven components of the research process, encompassing research philosophy, approach, strategy, design, data collection, and analysis, through the presentation of Wilson's honeycomb model. This technique differs from linear models by highlighting the interconnections among diverse components, so illustrating the complex interactions that characterise the research process.

This chapter examines the significance of research philosophy, concentrating on the ontological and epistemological dimensions that influence the quality and originality of research. It underscores the need of formulating a unique research philosophy, as this impacts study design, data requirements, and analytical methodologies. The discussion of epistemology makes three main points clear: This chapter ultimately identifies pragmatism as the fundamental epistemological framework supporting the mixed-methods methodology employed in this study. This result emphasises the imperative of amalgamating qualitative insights with quantitative rigour to comprehensively address the study's enquiries.

The methodology section distinguishes between deductive and inductive approaches, elucidating that the research will primarily utilise a mixed-methods approach. This integration enhances the understanding of the issue by employing both qualitative and quantitative data sources. Different ways for collecting data are categorised into two groups: primary and secondary sources. There are several ways to collect primary data, such as: Semi-structured interviews will be conducted to obtain a more profound understanding of participants' experiences and perceptions regarding Islamic microfinance institutions. Surveys: Questionnaires will be sent to gather quantitative data on various aspects of the research topic. Secondary data sources will be crucial, including the analysis of contemporary literature and previous research initiatives that provide substantial background and supporting evidence. A number of several were to analyse the data collected, with descriptive statistics being one of the most important. The focus will be on systematically defining statistical characteristics to enhance understanding of the study's findings.

The ethical implications are analysed, affirming the researcher's commitment to preserving the integrity of the study process. The need of following ethical standards is stressed, especially the need to get informed consent from participants and keep research methods fair. The chapter concludes by examining diverse research traditions, encompassing biographical, phenomenological, grounded theory, ethnographic, and case study methodologies. The case study methodology is considered especially suitable for this research, enabling an in-depth analysis of Islamic microfinance organisation and its's operational context. In summary, this chapter outlines a whole methodological framework that guides the study, ensuring that it is scientifically sound and trustworthy. The chapter develops a comprehensive methodology for understanding the intricate dynamics of Islamic microfinance, establishing a foundation for the subsequent analysis and findings of the study.

Chapter 5 Thematic Analysis Themes

Introduction

In the realm of poverty alleviation, numerous lessons can be discerned; primarily, the implementation of Shariah principles at IMFI has demonstrated efficacy in promoting financial inclusion. Secondly, all stakeholders, particularly Islamic banks and the government, must endorse IMFI's role in poverty alleviation. Thirdly, stock-based financing agreements, such as Musharakah and Mudharabah contracts, at IMFI significantly empower the impoverished. The consolidation of zakah, infaq, shadaqah, and qardhulhasan management at IMFI can serve as a mechanism for community empowerment.

Within the realm of poverty reduction, numerous concerns and challenges await academics in the future. Initially, investigate the determinants influencing IMFI production from both financial and social perspectives. Secondly, conduct an empirical study on how IMFI's profit-sharing financing affects poverty on a macroeconomic level.

Microfinance represented a significant advancement in combating poverty; nonetheless, due to several deficiencies, it is argued that it failed to achieve the anticipated outcomes. Numerous factors contribute to this, including elevated interest rates, diversion of funds, and insufficient personal growth. IM emerges as a novel concept within the realm of microfinance, demonstrating a comparatively superior capacity to combat poverty, particularly in predominantly Muslim regions. Furthermore, through its products and ethical development programme, the concept can mitigate poverty levels and foster sustainable long-term growth.

The interviewees from Meezan are denoted as “M” and interviewees from Akhuwat are denoted as “A” during the analysis.

The following themes are generated using semi-structured interviews and generating nodes and codebook using NVivo.

1. Institutional Logic (IL)
 - a. Religion, an element of IL
 - b. Role of IL towards building organisational identity
2. Multiple Institutional Logics
 - a. Types of Institutional Logics
 - b. Institutional Complexity
3. Organisational Performance
 - a. Islamic Microfinance

- b. Poverty alleviation
- c. Societal Welfare

Research Objective 1- To explore religion as an institutional logic and its role in shaping the organisational identity of an Islamic microfinance organisation.

5.1.1 Institutional Logic

This theme will provide insight into the term institutional logic and how the respondents have considered this term in managing the operational activities of an Islamic microfinance organization (Akhuwat). Further, it includes three sub-themes which shed light upon the elements of the first research question (*What is the role of religion as an institutional logic in determining the organisational identity of an Islamic microfinance organisation*).

Akhuwat Employees (A)

Institutional logics have significant importance for Akhuwat; however, in most interviews, when asked about institutional logic at the beginning of the interview, most interviewees had limited knowledge of the terms or were unsure of their meaning. The following statements indicate the unfamiliarity of the term to the staff.

“I don’t have an idea of the literal meaning of institutional logic, I think they are values” (A9)

“They are values or core beliefs of an organization if I am not mistaken” (A8)

“I suppose they are the core values or principles of the organisation” (A7)

“It is a new term for me; I think they are values of an organization” (A6)

“I understand that it could be our values, principles, or philosophy of the organisation” (A5)

“For me, I thought that it was a model such as the Grameen model etc. on which microfinance institutions are working upon. Reading these questions again I think it can be the core values of the organization” (A3)

“They maybe are the values of an organization; I don’t have a very elaborate idea” (A2)

” I don’t have much knowledge about them, but reading the questions makes me feel they are some core values of the organization” (A10)

The interviewees were provided with the participation information sheet which gave a brief understanding of the terms, but it was very new to them and after this question, they were explained in detail regarding institutional logic which helped in getting better information out of them in the later questions and due to that it was found that Akhuwat was facing even more institutional logics than were thought of.

Meezan Employees (M)

The role of institutional logic on the basis of religion in Akhuwat is explained by (M3)

“It is challenging for Akhuwat due to the behaviour of the public. When a company is providing Shariah compliance product, the public has a perception about, and they judge, and they would want for a Shariah compliance company to act and dress in a certain way otherwise the public will not trust the services” (M3)

Further, it is seen that to be Shariah Compliant, Akhuwat needs to follow the religious guidelines which are supervised by an institute i.e., Meezan Bank.

“So Akhuwat, to remain Shariah compliant, came to Meezan for a product in which they could charge their client operating costs. Operating costs cannot be blamed on loans; otherwise, it would be interesting, so Meezan made them a product called Ijarat ul Musha” (M2)

With the consideration of multiple logic, the Vice President of Meezan Bank mentioned that due to multiple logic Akhuwat will be able to enhance its performance by selling more products i.e., different Shariah-compliant financing products.

“Their traditional logic is not damaged or finished but this new logic is an add-on. Before you used to do 1 thing now you are doing 2, your shop used to sell 1 item but now you have added another line. It is taking them time now to understand, they are trying to understand as they never tried to be Shariah compliant like this before.” (M4)

With the help of interviews conducted with Meezan Bank employees, it provided a clear picture that they have clear knowledge about institutional logics and its types which helps Akhuwat to manage their business and gain fruitful results.

a) Religion

Values, beliefs, religion, and professions are examples of institutional logic which guide the choice of an individual and guide them toward providing meaning to their daily activities (Akmal, Foote, Podgorodnichenko, Greatbanks, and Gauld, 2020). With the help of religion as an element of institutional logic, the qualitative data will help to shed light on the factor of religion in shaping the organizational identity of the organisation.

Akhuwat Employees (A)

Religion is the core of the ideology of Akhuwat, it is their driving force, and it guides Akhuwat in all aspects as an organization.

“It has a significant role, as our model relies on religion. We take everything from the religious beliefs, be it work culture, dealing with staff, or dealing with clients. We try our best to follow

the guidelines of the religion, respect each other, respect other people's religion and be fair in what we do" (A9)

The senior management and the middle management were very passionate regarding religion being very important for them, and their statements depicted it quite clearly.

"Religion is the base on which the identity of the organisation has been shaped, all the guidelines are taken from religion for all aspects of the organization" (A10)

"We narrate our core beliefs from the religion" (A7)

It shows that it is not only important for them personally but also professionally which improves their organisational culture and also their relationship with their clients.

"It plays a significant role as our operational model is based on it, and we are trained extensively in it, so it becomes a part of professional behaviours" (A6)

"It promotes brotherhood, religious (Islamic) concept of equality. (A4)

"The philosophy or identity of Akhuwat is based wholly on religion as we follow the guidelines on social welfare from religion like how it was done back in the days of the Holy Prophet (PBUH)" (A5)

(A2) "The base of the ideology of Akhuwat is religion as we take the prime example of the Brotherhood that was created in Madinah by the Holy Prophet (PBUH). We cater for all religions when working for social welfare. We do loan disbursements for Christians in churches, for Hindus in their Temples and for Muslims in mosques. This creates peer pressure and as people relate to their religion, the return rate of the loan is excellent which is around 99%"

The brotherhood they define from religion, helps them to be helpful to different religions as well.

(A3) "Religion is the core of the ideology of the organisation and the reason why the organization was started so it plays a vital role in shaping its organisational identity"

(A1) "It has an inexplicably important role as the base of the identity of the organisation is religion from day one and without it, the identity will have no face value".

Meezan Bank (M)

Religion provides the basis of institutional logic in Akhuwat because the main requirement of their business model is to provide Shariah-compliant products to their consumers. Meezan bank helped them to manage it effectively by reviewing their products and checking the clauses in their agreements to make sure that they are Shariah compliant.

“The assistance from Meezan helps Akhuwat prepare the agreements; Akhuwat remains Shariah compliant. Any clause which is not Shariah compliant gets removed by Meezan. This helps Akhuwat keep the Islamic microfinance organisation's mandate and introduce themselves as an Islamic microfinance organisation” (M3).

To maintain the aspect of religion through Shariah-compliant models, Meezan bank provides technical, legal, and advisory support to introduce Shariah-compliant products, which are compulsory for them to sustain their business.

“Akhuwat is an Islamic Microfinance Organisation collaborating with Usmani Co & Sons for the products. We are the technical team behind the product make, approved by the Shariah advisory board that is Usmani & Co. We overlook the product making a new product, its Shariah” (M1).

b) Role of Institutional logic towards building organisational identity

This sub-theme shed light on the interviewees' responses regarding the building of Akhuwat's organisational identity.

Akhuwat Employees (A)

Institutional logic plays a big role in the organisational identity of Akhuwat. It has improved their recognition among people and as there were not many organisations that provided interest free loan and were so successful in their return while helping the community

“The people's awareness of the people has increased regarding Akhuwat, and we can reach more people now due to adding more institutional logic to the organisation” (A9) .

Akhuwat success due to their institutional logic has made other organisations join them and work for the community which they were not able to do before. Their success not only has increased awareness among their clients, but also amongst their peers and many Islamic banks.

“Akhuwat is now a more recognised organisation than ever, so it has been perfect for its identity. Due to that, Akhuwat has collaborated with other organisations, banks and even the government to reach a new category of clients they did not get before” (A8).

“It has increased the awareness of Akhuwat amongst people” (A7).

“It increased the awareness of Akhuwat among the local community, and more people are trying to reach us to get interest-free loans” (A6).

“Akhuwat is more recognised than ever, and due to that, we can use new products to reach more people and change their life for good” (A5).

“The identity of the organisation has received more recognition as we can reach more people and provide more products than we were able to do before” (A2).

“Akhuwat is now a renowned organisation and is recognised all over the due to its contribution to helping the community, especially the poor” (A3).

“It was perfect for our identity and gave us more motivation due to the recognition and praise we received from everyone” (A10).

Meezan Bank (M)

The institutional logic related to religion; Shariah compliance made Akhuwat modify their organisational identity because Akhuwat initiated providing interest-free loans. Due to their successful business model, the government also provided them with loans to build or renovate houses. Meezan bank proposed Akhuwat Ijarat ul Musha a product specifying that operating costs will not come under interest and could be charged to the customers.

“Akhuwat used to give interest-free loans, but recently they signed an MOU with the government where the government gave interest-free loans to Akhuwat to build houses or renovate houses of the people in the government's housing scheme. Akhuwat normally charges its operating cost to the donor. Still, the government told Akhuwat that they would only provide them with interest loans, so Akhuwat, to remain Shariah compliant, came to Meezan for a product in which they could charge their client operating costs. Operating costs cannot be blamed on loans; otherwise, it would be interesting, so Meezan made them a product called Ijarat ul Musha, where Akhuwat generates revenue by giving compensatory products to their clients and charges them operating costs to become self-sustainable.” (M1)

“It is a new way for them, they only used to do interest-free loans, but now they are entering the commercial market as well, which is an uphill task” (M3)

The VP of Meezan Bank also confirms that due to the institutional logic of commerce, the organisational identity of Akhuwat is improved and changed because it has boosted its performance and growth of Akhuwat.

“Akhuwat used to do one thing. Now they are doing 2 or 3 things, and as they have started doing low-cost housing and youth entrepreneurship, the government has also backed them. This has given a boost in their growth; they have also got more opportunities which will help them grow more in the future” (M4).

Questions 2 & 3- to explore the response of an Islamic microfinance organisation towards multiple institutional logics while experiencing institutional complexity and to investigate

the performance of Islamic microfinance organisations, their effects on poverty alleviation and the welfare of their clients.

5.1.2 Multiple Institutional Logics

a) Types of Institutional Logics

Under this sub-theme, different institutional logics considered by the management of Akhuwat and Meezan bank will be discussed.

Meezan Bank (M)

The interviews with Meezan employees reveal that Akhuwat is adopting different types of logic, including religious and professional logic. Before Meezan developed a professional portfolio related to Shariah-compliant products, Akhuwat initially provided only interest-free loans. Consequently, the combination of both logics enables Akhuwat to utilise multiple approaches.

“Akhuwat have found a new path; they are talking to different banks and organisations. They were reluctant in Shariah compliance, and it took them years to embrace it, we have been in talks with them since 2013 to take a step further, but it took time to materialise and a change in mindset. Akhuwat were proud of the work they were providing interest-free loans, but there is a change of mindset as I can see them have engagements with different organisations. They are signing MOU with a different organisation”. (M4)

With the help of multiple logic, Akhuwat can provide different products to its customers that would benefit them in the future.

“Further, we tell them what they can explore and how different dimensions could be beneficial for them” (M3)

Akhuwat Employees (A)

“We are currently generating revenue to cover the admin or operation costs and are not earning any profits. It has affected us positively as we are helping people in more than one way, which we could not do before

Positive impact, step towards sustainability. The new market touched; credibility increased. The government, army, and politicians have appraised Akhuwat” (A9).

“It has affected us positively, and now we can recover our operational costs by generating revenue and becoming sustainable”. (A8)

“I don’t think it has affected much, we were generating any revenue, but we are generating some now, which helps to cover our operational costs”. (A7)

“Akhuwat is working towards sustainability, but we are still a non-profit organisation”. (A6)

“Akhuwat has launched many products, such as housing and other products, with Meezan. The effect of this logic is that we are generating revenue to make Akhuwat sustainable and to cover the operating costs”. (A5)

“We are generating revenue from a housing product we are doing with Meezan, but the revenue only covers our operating costs. The new logic is helping us to become sustainable so that we can cover our operating costs ourselves rather than charging the donors”. (A2)

“We can generate revenue, but it is to cover our operating costs, but it is helping us to go towards sustainability, which is a big and positive step for us”. (A3)

“It has helped in adding new logic, which is sustainability, as we are generating revenue, which is helping in covering our operational costs”. (Mr A1)

b) Institutional Complexity

Different logics give rise to institutional complexity; this sub-theme will shed light on institutional complexity faced by Akhuwat employees.

Akhuwat Employees (A)

“It has affected us surprisingly in a positive way as it got very challenging, but it got the best out of us, and we were able to use more than institutional logic successfully”, (A10).

“It has helped in making it more effective; the more challenging it got, the more we got out of it and created better systems, so we successfully use the logic simultaneously through different departments”, (A2).

“It has improved the effectiveness as we add new logic and are still successful. It is the controls, checks and the system we have kept in place due to which we are successful even after using two or more institutional logic” (A3).

“It did not have any negative impact, but as a matter of fact, it has improved as we are adding new logic because the system and process kept in place are very robust”, (A5).

“The institution logics we are facing, we keep on top of the by using the guidelines from the religion and making proper processes so that the logics do not clash with each other”, (A6).

“I have not seen any negative impact”, (Mr A7).

“Positively, as we grow stronger and due to the new logic, we are moving towards sustainability and able to help more people”, (A8).

“There has been no negative impact due to proper systems kept in place by the top management. Each department has its work, and they are on top of it, which is why there are no grey areas left,” (A9).

5.1.3 Organisational Performance

a) Islamic Microfinance

This sub-theme provides responses related to the performance of Akhuwat as an Islamic microfinance organisation.

Meezan Bank (M)

It is seen that Akhuwat was started as an interest-free microfinance firm which is now grown as they have included Meezan bank and trying to include other financial institutions to increase their Shariah-compliant product range.

“Akhuwat have found a new path; they are talking to different banks and organisations. They were reluctant in Shariah compliance, and it took them years to embrace it, we have been in talks with them since 2013 to take a step further, but it took time to materialise and a change in mindset. Akhuwat were proud of the work that they were providing interest-free loans, but there is a change of mindset as I can see them have engagements with different organisations and they are signing MOU with a different organisation” (M4)

It illustrates that multiple logics helped Akhuwat to grow their business portfolio which ultimately increased the growth and performance of the organisation.

Akhuwat Employees (A)

“It was brilliant; we followed the religion strictly and respected other religious beliefs. Our staff are from different religions, but we respect them while being from different faiths. We appreciate all our employees, regardless of their position; everyone is respected equally. This has also helped us to maintain assertive, ethical behaviour throughout the organisation” (A9)

“It has affected us positively as we see everyone as equal and respect everyone. We also respect people of other religions and don’t differentiate between people when they are in need”. (A8)

“We are what we are as an organisation due to religion; otherwise, we are nothing” (A7).

“It plays a positive role; it helps to become not only a better human but also a better professional and grooms the organisation’s culture in a way that we can collectively work towards the growth and success of the organisation” (A6).

“It has majorly affected Akhuwat in a significant way. It has created equality in the organisation, and everyone is respected equally and given equal rights to raise a question or provide an opinion”. (A5)

“It affects us in a way that makes us respect our religion but also other religions. It helps us to create a positive environment within the organisation and a positive relationship with our clients” (A2)

“It affects positively in all aspects, whether it be operations or any other aspect of the organisation” (A3)

“It affects the culture in every way, it is strictly adhered to by all the employees, and it is one of the reasons the donors and the clients show trust and interest in us” (A10)

b) Poverty Alleviation

This sub-theme provides the managerial techniques used by the Akhuwat as an organisation to alleviate poverty by providing short-term loans.

Akhuwat Employees (A)

“It has been a remarkable journey, and I believe we have left our mark in helping the community, but we are far from alleviating poverty, and it would require a huge effort from every organisation in the country” (A1)

“Akhuwat has worked a lot over the years and contributed a lot towards the betterment of the community, but alleviating poverty is a huge task. Many organisations and even the government must step in to make a big impact on this problem. Otherwise, it is a mere impossible task for any organisation alone” (A2)

“It is a huge task, but we are doing our part, and we want to keep on doing what we do to create a change, but only one organisation cannot alleviate poverty” (A3)

“What we do, social welfare we have been successful for the small role we are playing in bringing the change we may lead to decreasing poverty and making a positive change in a normal person life” (A4)

“We have disbursed billions of rupees in loans, it had some impact on the community, and we are very hopeful we can contribute more towards alleviating poverty in the future” (A6)

“It is a big thing to alleviate poverty, we cannot claim anything, but we are trying to make a change and to change the lives of at least a few people” (A7)

“Akhuwat is doing its bit, but it will take hundreds or thousands of organisations to work together to achieve something like alleviating poverty. We are very hopeful with the contribution we are making toward the welfare of the community and will continue to do so in the future” (A8)

“Alleviation is a big word; we are trying our best to be a part of this movement of doing good for people of the lower class of society so that they can become self-sufficient and stand on their feet. Poverty alleviation is a colossal task, and no single organisation can do it” (A9)

c) Societal Welfare

Under this sub-theme, the researcher will review the policies discussed by the respondents in the interviews regarding uplifting the societal status of the customers of Akhuwat.

Akhuwat Employees (A)

“We are still doing social welfare, modes have changed, but our work is the same; we are not generating any profits. The revenue generated will cover our operating costs and will help us in becoming self-sustainable” (A9)

“There is a good balance as our departments are separate for socially responsible projects and generating revenue” (A8)

“I don’t think there was much difference; we are still doing the same work while generating revenue” (A7)

“Our work is the same; we are still working for the community and sticking with our ideology” (A6)

“We have been very diligent with our social welfare work, and we are generating revenue does not profit, and they are working side by side without affecting each other”. (A5)

“We are giving both products to customer side by side, and there is a good balance as we have different departments for them and have robust systems to back it up.” (A2)

“It has been very balanced as we developed excellent systems and departments for a different kind of work. Whatever we were doing before, we are still doing that along with the new products, and we are successfully doing both”. (A3)

“It is very well balanced, but to clarify, we are not generating profit but generating revenue which only helps to cover our operational cost”. (A1)

5.2 The rationale for selecting a case-study approach

Akhuwat was chosen as a case study as can be seen from the interviews that it was experiencing multiple logics and was still successful while experiencing institutional complexity. It added new institutional logic while using more than 2 institutional logics. It is a unique case where an organisation is facing multiple logics but is still successful, it can be seen from the interviews that it was down to their robust system in place and different departments for different institutional logics which helped them to successfully use them.

Chapter 6 Analysis

We estimate the survey data using linear regression analysis to assess the impact of the independent variables (IMF) on the dependent variables (Poverty Alleviation) in this study. This technique has been employed to provide precise analysis and discussion regarding the quantitative examination of the effects of Islamic microfinance on the poverty alleviation and the welfare of client in Pakistan (Akhuwat). This chapter analysis the influence of Islamic microfinance organisation on poverty alleviation using descriptive statistics.

6.1 Instrument's Reliability & Validity

When the random error is unaffected, another measure is said to be trustworthy (Forza & Filippini, 1998). Cronbach's Alpha is used to assess the internal consistency of a reliable source (Cronbach, 1951). According to Hair Jr. et al. (2007), alpha between 0.6 and 0.7 is acceptable, but this depends entirely on the study and its scope. After the factor analysis, the items that remained on the scales were subjected to Cronbach's alpha calculations. The fact that the sample size is 385 respondents may be the reason why the alpha values of all the scales—Poverty Alleviation and Client Welfare—is less than 0.6 or 0.7. Additionally, the scales' means, and standard deviations have been supplied in Table 5.1 as well.

Table 6.1: Reliability & Validity

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Number of Items</i>
<i>Islamic Microfinance</i>	0.621	36.19	4.46	05
<i>Poverty Alleviation and Welfare of the Client</i>	0.233	15.80	2.96	07

6.2 Result of Linear Regression Analysis

In the model summary table 0.0, the independent and dependent variables—Islamic Microfinance, Poverty Alleviation, and Client Welfare—are shown to be directly related by linear regression analysis. Although there is just one predictor, there is a straightforward association between Islamic microfinance, poverty alleviation, and client welfare. The value of the beta coefficient, which may be used to see how both variables affect the results, was (B=-.171), while the significance p-value, which is bigger than the alpha (0.05) value, is (p .001).

Table 6.2: Linear Regression Analysis

Hypotheses	Coefficients Beta	T	R-Square	P-Value
<i>Relation between Islamic Microfinance and Poverty Alleviation and Welfare of the Client</i>	0.171	3.49	.029	.001

The family of regression analysis includes ordinal regression. Ordinal regression describes data and explains the association between one dependent variable and two or more independent variables as a predictive study. Ordinal or continuous-level (ratio or interval) independent variables and ordinal or polytomous ordinal dependent variables make up an ordinal regression study. The term "dependent variable" can also refer to the outcome variable, prognostic variable, endogenous variable, or regressed. The exogenous variables, predictor variables, or regressors are other names for the independent variables.

To understand potential obstacles to and opposition to the goals of Islamic microfinance standardisation programmes, this research examines players whose institutional logics are at odds with those goals. In the social sciences, ordinal regression is frequently used, for instance in the modelling of human preference levels (on a scale from, say, **1 = Strongly Disagree**, **2 = Disagree**, **3 = Neutral**, **4 = Agree**, **5 = Strongly Agree**), as well as in information retrieval.

OUTPUT 1

Table displays a summary of case processing. For the variables used in the analysis, SPSS explicitly labels the variables and their values. To make sure you are analysing the variables you want to, it is crucial to do this. In this study we are modelling the popularity of Islamic microfinance along with other variables related to client welfare and poverty alleviation, such as interest-bearing borrowing, unemployment, decreasing poverty, small businesses and microentrepreneurs, application procedures, financial situations, and interest-free loans.

Case Processing Summary

		N	Marginal Percentage
Popularity	Strongly Disagree	12	3.1%
	Disagree	27	7.0%
	Neutral	82	21.3%
	Agree	147	38.2%
	Strongly Agree	117	30.4%
Interest Based Borrowing	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3%
	Disagree	9	2.3%
	Neutral	49	12.7%
	Agree	160	41.6%
	Strongly Agree	162	42.1%
Unemployment	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	15	3.9%
	Neutral	69	17.9%
	Agree	167	43.4%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%
Decreasing Poverty	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	69	17.9%
	Agree	154	40.0%
	Strongly Agree	132	34.3%
Small Business and Microentrepreneurs	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	72	18.7%
	Agree	159	41.3%
	Strongly Agree	121	31.4%
Application Process	Strongly Disagree	30	7.8%
	Disagree	41	10.6%
	Neutral	111	28.8%
	Agree	128	33.2%

	Strongly Agree	75	19.5%
Financial Circumstances	Strongly Disagree	6	1.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	68	17.7%
	Agree	162	42.1%
	Strongly Agree	123	31.9%
Interest Free Loan	Strongly Disagree	10	2.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	62	16.1%
	Agree	157	40.8%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%

Table 6.3: Case Processing Summary Output 1

Whether the model enhances our capacity for outcome prediction must be established before we begin examining the effects of each explanatory variable in the model. In this model by comparing a model without any explanatory variables against the explanatory variables in this model can be compared to those in models with all the explanatory variables to see which is better. At the moment, this model only includes the explanatory variables Interest Based Borrowing, Unemployment, Decreasing Poverty, Small Business and Micro Entrepreneurs, Application Process, Financial Circumstances, and Interest Free Loan. We assess if the final model has considerably improved the fit to the data by comparing it to the baseline. The final model's and the baseline's -2 log-likelihood (-2LL) values are provided in the Model fitting Information table, and SPSS runs a chi-square test to determine whether the two models' -2LL values vary.

Model Fit				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Intercept Only	1029.434			
Final	978.392	51.043	28	.005

Table 6.4: Model Fitting Information Output 1

The final model significantly outperforms the baseline intercept model, according to the significant chi-square value (p .005). Value and importance value are identical. However, in this instance, the research shows that the model provides a better forecast than if you were to

simply guess at the marginal probability for the outcomes of the given variable categories, such as Islamic Microfinance, poverty alleviation, and customer welfare.

The following Goodness of Fit table the model's chi-square statistic is included in Pearson's (as well as another chi-square statistic based on the deviance). These statistics are used to determine whether the fitted model and observed data are consistent. The fit is good in this model, according to the null hypothesis. The data and the model predictions are similar, and you may conclude that you have a good model if we do not reject this hypothesis (i.e. if the p value is high). The model does not, however, fit the data well if you reject the assumption of a good fit, which is typically the case if (p.003). The findings of this study's research indicate that the model does not fit the data very well since it is less the value of if $p < .005$).

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	1586.775	1432	.003
Deviance	966.830	1432	1.000

Table 6.5: Goodness of Fit Test Output1

Greater R² values indicate that more of the variation in the outcome can be explained up to a maximum of 1, while R-square (the coefficient of determination) quantifies the proportion of variance in the outcome that can be accounted for by the explanatory variables. The same R² statistic as in linear regression cannot be estimated for logistic and ordinal regression models, hence three approximations are generated in their place.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.124
Nagelkerke	.133
McFadden	.049

Table 6.6: Pseudo R-Square Statistics Output1

Depending on the nature of the outcome and the explanatory variables, one can determine what a "good" R² number is. Pseudo-R² values in this case (e.g., Nagelkerke = 13.1%), show that IM accounts for just a small percentage of the variation among PW variables. This is exactly what we would expect given the wide range of factors that have an impact on Islamic Microfinance, many of which will serve as much more significant attainment predictors than

any simple correlation with Islamic Microfinance variable. A model that just includes popularity is likely to be a poor predictor of the result given the low R2 value.

OUTPUT 2

In this study we are modelling the Social Relations of Islamic microfinance along with other variables Social Relations related to client welfare and poverty alleviation, such as interest-bearing borrowing, unemployment, decreasing poverty, small businesses and micro-entrepreneurs, application procedures, financial situations, and interest-free loans.

Case Processing Summary

		N	Marginal Percentage
Social Relation	Strongly Disagree	12	3.1%
	Disagree	33	8.6%
	Neutral	64	16.6%
	Agree	154	40.0%
	Strongly Agree	122	31.7%
Interest Based Borrowing	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3%
	Disagree	9	2.3%
	Neutral	49	12.7%
	Agree	160	41.6%
	Strongly Agree	162	42.1%
Unemployment	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	15	3.9%
	Neutral	69	17.9%
	Agree	167	43.4%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%
Decreasing Poverty	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	69	17.9%
	Agree	154	40.0%
	Strongly Agree	132	34.3%

Small Business and Microentrepreneurs	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	72	18.7%
	Agree	159	41.3%
	Strongly Agree	121	31.4%
Application Process	Strongly Disagree	30	7.8%
	Disagree	41	10.6%
	Neutral	111	28.8%
	Agree	128	33.2%
	Strongly Agree	75	19.5%
Financial Circumstances	Strongly Disagree	6	1.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	68	17.7%
	Agree	162	42.1%
	Strongly Agree	123	31.9%
Interest Free Loan	Strongly Disagree	10	2.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	62	16.1%
	Agree	157	40.8%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%

Table 6.7: Case Processing Summary Output 2

Whether the model enhances our capacity for outcome prediction must be established before we begin examining the effects of each explanatory variable in the model. In this model by comparing a model without any explanatory variables against the explanatory variables in this model can be compared to those in models with all the explanatory variables to see which is better. At the moment, this model only includes the explanatory variables Interest Based Borrowing, Unemployment, Decreasing Poverty, Small Business and Micro Entrepreneurs, Application Process, Financial Circumstances, and Interest Free Loan. We assess if the final model has considerably improved the fit to the data by comparing it to the baseline. The final model's and the baseline's -2 log-likelihood (-2LL) values are provided in the Model fitting Information table, and SPSS runs a chi-square test to determine whether the two models' -2LL values vary.

Model Fit

Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	1020.244			
Final	988.761	31.483	28	.296

Table 6.8: Model Fitting Information Output 2

The final model significantly outperforms the baseline intercept model, according to the significant chi-square value ($p < .005$). Value and importance value are identical. However, in this instance, the research shows that the model provides a better forecast than if you were to simply guess at the marginal probability for the outcomes of the given variable categories, such as Islamic Microfinance, poverty alleviation, and customer welfare.

The following Goodness of Fit table the model's chi-square statistic is included in Pearson's (as well as another chi-square statistic based on the deviance). These statistics are used to determine whether the fitted model and observed data are consistent. The fit is good in this model, according to the null hypothesis. The data and the model predictions are similar, and you may conclude that you have a good model if we do not reject this hypothesis (i.e. if the p value is high). The model does not, however, fit the data well if you reject the assumption of a good fit, which is typically the case if ($p < .296$). The findings of this study's research indicate that the model is a good fit the data very well since it is greater the value of if $p < .005$).

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Pearson	1448.478	1432	.375
Deviance	971.890	1432	1.000

Table 6.9 Goodness of fit Information Output 2

Depending on the nature of the outcome and the explanatory variables, one can determine what a "good" R^2 number is. Pseudo- R^2 values in this case (e.g., Nagelkerke = 84%), show that IM accounts for just a small percentage of the variation among PW variables. This is exactly what we would expect given the wide range of factors that have an impact on Islamic Microfinance, many of which will serve as much more significant attainment predictors than any simple

correlation with Islamic Microfinance variable. A model that just includes popularity is likely to be a poor predictor of the result given the low R2 value.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.079
Nagelkerke	.084
McFadden	.030

Table 6.10: Pseudo R-Square Statistics Output 2

OUTPUT 3

Table displays a summary of case processing. For the variables used in the analysis, SPSS explicitly labels the variables and their values. To make sure you are analysing the variables you want to, it is crucial to do this. In this study we are modelling the Welfare of Islamic microfinance along with other variables related to client welfare and poverty alleviation, such as interest-bearing borrowing, unemployment, decreasing poverty, small businesses and micro-entrepreneurs, application procedures, financial situations, and interest-free loans.

Case Processing Summary			
		N	Marginal Percentage
Welfare	Strongly Disagree	17	4.4%
	Disagree	23	6.0%
	Neutral	55	14.3%
	Agree	161	41.8%
	Strongly Agree	129	33.5%
Interest Based Borrowing	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3%
	Disagree	9	2.3%
	Neutral	49	12.7%
	Agree	160	41.6%
	Strongly Agree	162	42.1%
Unemployment	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	15	3.9%
	Neutral	69	17.9%

	Agree	167	43.4%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%
Decreasing Poverty	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	69	17.9%
	Agree	154	40.0%
	Strongly Agree	132	34.3%
Small Business and Microentrepreneurs	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	72	18.7%
	Agree	159	41.3%
	Strongly Agree	121	31.4%
Application Process	Strongly Disagree	30	7.8%
	Disagree	41	10.6%
	Neutral	111	28.8%
	Agree	128	33.2%
	Strongly Agree	75	19.5%
Financial Circumstances	Strongly Disagree	6	1.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	68	17.7%
	Agree	162	42.1%
	Strongly Agree	123	31.9%
Interest Free Loan	Strongly Disagree	10	2.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	62	16.1%
	Agree	157	40.8%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%

Table 6.11: Case Processing Summary Output 3

Whether the model enhances our capacity for outcome prediction must be established before we begin examining the effects of each explanatory variable in the model. In this model by comparing a model without any explanatory variables against the explanatory variables in this model can be compared to those in models with all the explanatory variables to see which is

better. At the moment, this model only includes the explanatory variables Interest Based Borrowing, Unemployment, Decreasing Poverty, Small Business and Micro Entrepreneurs, Application Process, Financial Circumstances, and Interest Free Loan. We assess if the final model has considerably improved the fit to the data by comparing it to the baseline. The final model's and the baseline's -2 log-likelihood (-2LL) values are provided in the Model fitting Information table, and SPSS runs a chi-square test to determine whether the two models' -2LL values vary.

Model Fit				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	995.714			
Final	950.948	44.766	28	.023

Table 6.12: Model Fitting Information Output 3

The final model significantly outperforms the baseline intercept model, according to the significant chi-square value (p .005). Value and importance value are identical. However, in this instance, the research shows that the model provides a better forecast than if you were to simply guess at the marginal probability for the outcomes of the given variable categories, such as Islamic Microfinance, poverty alleviation, and customer welfare.

The following Goodness of Fit table the model's chi-square statistic is included in Pearson's (as well as another chi-square statistic based on the deviance). These statistics are used to determine whether the fitted model and observed data are consistent. The fit is good in this model, according to the null hypothesis. The data and the model predictions are similar, and you may conclude that you have a good model if we do not reject this hypothesis (i.e. if the p value is high). The model does not, however, fit the data well if you reject the assumption of a good fit, which is typically the case if (p.023). The findings of this study's research indicate that the model is a good fit the data very well since it is greater than the value of if $p < .005$).

Goodness-of-Fit

	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Pearson	1510.956	1432	.072
Deviance	935.227	1432	1.000

Link function: Logit.

Table 6.13 Goodness of fit Information Output 3

Greater R² values indicate that more of the variation in the outcome can be explained up to a maximum of 1. At the same time, R-square (the coefficient of determination) quantifies the proportion of variance in the outcome that can be accounted for by the explanatory variables. The same R² statistic as in linear regression cannot be estimated for logistic and ordinal regression models, hence three approximations are generated in their place.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.110
Nagelkerke	.118
McFadden	.044

Table 6.14: Pseudo R-Square Statistics Output 3

One can determine what a "good" R² number is depending on the nature of the outcome and the explanatory variables. Pseudo-R² values in this case (e.g., Nagelkerke = 11.8%), show that IM accounts for just a small percentage of the variation among PW variables. This is exactly what we would expect given the wide range of factors that have an impact on Islamic Microfinance, many of which will serve as much more significant attainment predictors than any simple correlation with Islamic Microfinance variable. A model that just includes popularity is likely to be a poor predictor of the result given the low R² value.

OUTPUT 4

Table displays a summary of case processing. For the variables used in the analysis, SPSS explicitly labels the variables and their values. To make sure you are analysing the variables you want to, it is crucial to do this. In this study we are modelling the religious reasons of Islamic microfinance along with other variables related to client welfare and poverty alleviation, such as interest-bearing borrowing, unemployment, decreasing poverty, small businesses and micro-entrepreneurs, application procedures, financial situations, and interest-free loans.

Case Processing Summary			
		N	Marginal Percentage
Religious Reasons	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3%
	Disagree	10	2.6%
	Neutral	34	8.8%
	Agree	173	44.9%
	Strongly Agree	163	42.3%
Interest Based Borrowing	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3%
	Disagree	9	2.3%
	Neutral	49	12.7%
	Agree	160	41.6%
	Strongly Agree	162	42.1%
Unemployment	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	15	3.9%
	Neutral	69	17.9%
	Agree	167	43.4%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%
Decreasing Poverty	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	69	17.9%
	Agree	154	40.0%
	Strongly Agree	132	34.3%
Small Business and Microentrepreneurs	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	72	18.7%
	Agree	159	41.3%
	Strongly Agree	121	31.4%
Application Process	Strongly Disagree	30	7.8%
	Disagree	41	10.6%
	Neutral	111	28.8%
	Agree	128	33.2%

	Strongly Agree	75	19.5%
Financial Circumstances	Strongly Disagree	6	1.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	68	17.7%
	Agree	162	42.1%
	Strongly Agree	123	31.9%
Interest Free Loan	Strongly Disagree	10	2.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	62	16.1%
	Agree	157	40.8%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%

Table 6.15: Case Processing Summary output 4

Whether the model enhances our capacity for outcome prediction must be established before we begin examining the effects of each explanatory variable in the model. In this model, the explanatory variables can be compared to those in models with all the explanatory variables to see which is better. At the moment, this model only includes the explanatory variables Interest Based Borrowing, Unemployment, Decreasing Poverty, Small Business and Micro Entrepreneurs, Application Process, Financial Circumstances, and Interest Free Loan. We assess if the final model has considerably improved the fit to the data by comparing it to the baseline. The final model's and the baseline's -2 log-likelihood (-2LL) values are provided in the Model fitting Information table, and SPSS runs a chi-square test to determine whether the two models' -2LL values vary.

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	824.359			
Final	802.007	22.352	28	.765

Table 6.16 Model Fitting Information Output

The final model significantly outperforms the baseline intercept model, according to the significant chi-square value (p .005). Value and importance value are identical. However, in this instance, the research shows that the model provides a better forecast than if you were to

simply guess at the marginal probability for the outcomes of the given variable categories, such as Islamic Microfinance, poverty alleviation, and customer welfare.

The following Goodness of Fit table the model's chi-square statistic is included in Pearson's (as well as another chi-square statistic based on the deviance). These statistics are used to determine whether the fitted model and observed data are consistent. The fit is good in this model, according to the null hypothesis. The data and the model predictions are similar, and you may conclude that you have a good model if we do not reject this hypothesis (i.e. if the p value is high). The model does not, however, fit the data well if you reject the assumption of a good fit, which is typically the case if (p.765). The findings of this study's research indicate that the model is a good fit the data very well since it is greater than the value of if $p < .005$).

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Pearson	1474.624	1432	.212
Deviance	789.059	1432	1.000

Table 6.17. Goodness of fit Information Output 4

Greater R² values indicate that more of the variation in the outcome can be explained up to a maximum of 1, while R-square (the coefficient of determination) quantifies the proportion of variance in the outcome that can be accounted for by the explanatory variables. The same R² statistic as in linear regression cannot be estimated for logistic and ordinal regression models, hence three approximations are generated in their place.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.056
Nagelkerke	.064
McFadden	.027

Table 6.18: Pseudo R-Square Statistics

Depending on the nature of the outcome and the explanatory variables, one can determine what a "good" R² number is. Pseudo-R² values in this case (e.g., Nagelkerke = 64%), show that IM accounts for just a small percentage of the variation among PW variables. This is exactly what we would expect given the wide range of factors that have an impact on Islamic Microfinance, many of which will serve as much more significant attainment predictors than any simple

correlation with Islamic Microfinance variable. A model that just includes religious reasons is likely to be a poor predictor of the result given the low R2 value.

OUTPUT 5

Table displays a summary of case processing. For the variables used in the analysis, SPSS explicitly labels the variables and their values. To make sure you are analysing the variables you want to, it is crucial to do this. In this study we are modelling the interest free loan of Islamic microfinance along with other variables related to client welfare and poverty alleviation, such as interest-bearing borrowing, unemployment, decreasing poverty, small businesses and micro-entrepreneurs, application procedures, financial situations, and interest-free loans.

Case Processing Summary			
		N	Marginal Percentage
Interest Free Loan	Strongly Disagree	11	2.9%
	Disagree	17	4.4%
	Neutral	39	10.1%
	Agree	174	45.2%
	Strongly Agree	144	37.4%
Interest Based Borrowing	Strongly Disagree	5	1.3%
	Disagree	9	2.3%
	Neutral	49	12.7%
	Agree	160	41.6%
	Strongly Agree	162	42.1%
Unemployment	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	15	3.9%
	Neutral	69	17.9%
	Agree	167	43.4%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%
Decreasing Poverty	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	69	17.9%

	Agree	154	40.0%
	Strongly Agree	132	34.3%
Small Business and Microentrepreneurs	Strongly Disagree	7	1.8%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	72	18.7%
	Agree	159	41.3%
	Strongly Agree	121	31.4%
Application Process	Strongly Disagree	30	7.8%
	Disagree	41	10.6%
	Neutral	111	28.8%
	Agree	128	33.2%
	Strongly Agree	75	19.5%
Financial Circumstances	Strongly Disagree	6	1.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	68	17.7%
	Agree	162	42.1%
	Strongly Agree	123	31.9%
Interest Free Loan	Strongly Disagree	10	2.6%
	Disagree	26	6.8%
	Neutral	62	16.1%
	Agree	157	40.8%
	Strongly Agree	130	33.8%

Table 6.19: Case Processing Summary Output 5

Whether the model enhances our capacity for outcome prediction must be established before we begin examining the effects of each explanatory variable in the model. In this model by comparing a model without any explanatory variables against the explanatory variables in this model can be compared to those in models with all the explanatory variables to see which is better. Now, this model only includes the explanatory variables Interest Based Borrowing, Unemployment, Decreasing Poverty, Small Business and Micro Entrepreneurs, Application Process, Financial Circumstances, and Interest Free Loan. We assess if the final model has considerably improved the fit to the data by comparing it to the baseline. The final model's and

the baseline's -2 log-likelihood (-2LL) values are provided in the Model fitting Information table, and SPSS runs a chi-square test to determine whether the two models' -2LL values vary.

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	905.628			
Final	886.925	18.703	28	.907

Table 6.20 Model Fitting Information Output

The final model significantly outperforms the baseline intercept model, according to the significant chi-square value ($p < .005$). Value and importance value are identical. However, in this instance, the research shows that the model provides a better forecast than if you were to simply guess at the marginal probability for the outcomes of the given variable categories, such as Islamic Microfinance, poverty alleviation, and customer welfare.

The following Goodness of Fit table includes the model's chi-square statistic in Pearson's (as well as another chi-square statistic based on the deviance). These statistics are used to determine whether the fitted model and observed data are consistent. The fit is good in this model, according to the null hypothesis. The data and the model predictions are similar, and you may conclude that you have a good model if we do not reject this hypothesis (i.e., if the p-value is high). The model does not, however, fit the data well if you reject the assumption of a good fit, which is typically the case if ($p > .907$). The findings of this study's research indicate that the model is a good fit for the data very well since it is greater than the value of if ($p < .005$).

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Pearson	1435.998	1432	.465
Deviance	871.204	1432	1.000

Table 6.21 Goodness of fit Information Output 5

Greater R² values indicate that more of the variation in the outcome can be explained up to a maximum of 1, while R-square (the coefficient of determination) quantifies the proportion of variance in the outcome that can be accounted for by the explanatory variables. The same R²

statistic as in linear regression cannot be estimated for logistic and ordinal regression models, hence three approximations are generated in their place.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.047
Nagelkerke	.052
McFadden	.020

Table 6.22: Pseudo R-Square Statistics Output 5

One can determine what a "good" R² number is depending on the nature of the outcome and the explanatory variables. Pseudo-R² values in this case (e.g., Nagelkerke = 52%) show that IM accounts for just a tiny percentage of the variation among PW variables. This is exactly what we would expect given the wide range of factors that have an impact on Islamic Microfinance, many of which will serve as much more significant attainment predictors than any simple correlation with the Islamic Microfinance variable. A model that just includes an interest-free loan is likely to be a poor predictor of the result, given the low R² value.

6.3 Limitations

During the data collection phase, the researcher experienced various problems. The timing of data collection posed a challenge for the author due to living in a different country, the COVID-19 pandemic, the time difference between the two countries, and other commitments of Akhuwat and Meezan's interviewees.

It was challenging to complete the questionnaire, as the microfinance clients were mostly microentrepreneurs who were not literate. As a result, several of the surveys we received were incomplete. The researcher assisted the microfinance clients and answered their questions about the questionnaire, which was a very time-consuming task. The informed microfinance clients answered the questionnaire independently but required assistance to understand its contents.

Microfinance clients in the Lahore city of Pakistan, provided the data from a few centres where the loans were given out. Due to the differences in cultural customs among microfinance consumers in other countries, the findings may not be applicable. Furthermore, nations employ a range of regulatory frameworks and techniques to safeguard the interests of financial service customers. Clients in a secular state, for example, may perceive loan interest rates differently than those in a religious state.

This research employed a mixed-methods approach, and it was challenging to do justice to both quantitative and qualitative aspects. It was time-consuming and financially not viable.

Chapter 7: Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Introduction

Microfinance was a significant advancement in the fight against poverty; nevertheless, because to numerous flaws, it is claimed that it did not reach the desired effects. Several factors contribute to this, including excessive interest rates, financial diversion, and insufficient personal development. IM is a novel concept in microfinance, with a slightly improved potential to reduce poverty, particularly in predominantly Muslim communities. Furthermore, the concept's products and ethical development initiatives have the potential to alleviate poverty and foster long-term progress.

Akhuwat serves as a compelling case study for alternative microfinance approaches that prioritise ethical lending and community empowerment. Its ongoing initiatives to mitigate poverty through interest-free loans may serve as a model for such projects in other areas. As the organisation progresses, further research is required to examine its long-term impacts and possible modifications in alternative contexts.

7.2 Conclusion

The research indicates that Islamic microfinance organisations has increasingly experienced institutional complexity. The organisation is shaped historically by the dominating institutional logic of religion in its institutional environment, and by influential actors such as the Shariah board in setting the standard to represent the logic of religion, keeping it Shariah compliant. The research indicates that while institutional complexity, the Islamic microfinance organisation is able to influence poverty alleviation in a significant manner.

7.3 Research contribution

This research is unique in a way that it attempts to integrate two distinct literatures. First, the research contributes to the literature of institutional logics in a religious organisation. (Peifer, 2014)(Greenwood, et al., 2011) following these two studies, an attempt was made to fill the gap in the literature on the institutional complexity of a religious organisation and its organisational responses. Piefer (2014) did research on a religious (Christian) organisation but did not consider the principles of religion in the study. This research aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the principles of Islam, which form the basis of operations and all other activities within the Islamic microfinance organisation. The study also attempted to get an understanding of the Shariah board through semi-structured interviews with Meezan employees. The Shariah board supervises the Islamic microfinance organisation to ensure it

remains Shariah compliant. This was not considered in the previous studies and adds to the literature. Shariah compliance helps the Islamic microfinance organisation not only in its operations but also in its performance. The second part of the contribution is to contribute to the literature on the performance of Islamic microfinance organisations in alleviating poverty. The research contributes to the literature, along with studies like (Malik, 2024) (Nazim Uddin, et al., 2023) and (Nadeem, et al., 2024) to reflect the benefits that IMFI provide, challenges they face, and new venues such as helping refugees or empowerment of women are discussed.

7.3.1 Contributions to knowledge

The findings of this study affirm that both Islamic and conventional microfinance variables exert a considerable positive influence on poverty alleviation. These findings offer valuable recommendations to policymakers and practitioners for refining their microfinance approaches to achieve poverty alleviation goals. To enhance the efficacy of microfinance in poverty alleviation, the government and policymakers should refine their strategies by transitioning from traditional microfinance to Islamic microfinance, which is more conducive to alleviating poverty due to the high interest rates imposed by conventional microfinance on impoverished clients. Moreover, it is essential to reduce bureaucratic obstacles in loan application processing, which can be achieved by implementing an information and communication technology (ICT) system and training microfinance clients on its use. Implementing the ICT system can enhance the microfinance loan application and repayment procedures. The government and policymakers must exert considerable effort to lower the interest rates imposed by microfinance firms, and they should enact definitive laws to enforce Shariah compliance inside the microfinance sector by getting supervision from a Shariah board. Implementing Islamic microfinance will mitigate unethical activities prevalent in traditional microfinance, such as the abusive conduct of loan officers towards clients and the seizure of assets belonging to microfinance clients due to the repayment failures of other borrowers.

7.3.2 Contribution to Practice

One of the primary approaches to benefiting the poor is to facilitate their access to suitable financial services and products. Islamic financial institutions need to consider some measures such as the establishment of new branches in area lacking financial services. Also, hiring and training local male as well as female staff to better reach and serve poor clients in them

communities have a crucial role in terms of poverty alleviation. Applying group guarantees or group lending should be an effective method in reaching the poor, reducing the risk of default, and lowering transaction costs.

Furthermore, designing a special lending program based on repeated loans of increasing size and duration is an important key task. Such program be supposed to encourages business expansion, provides an incentive for timely and complete repayment and, develops continuing relation with the financial institution; Providing complete financial services including savings or deposit mobilisation not just lending, reducing transactions costs in terms of money and time through simplifying credit application and approval procedures, and increasing the decision authority of field offices and finally providing standardized financial services and products which meet the various needs of borrowers with fees and no riba or interest should be taken in account.

7.3.3 Theoretical Contribution

This study theoretically contributes to the expanding literature utilising the institutional logics approach as a theoretical framework. In this context, religion has been recognised by Friedland and Alford (1991) and Thornton et al. (2012) as one of the institutional orders that form the 'interinstitutional system'. This connection was confined to a particular context: the impact of Christianity in Western civilisations. Thornton et al. (2012) acknowledged that this limited emphasis constitutes a significant prejudice. This study uniquely elucidates the role of Islam as a significant institutional framework affecting specific phenomena (accounting practices and standards) inside a context outside the Western world (Islamic world). This is regarded as an extension of ILP application to a novel empirical environment. Greenwood et al. (2011) suggest that the majority of ILP scholars have confined themselves to two assumptions on the approach to institutional complexity. These are (1) the limited scope by examining solely two logics and (2) the presumption of their incompatibility. Within this constrained framework, "the degree of complexity encountered may be undervalued or misconstrued; and the specific responses noted may not be accurately comprehended". This thesis addresses the request by Greenwood et al. (2011) (Peifer, 2014) for a more thorough investigation of contexts where many institutional logics, beyond two, may not only compete but also coexist and mutually reinforce one another. This thesis demonstrates that Islamic Microfinance organisation (Akhuwat) has been influenced by five institutional logics: Religion, Profession, Market, State, and Community, each possessing distinct rationalities and sources of legitimacy. It has also demonstrated how certain logics have collaborated to advance

their demands and bolster their perceived reason. This thesis contributes to the research on the institutional complexity underlying organisations.

Prior research has yielded inconsistent results about the efficacy of microfinance in alleviating poverty, demonstrating a range of effects that include positive, neutral, and negative outcomes. The author of the present study observed that the discrepancies in findings regarding the impact of microfinance on poverty alleviation may stem from factors such as the methodology employed for data analysis, the data collection approach used, the type of microfinance (Islamic or conventional) implemented, or the insufficient emphasis placed on the variables influencing the relationship between microfinance and poverty alleviation. This study investigates the effects of Islamic microfinance on poverty alleviation to determine if it has an influence on poverty alleviation, thus contributing to the existing literature on microfinance and poverty alleviation addressed a significant gap in research by carefully comparing Islamic and conventional microfinance for poverty alleviation, offering merely providing instead of just basic descriptions of the results. Empirical data substantiate the comparison, demonstrating that the interest-free strategy offers distinct advantages in poverty alleviation. This research has enhanced our understanding of institutional theory by showing the differences between Islamic and conventional microfinance, particularly how changes such as an interest-free model that aligns with cultural and ethical values can lead to more effective poverty reduction outcomes. These results enhance existing theoretical frameworks and provide a solid foundation for future studies examining the contextual dynamics of microfinance programs.

7.4 Research Implications

This study's findings affirm that Islamic microfinance variables significantly contribute to poverty alleviation. These findings offer practical guidance to policymakers and practitioners on enhancing their microfinance techniques to achieve poverty alleviation goals.

Prior research has yielded inconclusive results regarding the efficacy of microfinance in alleviating poverty, indicating that its impact varies among positive, neutral, and negative outcomes. The discrepancies in findings regarding the effects of microfinance on poverty alleviation may stem from factors such as the methodology employed for data analysis, the approach to data collection, the type of microfinance used (Islamic or conventional), or the insufficient emphasis placed on the variables influencing the relationship between microfinance and poverty alleviation.

This study has addressed an important gap in research by carefully comparing Islamic and conventional microfinance in how they help reduce poverty, offering detailed insights instead

of just basic descriptions of their results. Empirical data substantiate the comparison, demonstrating that the interest-free strategy offers distinct advantages in poverty alleviation. This research has improved our understanding of institutional theory by explaining the differences between Islamic and conventional microfinance, showing how features like the interest-free model that fits with cultural and ethical values help achieve better results in reducing poverty. These results enhance existing theoretical frameworks and provide a solid foundation for future studies examining the contextual dynamics of microfinance programs.

7.5 Recommendations

The discrepancies in findings regarding the effects of microfinance on poverty alleviation may stem from factors such as the methodology employed for data analysis, the approach to data collection, the type of microfinance used (Islamic or conventional), or the insufficient emphasis placed on the variables influencing the relationship between microfinance and poverty alleviation.

Future research may address issues with regional and institutional implications, aiming to enhance our understanding of the contributions of microfinance and mitigate the impact of external economic variables on the findings. Furthermore, future research should use a variety of methodologies to evaluate the impact of microfinance on poverty alleviation and analyse numerous processes that may improve microfinance programs.

7.6 Limitations

There are numerous limitations. It is challenging to arrange interviews and questionnaire, especially if you are not living in the same country.

This study addresses a significant gap in research by carefully comparing Islamic and conventional microfinance in terms of their effectiveness in reducing poverty, providing detailed insights rather than merely providing basic descriptions of their results. Empirical data substantiate the comparison, demonstrating that the interest-free strategy offers distinct advantages in poverty alleviation. This research has enhanced our understanding of institutional theory by clarifying the differences between Islamic and conventional microfinance, illustrating how features such as the interest-free model, which aligns with cultural and ethical values, contribute to more effective poverty reduction. These results enhance current theoretical frameworks and provide a solid foundation for future studies examining the contextual dynamics of microfinance programs

Furthermore, countries utilise a variety of regulatory frameworks and strategies to protect consumers of financial services. Clients living in secular states may hold different views on loan interest rates compared to those in religious states. Future research could investigate specific regional and institutional factors that may provide a more profound understanding of how microfinance operates, ensuring that external economic influences do not skew the results. Additionally, subsequent studies should adopt various methodologies to evaluate the impact of microfinance on poverty alleviation and explore the different mechanisms by which it could enhance microfinance initiatives.

7.8 Future research Suggestions

More research on Islamic microfinance, not only on the national level but also at the international level, as a significant proportion of Muslims originate from the Muslim world, Islamic finance should focus more on providing alternative financing for empowering refugees. A viable financing structure for refugee entrepreneurship must address the classic trade-off between sustainability and outreach. By integrating funds from the private sector, philanthropic organisations, and government support, Islamic blended microfinance offers potential solutions. However, any policy-oriented proposal should address the competing institutional logic issue amongst the institutions involved in the process.

The logic of the three agents and religion (Islam) converges in the dimensions of contextuality and temporality, where the private sector is adjusting not only towards material sustainability but also towards outreach. This makes blended finance an appropriate mechanism for financing development. The refugee financing payoff should facilitate risk-sharing between the private sector and philanthropic organisations in both favourable and adverse economic conditions. Integration with philanthropic instruments like *waqf* and *zakat* also enhances refugees' entrepreneurial skills and provides an insurance mechanism.

Research may investigate the perspectives of Rohingya refugees about Islamic microfinance. Comprehending their aspirations, challenges, and perspectives helps facilitate the formulation of effective replies. The Islamic microfinance initiatives for Rohingya refugees can be statistically assessed. This may encompass the analysis of socioeconomic outcomes, such as income generation, employment creation, business development, and the social integration and empowerment of refugees.

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Appendix

Ethical Approval

20/04/2021

Dear Abdul Shakoor Safdar Hashmi,

Your application 16283: The Institutional complexity of a Religious Microfinance institution: A case study of an Islamic Microfinance Institution (Akhawat), submission 13548, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Name of the participant: -

Title of the research project: The Institutional complexity of a Religious Microfinance institution: A case study of an Islamic Microfinance Institution (Akhuwat)

Main investigator and contact details: Abdul Shakoor Safdar Hashmi School of Business and Creative Industries University of the West of Scotland, [REDACTED]

Members of the research team: Dr.Nasir Kolade and Professor Heather Tarbert

I confirm that I agree to take part in the above research. I have read the participant information sheet which is attached to this consent form. I understand what my role will be in this research work, and all my questions/clarifications have been answered to my satisfaction.

I understand that I am free to withdraw from participating in this research at any time I want, for any reason and without prejudice

I have been adequately informed that the confidentiality of the information I provide will be safeguarded.

I am free to ask any question at any time before and during the study.

I have been provided with a copy of this form and the participant information sheet

Data protection, I agree to the University of the West of Scotland processing personal data which I have supplied. I agree to the processing of such data for any purposes connected with the Research project as an outline to me.

Name of Participant.....

Signed

Date

YOU WILL BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS FORM TO KEEP If you would like to withdraw from the research, please complete the form below and return it to the main investigator named above

I WISH TO WITHDRAW FROM THIS STUDY

Singed

Date

The following pages have been redacted due to containing personal details of participants.

Participation Information sheet

The Institutional complexity of a Religious Microfinance institution: A case study of an Islamic Microfinance Institution (Akhuwat)

Researcher: Mr Abdul Shakoor Safdar Hashmi

Dear Participant

Please take some time to read through the information sheet. If you have any questions at any point, please do not hesitate to ask the researcher, Abdul Shakoor Safdar Hashmi or contact him at any stage later at [REDACTED]

Synopsis

You have been invited to take part in a Doctorate (DBA) research study to explore religion as an institutional logic and its role in shaping the organisational identity of an Islamic microfinance organisation and to explore the response of an Islamic microfinance organisation towards multiple institutional logics while experiencing institutional complexity.

What you have been asked to do

You have been asked to participate in a confidential and anonymous face-to-face interview session which will last around 30 minutes. This interview will be arranged for a specified time, date, and location according to your convenience.

The interview session initially includes the basic questions related to institutional logics Akhuwat was facing and its response towards the new institutional logic it is facing. It will also include questions on religion, how religion has shaped the organisational identity of Akhuwat, the difference between Akhuwat and a conventional microfinance institution and Akhuwat contribution toward the alleviation of poverty.

In the end, you can also provide any suggestions towards the study, and you can also ask questions from the researcher for your clarification.

Your Data

To enhance the accuracy of the data, the researcher will record the audio recording of the interview with your permission. Also, with your permission, I may include some quotes from your interview to enhance the reliability of the collected data and to help the researcher to emphasise a specific point which helps to provide more insights towards the results of the study. These interviews will be anonymised, and great care will be taken to ensure that any wording or quotation used will not pose any potential risk to you or the organisation.

The notes and recordings will be kept anonymised and will be stored in an encrypted folder with password protection on it. The recordings and data will only be accessible to the researcher Abdul Shakoor Safdar Hashmi and the supervisory team.

Lastly, your participation in the study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to answer any question. You may withdraw your participation at any time or after the interview session.

Thank you for your kind co-operation.

Abdul Shakoor Safdar Hashmi

Doctorate in Business Administration (DBA)

Business School

University of the West of Scotland

Email: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

INTERVIEW QUESTIONS FOR AKHUWAT

The Institutional complexity of a Religious Microfinance institution: A case study of an Islamic Microfinance Institution (Akhuwat)

1. What is your current post in this organisation?

2. What is your opinion of institutional logics, or do you have any knowledge of institutional logic?

3. How many institutional logics is Akhuwat influenced by?

Prompt: What is the role of religion as institutional logic in shaping the organisational identity of Akhuwat?

4. How Religion (Islam) as an institutional logic affects Akhuwat's organisational culture?

Prompt: Experience of Akhuwat as a religious microfinance organisation?

5. How does your organisation differ from a conventional microfinance institution?

Prompt: Affiliation with a denomination

6. Who is the supervisory body that oversees Akhuwat's engagement with Meezan?

Prompt: What is their role?

7. Has the engagement with Meezan affected your organisation's institutional logic?

Prompt: Decision making of Akhuwat

8. How has the logic of commerce affected your organisation?

Prompt: Balance between socially responsible and generating profit.

9. Does your institution have a specific target audience and why?

Prompt: do they have to be Muslims and also Shariah-compliant?

10.Has institutional complexity affected the effectiveness of Akhuwat?

Prompt: Organisational Identity

11.In your opinion how successful has Akhuwat been in contributing towards the alleviation of poverty?

INTERVIEWS QUESTIONS FOR MEEZAN

1.What is your current post in this organisation?

2. When did you start working in this organisation?

3. What services are provided by Meezan to Akhuwat?

4.What is the role of Meezan?

Prompt: role of Shariah board

5. How do these services help Akhuwat to be Shariah Compliant?

6.What change do you see in Akhuwat after engagement with Meezan?

7.How has the institutional logic of commerce affected the organisational identity of Akhuwat after engagement with Meezan?

Prompt: Shift from being a profit to a non-profit organisation.

8. What has been the response of Akhuwat after facing commercial logic?

Close ended Questionnaire

To investigate the performance of Islamic microfinance organisations, their effects on poverty alleviation and the welfare of their clients.

Q1. What is your age?

18-25

26-35

36-45

46-55

56 or over

Q2. What is your gender?

Male

Female

Prefer not to say

Q3. Religion

Muslim

Hindu

Christianity

Q4. Please indicate your highest educational qualification

Matriculation

Intermediate/F.Sc./F. A

Undergraduate/B.Sc.

Masters/MSc

Doctorate/PhD

Q5. What is your occupation?

Manager

Academic

Professional

Microentrepreneur

Businessmen/women

Student

Q6. Which one of the following categories best describes your monthly income?

0 to Rs10,000

Rs10,00 to Rs20,000

Rs20,000 to Rs30,000

Rs30,000 to Rs40,000

Rs40,000 to Rs50,000

Over Rs50,000

Q7. Are you familiar with the term Micro-Finance?

Yes No

Q8. Are you familiar with the term Islamic Micro-Finance?

Yes No

Q9. Which factors motivated you to deal with an Islamic Microfinance Institution (Akhuwat)?

Shariah compliance (Islamic Law) Ethical concerns Returns Interest free loans
 Interest free borrowing

Q10. When you choose Akhuwat, what sources of information did you choose? Please tick all that apply.

Recommended by Family and Friends Local Place of worship (Mosque/Church)
 Internet Media (TV, radio, newspaper)

Q11. Please indicate by crossing the box, how strongly you agree or disagree with each statement using the scale provided.

SCALE						
<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>		
<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>		
Islamic Micro-Finance Institution (Akhuwat)						
1	Islamic Microfinance Institution are becoming popular among the Muslim Countries especially in Pakistan.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2	Islamic microfinance Institution (Akhuwat) is positively influencing social relations and income generating activities in Pakistan.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3	Islamic Microfinance Institutions have greater significance over conventional Microfinance regarding welfare to their clients.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4	Getting interest free loans from an Islamic Microfinance Institution is a priority due to religious reasons.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

5	Interest free loans which are Shariah compliant have a positive impact on the society.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Poverty Alleviation and Welfare of the Client</i>						
6	Poverty in Pakistan is because of the financial system as it is not interest free.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>
7	Poverty in Pakistan can be alleviated or decreased with the help of Islamic Microfinance Institution (Akhawat).	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>
8	Poverty is considered as the root cause for Un-Employment in Pakistan.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>
9	Islamic Microfinance Institution (Akhawat) are playing a positive role in decreasing poverty.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>
10	Developing microentrepreneurs through help from Islamic microfinance Institution (Akhawat) can be helpful in eradicating poverty from Pakistan.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>
11	Did your financial circumstance improved after getting an interest free loan from Akhawat?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>
12	Borrowing an interest free loan had a positive impact on your social life and welfare.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>

	Financial sector in U.S.	quantitative analysis	logic facilitates professional group status mobility programmes.
Kitchener, 2002	Field 1999–2000 Health care in U.S.	Case study	The transition from professional to market logic alters the foundation of legitimacy and leads to the collapse of business mergers.
Rao, Monin, & Durand, 2003	Field 1970–1997 Elite cuisine in France	Historical narrative and quantitative analysis	Identity shifts result in the changing of logic and roles.
Thornton, 2004	Industry 1958–1990 Higher-education publishing in U.S.	Historical narrative and quantitative analysis	Institutional logics at the societal level shape organisational attention structures and decision-making processes.
Zajac & Westphal, 2004.	Field 1980–1994 Financial sector in U.S.	Quantitative analysis	The change from corporate logic to agency logic affects how activities are seen and how the financial markets react to them.
Reay & Hinings, 2005	Field 1988–1998 Health care in Canada	Case study	The transition from professional to commercial logic results in profound transformation. The continuation of the prior prevailing reasoning is emphasised.
Thornton, Jones, & Kury, 2005	Industry 1950s–1990s Accounting, architecture, and higher-education publishing in U.S.	Historical comparative analysis	The shifts in institutional logic have an effect on patterns of institutional stability and organisational governance change.

Reay & Hinings, 2009	Field 1994–2008 Health care in Canada	Case study	The persistence of an array of logic is emphasised. Its management through field actor interaction is examined.
Purdy & Gray, 2009	Field 1982–2004 Alternative dispute resolution in U.S.	Case study and qualitative content analysis	Researchers look at how competing logics spread and what makes it possible for different logics to stay around in the same field.
Battilana & Dorado, 2010	Organization 1997, 1998, 2000 Microfinance sector in Bolivia	Comparative case study	In hybrid organisations, the confluence of two opposing logics is emphasised. The criteria under which hybridity is maintained by organisations are examined.
Shipilov, Greve, & Rowley, 2010	Organization 1999–2005 Public companies in Canada	Quantitative analysis	In the framework of governance practises, the diffusion of institutions and their underlying logics in numerous waves is explored.
Greenwood, Diaz, Li, & Lorente, 2010	Industry 1994–2000 Manufacturing sector in Spain	Historical narrative and quantitative analysis	How organisations respond to broad market logic is influenced by regional state logic and family logic. Religion's involvement is implicated.
Dunn & Jones, 2010	Field 1910–2005 Medical education in U.S.	Historical narrative and quantitative analysis	Multiple logics are supported by different groups and interests. Logics change over time and create dynamic tensions.
Miller, Le-Breton-Miller, & Lester, 2010.	Organization 1996–2000 Fortune 1000 in U.S.	Quantitative analysis	Variability in role identities and logic reflects disparities in the strategic behaviours of

Glynn & Lounsbury, 2005	Field 1995–1998 Atlanta symphony orchestra	Quantitative content analysis	The transformation of institutional logic influences the discourse of reviewers and their evaluations of performances.
Djelic & Ainamo, 2005	Field 19th century–2004 Global mobile telephony	Historical narrative and comparative case studies	The process of translating logic between disciplines is studied. The dynamics of hybridization and logic coexistence are emphasised.
Meyer & Hammerschmid, 2006	Individual 2003 Public sector in Austria	Quantitative analysis	The lexicon of individuals for asserting their social identities reflects the shift from legalistic-bureaucratic reasoning to management logic.
Lounsbury, 2007	Field 1944–1985 Financial sector in U.S.	Quantitative analysis	Competing logics influence the diffusion of a new practise by causing variation in organisational behaviour and practise adoption.
Luo, 2007	Individual 1995 Citizens in Germany, Luxembourg, UK	Quantitative analysis	Individuals' views and interests toward the constant learning model for employee training are influenced by national institutional logic.
Marquis & Lounsbury, 2007	Field 1994–2002 Banking sector in U.S.	Quantitative analysis	Competing logics enable institutional change resistance by fostering new types of professional entrepreneurship.

			family managers and lone founders.
Nigam & Ocasio, 2010	Field 1991–1995 Health care in U.S.	Case study and quantitative content analysis	Field-level logics are made and used because of how attention and perception of the environment work together.
Lok, 2010	Field 1984–2004 Corporations in UK	Historical case study and discourse analysis	The function of identity formation in the institutionalisation process identity work that paradoxically accommodates and opposes the implications of new institutional logics on practise and identity.
Pache & Santos, 2011	Organization 2007–2008 Social sector in France	Comparative case study	In response to competing logics, organisations embrace a combination of unaltered practises from each rationale.
Edwards & Delbridge, 2011	Field 1960s–present Superyacht industry	Historical case study	The conflict and interdependence of market and professional logics are emphasised. Logics coexist with varied degrees of (in)compatibility and coexist in conflict.

Table 1 Summary of Studies on Institutional Logics and Institutional Complexity.

(Greenwood, et al., 2011)

The following pages have been redacted due to containing personal

